

University of the West of Scotland

School of Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences

Doctoral Thesis

**Interferometrically Enhanced
Modulation for Tunable Diode Laser-
based Photoacoustic Spectroscopy**

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Interferometrically Enhanced Modulation for Tunable Diode Laser- based Photoacoustic Spectroscopy

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I declare that this doctoral thesis is my own work and I have documented all sources and material used.

No portion of this work referred to in this thesis has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification of this or any other university or institute of learning.

Hamburg, 3 December 2025

Abstract

Methane, ethane, and propane are key targets for atmospheric monitoring and industrial process control due to their roles as greenhouse gases and natural gas constituents. Photoacoustic spectroscopy (PAS) combined with tunable diode lasers (TDLs) offer a highly sensitive, selective, and compact approach for their detection. However, due to the need of laser modulation, a fundamental phenomenon arises from the intrinsic coupling between emission intensity and wavelength in semiconductor lasers: wavelength modulation inevitably produces residual amplitude modulation (RAM), and vice versa. This coupling distorts spectral features and therefore impede quantitative analysis, particularly in multi-component gas mixtures where overlapping absorption bands are common.

This study introduces and validates the novel concept of interferometrically enhanced (IE) modulation, which uses a Mach-Zehnder interferometer to partially decouple intensity and wavelength modulation in TDL-based PAS. A comprehensive analytical model has been developed to enable direct frequency-domain calculation of the interferometer output. Experimental implementation has demonstrated an 83% reduction in residual wavelength modulation during intensity modulation. Additionally, a detailed characterisation of the photoacoustic sensor is provided, including the analysis of the magnitude and phase responses of the acoustic signal in an H-type resonant photoacoustic cell. Finally, multivariate analysis using partial least squares regression (PLSR) with feature selection is applied to multicomponent gas mixtures (methane, ethane and propane), demonstrating detection limits in the low ppm range.

The methodology combines the fundamental physical theory, theoretical modelling, experimental validation and data-driven analysis. IE modulation is described analytically and realised experimentally using a distributed feedback interband cascade laser (DFB-ICL) operating at $3.35\ \mu\text{m}$. A free-beam Mach-Zehnder interferometer with tilting-window phase control has been constructed and characterised. Photoacoustic measurements are performed using $1f$ and $2f$ wavelength modulation with lock-in detection. Both the in-phase and quadrature signal components are analysed to isolate and

characterise RAM contributions. To quantify concentrations of multiple components, a simplex lattice experimental design is employed to generate training, validation and test datasets spanning from 0 to 100 ppm per component. Variance-covariance analysis is then used to identify wavelength features of high predictive importance and PLSR models are developed to quantify gas concentrations.

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Abbreviations

CV – cross-validation
CW – continuous wave
DFB – distributed feedback
DFT – discrete fourier transform
ECM – electret condenser microphone
EOM – electro-optic modulator
FKM – fluoro-elastomer, German "Fluorkautschuk Material"
FPGA – field-programmable gate array
FWHM – full width at half maximum
ICL – interband cascade laser
IE – interferometrically enhanced
IIR – infinite impulse response
IM – intensity modulation
InAsSb – indium arsenide antimonide
IR – infrared
LDD – laser diode driver
LIA – lock-in amplifier
LN – lithium niobate
LOD – limit of detection
LOQ – limit of quantification
LT – lithium tantalate
MEMS – microelectromechanical systems
MFC – mass flow controller
MZI – Mach-Zehnder interferometer
MZM – Mach-Zehnder modulator
NIPALS – nonlinear iterative partial least squares
NOAA – National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
OPO – optical parametric oscillator
PA – photoacoustic
PAC – photoacoustic cell

P&ID – piping and instrumentation diagram
PAS – photoacoustic spectroscopy
PC – principal component
PCA – principal component analysis
PCR – principal component regression
PD – photodetector
PLS – partial least squares
PLSR – partial least squares regression
PS – phase shifter
PT – photothermal
PTFE – polytetrafluoroethylene
QCL – quantum cascade laser
QTF – quartz tuning fork
QW – quantum well
RAM – residual amplitude modulation
RMS – root mean square
RMSE – root mean square error
SNR – signal-to-noise ratio
TDL – tunable diode laser
TDLS – tunable diode laser spectroscopy
TEC – thermoelectric cooler
UV – ultraviolet
VIS – visible
VOC – volatile organic compound
WG – waveform generator
WM – wavelength modulation
WMS – wavelength modulation spectroscopy

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Methane (CH_4), ethane (C_2H_6) and propane (C_3H_8) are light alkanes that play key roles in both climate and environmental science, as well as in the energy industry. Although a molecule of methane has a relatively short lifespan of just 7 to 12 years in the atmosphere. It is a very potent greenhouse gas and the second-largest contributor to global warming after carbon dioxide (CO_2). Greenhouse gases absorb infrared radiation emitted from the Earth's surface, trapping heat in the atmosphere that would otherwise go out into space. CO_2 can exist for hundreds of years or more [8]. The 100-year global warming potential of methane is still 28 relative to CO_2 [9]. Methane originates from both natural sources and human activities. It is estimated that 60 % of today's methane emissions result from human activities. The sources with the highest contributions are agriculture, fossil fuels exploration and decomposing landfill waste. Natural processes account for the remaining 40 %, with wetlands being the largest natural source [8]. Figure 1-1 shows the development of the methane concentrations in the atmosphere since 1983, as measured by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) from a network of air sampling sites distributed around the globe. From 1983 concentrations of atmospheric methane increased by 24 %, reaching a total concentration of 1.94 ppm in 2025 [1]. The rising methane concentration over the last decades has been explained in recent studies as a result of changes in sources and sinks [10–12].

Ethane and propane occur at much lower concentrations in the atmosphere than methane (roughly three orders of magnitude), yet they play a key role in tropospheric chemistry and pollution formation. Their atmospheric lifetimes are short, ethane

Figure 1-1: Monthly measurements of methane concentrations in the atmosphere from 1983 to 2025, as measured by NOAA from a globally-distributed network of air sampling sites [1].

is around two months and propane is around two weeks, because they both react readily with the hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$) [13–15]. Through their oxidation, C_2H_6 and C_3H_8 alkanes contribute to the formation of tropospheric ozone and influence the atmosphere’s oxidative capacity; consequently, they are important tracers for emission source attribution and help understanding photochemical pollution pathways [13–15]. Global emissions of ethane and propane are significant and include both natural and anthropogenic components, with fossil fuel activities and biomass burning being among the largest contributors [16,17].

From an industrial perspective, methane, ethane, and propane are the primary constituents of natural gas and are key to petrochemical processes, such as ethane cracking to produce ethylene. Accurate, high-sensitivity monitoring of these species, therefore, supports resource evaluation, process control, emissions detection, and safety, including leak detection and prevention, in the oil and gas sector [18–20].

Photoacoustic spectroscopy (PAS) is an innovative laser-based measurement method that experienced an innovation boost by recent developments. A typical application of PAS is the detection of atmospheric methane or nitrous oxide (N_2O) using quantum cascade lasers (QCLs). Sensitivities in the range of a few ppb have been achieved [21]. Future potential applications of PAS include medical diagnostics, imaging

and gas phase analysis. Notably, its ability to distinguish optical absorption from light scattering makes it particularly effective in the analysis of atmospheric aerosols [22].

1.2 State of the Art

While quantitative PAS has been known since 1938, the first documented photoacoustic (PA) measurements were already made by Alexander Graham Bell in 1881 [23]. All PA instruments, from Bell's earliest efforts to today's state-of-the-art instruments, consist of three main components: A modulated light source, a PA cuvette, and a sound detection device. PAS instrumentation benefits particularly from recent advances in the following areas:

- New laser light sources such as diode lasers, QCLs and interband cascade lasers (ICLs) provide tunable radiation with a narrow emission wavelength and relatively high power [24–27].
- New transducer technology such as microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) microphones [28,29] or quartz tuning forks are sensitive to very low sound pressure levels [30,31].
- Data processing, such as digital lock-in amplification, allows the PA signal to be separated from noisy background signal [32,33]. The continuous development of field-programmable gate arrays (FPGAs) in recent years has led to increased capability in digital lock-in amplifiers (LIAs) [34].

These advances have made PAS competitive with other commonly used absorption techniques such as single/multi-pass absorption, fluorescence, refractive index measurements and electrochemical detection [22].

In particular, the use of tunable diode lasers, QCLs and ICLs has led to the widespread use of wavelength modulation spectroscopy (WMS), where the wavelength is periodically modulated by the laser current. The analytical framework of WMS differs from classical spectroscopic methods in that the recorded signal is no longer directly proportional to the transmission/absorption of the sample, but rather to its change in transmission/absorption. The modulation behaviour of the laser also influences the

resulting signal. As the wavelength cannot be completely separated from the emission intensity, this type of modulation comes with new challenges [35,36].

One of these challenges is a phenomenon known as residual amplitude modulation (RAM), which arises from the intrinsic coupling between the wavelength and intensity of emission in semiconductor lasers. When the laser current is modulated to vary the wavelength, the optical power inevitably varies simultaneously, introducing an unwanted modulation of the intensity that distorts the derivative spectra. Furthermore, the phase relationship between intensity and wavelength modulation varies with modulation frequency and differs between laser types, which makes implementing universal compensation strategies difficult.

1.3 Aims and Objectives

In the scope of this dissertation a PA sensor for WMS for the detection of trace levels of methane, ethane and propane in multi-component gas mixtures is developed with the aim to *improve the state of the art of photoacoustic spectroscopy with WMS* and to show further research potential. In order to achieve this aim, the following main objectives have been established:

- To explore the impact of RAM on the PA signal strength in WMS.
- To identify strategies to effectively reduce the impact of RAM on the PA spectrum in WMS.
- To introduce the concept of interferometrically enhanced modulation in WMS.
- To validate the extent to which RAM affects the prediction accuracy of partial least squares regression (PLSR) models in wavelength modulation (WM) PAS.

Secondary objectives are:

- To identify the spectral regions within the lasers emission wavelength that enable accurate detection of methane, ethane, and propane in multi-component gas mixtures.
- To quantify the detection limits for methane, ethane and propane of the presented setup.

1.4 Outline

Firstly, the fundamentals of photoacoustic spectroscopy are presented. This is followed by a presentation of the findings and results of the following key themes: the development of a PA sensor for WM tunable diode laser spectroscopy (TDLS), the introduction of a novel interferometrically enhanced modulation concept and the quantitative PA spectrum analysis. Finally, conclusions are drawn from the overall research presented and limitations are discussed.

In Chapter 2 (Fundamentals) the theoretical background of PAS is presented. The development of PA sensors requires a fundamental understanding of infrared (IR) spectroscopy, the PA effect and the three main components of a PA based instrument: A modulated light source, a photoacoustic cell (PAC) and a sound detector. In addition, modern PA instrumentation requires electronic signal amplification, sampling and processing. There is a particular emphasis on measuring trace gases, such as methane, ethane and propane. Special attention is also given to the implications of intensity modulation (IM) and WM in TDLS.

In Chapter 3 (Design of the PA Sensor) the development of the tunable diode laser (TDL)-based PAS sensor for the detection of methane, ethane and propane is described. The PA sensor is designed based on the previously introduced principles. Its individual components are characterised and its performance with respect to the limit of detection (LOD) of methane, ethane and propane is assessed. Emphasis is given to the magnitude and phase of the PA signal, both for the resonance behaviour of the PAC and for the PA spectra recorded with WMS.

In Section 4 (Interferometrically Enhanced Modulation) the novel concept of interferometrically enhanced modulation is introduced. The interferometrically enhanced modulation is achieved using a combination of an ICL and a Mach-Zehnder interferometer (MZI). The behaviour of the Mach-Zehnder modulated signal in the time and frequency domain is first described, followed by the concept of interferometrically enhanced modulation in TDLS. The results of this chapter are published as *Mach-Zehnder Modulator Output in Time and Frequency Domain – Calculation*

and Experimental Confirmation [37] and *Interferometrically Enhanced Intensity and Wavelength Modulation in Tunable Diode Laser Spectroscopy* [38].

In Chapter 5 (Quantitative PA Spectrum Analysis) the quantification of the trace gases methane, ethane and propane is performed using PLSR. After an introduction to multivariate analysis methods in general and PLSR in particular, the experimental design for calibration, validation and testing of the PA sensor is explained. The focus here is not only on the pure accuracy of the PLSR prediction, but also on insights from the analysis itself, such as the importance of individual wavelengths for the algorithm.

In Chapter 6 (Conclusions) conclusions are drawn from the results presented for the WM TDL-based PAS sensor, the implications for multivariate data analysis, and the potential of interferometrically enhanced modulation. An outlook on required future research and development efforts is given.

Chapter 2

Fundamentals

2.1 Introduction

This chapter establishes the theoretical and methodological foundations for TDL-based PAS. The entire process of PA signal generation and detection is examined, from laser emission through light-matter interaction, acoustic wave generation, resonant amplification and phase-sensitive signal processing. Additionally, mathematical frameworks for interferometric modulation and multivariate spectral analysis are presented.

The chapter begins with TDLS, introducing direct absorption and wavelength-modulation approaches. It highlights the fundamental challenge of RAM, which arises from the intrinsic coupling between emission wavelength and intensity in semiconductor lasers, and motivates subsequent developments in interferometrically enhanced modulation (see Section 2.2).

PAS is then examined from Alexander Graham Bell's 1880 discovery to modern implementations using TDLs. Unlike conventional optical techniques that detect transmitted or reflected photons, PAS directly measures absorbed energy through acoustic signals generated by non-radiative relaxation. The complete signal-generation pathway encompasses modulated radiation emission, photoexcitation, acoustic wave generation, resonant amplification in H-type cells and phase-sensitive detection (see Section 2.3).

distributed feedback (DFB)-ICLs provide a spectrally narrow linewidth, wavelength tunability and access to strong absorption features of methane, ethane and propane at a wavelength of around 3.35 μm . Methane is used as a detailed example here. Spectral line-broadening mechanisms (natural, Doppler and collisional) directly influence the

spectral resolution. The dependencies of temperature and pressure on line-broadening are examined (see Section 2.3.1 and Section 2.3.3).

Acoustic wave generation, resonant amplification and transducer selection are presented. Phase-sensitive detection through lock-in amplification extracts small signals from noise, with phase information enabling resonance tracking and the separation of wavelength modulation from residual amplitude modulation. The damped harmonic-oscillator model describes the phase relationship between laser modulation and the PA response (see Section 2.3.5, Section 2.3.7 and Section 2.3.8).

The history and functionality of the MZI, which is of central importance for interferometrically enhanced modulation, is also described. Modulation is achieved by varying the phase difference between the split beam paths, and thus alternating between constructive and destructive interference (see Section 2.4).

Finally, the foundations of multivariate data analysis are presented, including variance-covariance analysis, linear regression and dimensionality reduction techniques that establish the basis for partial least squares regression in multicomponent gas quantification (see Section 2.5).

2.2 Tunable Diode Laser Spectroscopy

A common laser-based absorption technique used for the quantitative measurement of gas-phase species is TDLS. In this technique the emission wavelength of a laser diode with a narrow linewidth is scanned over an individual gas absorption peak [39]. A typical setup consists of a laser diode, a photodetector and an optical component that facilitates the interaction between light and gas. Standard approaches for TDLS include direct spectroscopy as well as WMS. In direct spectroscopy the laser emission is scanned across one or more gas absorption lines by adjusting the injection current of the laser diode. The gas absorption can then be determined by subtracting a zero reference measurement. In WMS a sinusoidal modulation is applied to scan the laser-emitted radiation through an absorption feature of the substance to be detected. The interaction of the modulated radiation with the absorption line generates a signal at specific harmonics of the modulation frequency. This signal is directly proportional

to the absorption [40]. More detailed information on TDLS can be found elsewhere [39–42].

In addition to purely optical measurements, TDLS can be combined with various detection techniques, such as photothermal (PT) or PA measurements, to enhance sensitivity and selectivity. In this study, TDLS is employed alongside PAS measurements. Section 2.3 provides a comprehensive discussion of PAS functionality.

The radiation intensity and emission wavelength of a semiconductor laser change as a function of the laser current. With its narrow emission bandwidth, this tunable quasi-monochromatic light source is well suited for spectroscopic applications, which are widely known as TDLS [43].

In comparison to a continuous change in laser current, the use of a modulated current offers the advantage of greatly improved signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) through the phase-sensitive detection of the emitted radiation. This can be accomplished with a LIA, which allows for the recognition of even the smallest features of the spectrum [44].

A number of methods may be used to modulate laser radiation. Mechanical modulators are straightforward to implement and are suitable for use in the ultraviolet (UV), visible (VIS), and the entire IR range. However, they are typically less frequency-stable compared to electro-optical modulation [45]. Electro-optical modulators are frequency-stable across a broad range of frequencies, which is a key factor in their widespread use in telecommunications [46]. One limitation of these devices in free-space IR spectroscopy applications is that the required operating voltage increases proportionally to the wavelength of the light to be modulated. Recent advancements in integrated photonics have enabled the use of smaller voltages due to the miniaturization of the underlying structures [47]. The direct modulation of the laser current is a particularly simple method that is frequency-stable and applicable across the entire operating wavelength range of the laser. However, the relation between emitted radiation intensity and wavelength is challenging for spectroscopic measurements [48].

In TDLS, the light modulation of a semiconductor laser is performed by modulating its injection current, which results in a combined IM and WM with a phase relation between the two. The phase shift between IM and WM varies depending on the laser,

but typically decreases from lower to higher modulation frequencies [40]. Therefore, it is quite challenging to compensate the respective undesired effect.

In WMS, researchers are interested in the signals generated solely by the WM of the laser emission. IM distorts the spectrum and is therefore referred to as RAM [40]. Derivative spectroscopy offers the advantage of isolating changes in the sample's transmissivity with wavelength, removing the background signal from transmitted or reflected light. This improves the resolution of weak and overlapping spectral features compared to direct absorption or reflection spectroscopy [49,50].

The main challenge in WMS is eliminating spectral distortion caused by the wavelength dependences of emission intensity I_e , detector responsivity G , and steering optics. In a basic absorption experiment with non-dispersive optics, the detector signal $S = I_eGT$, where T is the sample transmissivity. The normalized derivative signal is

$$\frac{1}{S} \frac{dS}{d\lambda} \Delta\lambda = \left(\frac{1}{I_e} \frac{dI_e}{d\lambda} + \frac{1}{G} \frac{dG}{d\lambda} \right) \Delta\lambda + \frac{1}{T} \frac{dT}{d\lambda} \Delta\lambda. \quad (2-1)$$

where $\Delta\lambda$ is the depth of the wavelength modulation [49].

2.3 Photoacoustic Spectroscopy (PAS)

The beginnings of PAS date back to the 19th century with the discovery of the PA effect by A. G. Bell in 1880, later published in the *Journal of the Franklin Institute* [23]. He demonstrated the emission of sound from a thin pane of glass when exposed to modulated sunlight and was also able to prove a connection between the wavelength of light and the resulting sound pressure (loudness) by using infrared and ultraviolet light in addition to visible light.

It was not until a century later, under the direction of A. Rosencwaig at Bell Labs, that the theoretical basis for the effect (which had been largely forgotten) was formulated [51]. A plot of sound pressure versus the wavelength of the light used is called a PA spectrum [52]. Today, PAS is a well-known technique for the non-destructive detection of IR-active solids, liquids and gases.

In recent years, TDLs such as QCLs and ICLs have been increasingly used as quasi-monochromatic¹, coherent, and spectrally tunable light sources in PAS. This tunability has led to the widespread use of directly pulsed, intensity-modulated or wavelength-modulated radiation without the need for a mechanical chopper².

This direct modulation provides the desired frequency stability but introduces a phenomenon called RAM. This means that the emission wavelength and intensity are coupled: wavelength modulation produces intensity modulation and vice versa.

PAS is one of several techniques in the field of spectroscopy. Spectroscopy can be broadly defined as the study of the interactions between matter and electromagnetic radiation, encompassing absorption, emission, reflection, transmission, scattering, and refraction, as schematically shown in Figure 2-1.

Figure 2-1: Schematic illustration of light-matter interactions.

The behaviour of incident radiation at a material interface is commonly described by three fundamental optical parameters: transmittance τ , absorptance α and reflectance ρ . These parameters describe how the incident light energy is distributed when it interacts with the sample.

Transmittance refers to the fraction of incident light that passes through the material, while reflectance describes the fraction that is reflected at the surface. Absorptance quantifies the fraction of light absorbed by the material, which may subsequently contribute to non-radiative processes such as heat generation.

¹Very narrow emission linewidth.

²The chopper is still the conventional means of modulation.

Under ideal conditions, where scattering and luminescence are negligible, energy conservation dictates that the sum of these three quantities must equal one [53]

$$\tau + \alpha + \rho = 1. \quad (2-2)$$

To determine the values of τ , α and ρ , light of known power is directed at the sample. The optical powers of the reflected and transmitted light are then measured. From the relationship between the incident power P_e , the transmitted power P_{tr} and the reflected power P_{re} , the transmittance is given by [53]

$$\tau = \frac{P_{tr}}{P_e}, \quad (2-3)$$

the reflectance is given by

$$\rho = \frac{P_{re}}{P_e}, \quad (2-4)$$

and the absorption by

$$\alpha = \frac{P_{abs}}{P_e} = \frac{P_e - P_{tr} - P_{re}}{P_e}. \quad (2-5)$$

As seen in Equation (2-5), the absorbed optical power P_{abs} is not measured directly but is calculated from the transmitted power P_{tr} and the reflected power P_{re} . Other approaches to measure the absorbance of a sample are PT or PA measurements¹.

PT refers to the conversion of absorbed light energy into heat within a material, causing a localised temperature rise and associated thermal phenomena. When a material is exposed to non-stationary (modulated or pulsed) light, the PT effect produces sound (the PA effect). PAS uses this effect for spectroscopic analysis. Unlike conventional optical techniques that analyse transmitted, reflected or scattered photons after interaction with the material, PAS measures the absorbed energy directly. Specifically, it detects the transient heating induced by photon absorption, making it both a form of calorimetry and an optical spectroscopy technique [52].

In Figure 2-2, the stages of PA signal generation, from incident radiation to final detection, are illustrated. It should be noted that although PA measurements without

¹Only non-radiative decay contributes to the PT or PA signal.

acoustic amplification are possible, they are less common and are not performed here. Each step is discussed in detail in the following sections, with particular emphasis on the specific experimental set-up used in this study.

Figure 2-2: Stages of photoacoustic signal generation.

2.3.1 Modulated or Pulsed Radiation by Interband Cascade Laser

PAS requires modulated or pulsed radiation to generate an acoustic signal by periodic light absorption by the sample. Depending on the target molecules and their quantities, the radiation source must meet the following criteria.

Optical power The strength of the photoacoustic signal is directly proportional to the optical power over several orders of magnitude. It must be high enough to produce a measurable acoustic signal¹.

Wavelength tuning The ability to tune the wavelength defines the accessible spectral region and ensures precise excitation of specific molecular absorption lines. The source must cover sufficiently strong absorption features of all target components.

Emission linewidth The spectral resolution is determined by the emission linewidth; narrower linewidths allow better discrimination of closely spaced spectral features.

Operating mode The source can operate in either modulation or pulsed mode, each offering distinct advantages depending on the application requirements.

Based on these criteria, DFB-ICLs are suitable for PAS, offering high resolution and sensitivity.

The following is a brief description of the functionality of the DFB-ICL used in this study, together with its main characteristics, advantages and limitations. DFB-ICLs availability in the 3 to 4 μm wavelength range makes them well suited for the detection of short-chain hydrocarbon gases such as methane, which is one of the target molecules of this study. This is illustrated by the methane absorbance spectrum shown in Figure 2-3.

The linewidth of DFB-ICLs is typically much narrower than that of molecular absorption lines, allowing the latter to be fully resolved. The narrow linewidth also yields a higher spectral power density compared with broadband light sources. In addition, the tunability of ICL wavelengths enables scanning across absorption features, thereby differentiating target molecules from interfering compounds and background signals [4,54].

The ICL was introduced in 1996 by J.R. Meyer et al. [55], only two years after the introduction of the QCL [56]. Whereas the QCL uses intersubband transitions², an ICL emits photons via interband transitions between the conduction band and valence band,

¹In addition to the optical power, the strength of the acoustic signal depends on the cell constant, the concentration, and the absorption of the sample.

²Intersubband transitions are discrete excited states of the conduction band.

Figure 2-3: Absorbance spectrum of methane in the IR region. The spectral data was provided by HITRAN [2], reproduced with permission from Springer Nature.

as in a conventional diode laser [57]. ICLs lasing in continuous wave (CW) mode at room temperature were first demonstrated in 2008 [58].

The term cascade refers to a sequence of repeating stages, each consisting of an active quantum well (QW), a hole injector and an electron injector. The QWs consist of very thin layers of semiconductor materials with different band gaps. For the emission wavelength, the thickness of these layers (which determines the energy levels of the QW) is more significant than the band gap of the semiconductor materials. The injector structures are located between these active zones and guide electrons to the next active zone. Due to this design, a single electron travelling and tunnelling through the cascade stages can emit multiple photons, one per stage. This architecture allows output power to be scaled not only by laser current but also by increasing the number of stages [57].

In a DFB laser, the generation and amplification of coherent light by stimulated emission are achieved by optical feedback from a Bragg grating integrated directly into the laser waveguide. Unlike Fabry-Pérot lasers, in which feedback is mainly due to reflection at the end facets, DFB lasers distribute the optical feedback along the entire length of the waveguide. This design enables single-mode operation and results in a very narrow linewidth [57].

Alternative Radiation Sources for Infrared Spectroscopy

ICLs are available in the wavelength range from 2.8 μm to 6 μm ¹. For longer wavelengths (approximately 6 μm to 14 μm ¹) QCLs are more suitable, while for shorter wavelengths (approximately 760 nm to 3 μm ¹) conventional laser diodes are typically used.

An alternative is to use a standard Nd:YAG laser ($\lambda = 1\,064\text{ nm}$) and convert the emission wavelength subsequently using non-linear optics. For example, an optical parametric oscillator (OPO) can generate tunable radiation up to 3.5 μm ². Such systems can provide output powers of up to 2 W. However, this technology is comparatively expensive.

2.3.2 Photoexcitation

Interactions between light and matter result in a temporary or permanent exchange of energy. An atom or molecule is said to be in its ground state when it occupies the lowest energy level. Conversely, it is said to be in an excited state when it occupies a higher energy level. Transitions between energy states occur when a molecule emits or absorbs a photon (electromagnetic radiation) with energy exactly equal to the difference ΔE between the two states

$$\Delta E = E_2 - E_1. \quad (2-6)$$

The absorption of a photon is called photoexcitation. Its energy is proportional to the frequency ν of the absorbed photon

$$E_{\text{photon}} = h\nu, \quad (2-7)$$

where h is the Planck's constant.

The total excitation energy of a molecule is expressed as the sum of its quantized electronic E_{el} , vibrational E_{vib} , and rotational E_{rot} energies [59]

$$E = E_{\text{el}} + E_{\text{vib}} + E_{\text{rot}}. \quad (2-8)$$

¹Nanoplus Nanosystems and Technologies GmbH, Meiningen, Germany

²C-WAVE Series from HÜBNER Photonics GmbH, Kassel, Germany

The electronic energy of a molecule is determined by its electronic energy levels. A transition between these levels occurs when an electron moves between two orbitals, governed by specific quantum-mechanical selection rules. Such transitions can be induced by photon absorption or emission, inelastic collisions, electron emission or thermal excitation [4,60].

Vibrational energy is associated with the various vibrational modes of a molecule, which depend on its structure and the number of atoms. Molecular vibrations occur when the atoms within a molecule move periodically, even while the molecule as a whole may undergo translational or rotational motion [4]. Table 2-1 provides an overview of the origin of absorption spectra in different regions of the electromagnetic spectrum.

Table 2-1: Origin of absorption spectra in different regions of the electromagnetic spectrum [3,4].

Spectral region	Wavelength	Cause of absorption
UV	(200 – 400) nm	Electronic transition
Visible	(400 – 700) nm	Electronic transition
Near IR	(0.7 – 2.5) μm	Molecular vibration and rotation, overtone
Mid IR	(2.5 – 14) μm	Molecular vibration and rotation, fundamental
Far IR	(14 – 1 000) μm	Molecular rotation

Based on the Equations (2-6), (2-7) and (2-8), the energy transition is calculated as follows [59]

$$E_{\text{photon}} = \Delta E = \Delta E_{\text{el}} + \Delta E_{\text{vib}} + \Delta E_{\text{rot}}. \quad (2-9)$$

In general, the energy of electronic transitions is higher than that of vibrational and rotational transitions [59]

$$\Delta E_{\text{el}} \gg \Delta E_{\text{vib}} \gg \Delta E_{\text{rot}}. \quad (2-10)$$

Rotational spectra result from transitions with $\Delta E_{\text{el}} = \Delta E_{\text{vib}} = 0$ and for rovibrational spectra only $\Delta E_{\text{el}} = 0$ apply. Figure 2-4 shows schematically the different energy levels of a molecule.

Methane, one of the molecules to be detected within the scope of this work, serves as an example for a more detailed examination of the vibrational transitions ν_i . Methane has four allowed vibrational transitions in the infrared spectrum

- ν_1 symmetric stretching at 2917 cm^{-1} ,
- ν_2 degenerate deformation at 1534 cm^{-1} ,
- ν_3 degenerate stretching at 3019 cm^{-1} , and
- ν_4 degenerate deformation at 1306 cm^{-1} .

The transitions at ν_1 and ν_2 are mainly IR inactive¹, but can be detected by Raman spectroscopy. In contrast, the two transitions at ν_3 and ν_4 are IR active, with ν_3 being observable by both Raman and IR spectroscopy [61].

Figure 2-4: Schematic of a molecule's energy structure illustrating electronic, vibrational and rotational levels and the typical transitions between them. Diagram is illustrative and not to scale.

2.3.3 Spectral Line Broadening

Spectral lines associated with molecular energy transitions in absorption (or emission) spectra are never perfectly monochromatic. Even in high resolution spectra, a spectral distribution or broadening of the absorbed intensity around the central line frequency ν_0 is observed. This broadening results from various physical processes in the medium that alter the energy levels of the transitions or the interactions between molecules and light [62]. A brief overview of the principal broadening mechanisms is given, including natural broadening, collisional (pressure) broadening, and Doppler broadening.

¹ ν_2 becomes IR active through Coriolis interaction with ν_4 .

Natural linewidth

The natural linewidth can be derived from the uncertainty principle [63]. For an excited state with a mean lifetime τ_i , the energy E_i of that level can only be determined with an uncertainty of

$$\Delta E_i = \frac{h}{2\pi\tau_i}. \quad (2-11)$$

Consequently, the frequency ν_i of a transition to the stable ground state E_k will also have an associated uncertainty of

$$\Delta\nu_i = \frac{1}{2\pi\tau_i}. \quad (2-12)$$

If the lower level E_k is not the ground state but another excited state with a lifetime τ_k , the uncertainties ΔE_i and ΔE_k of both levels contribute to the overall linewidth. As a result, the total uncertainty is given by

$$\Delta E_{\text{natural}} = \sqrt{\Delta E_i^2 + \Delta E_k^2}, \quad (2-13)$$

and

$$\Delta\nu_{\text{natural}} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\tau_i^2} + \frac{1}{\tau_k^2}}. \quad (2-14)$$

The natural line has a Lorentzian shape, with full width at half maximum (FWHM) equal to the described uncertainty $\Delta\nu_{\text{natural}}$ [64].

Doppler Broadening

In general, the natural line profile cannot be observed without special techniques, because its narrow linewidth is completely obscured by other broadening effects, such as Doppler broadening in gases. Here, the thermal motion of the absorbing (or emitting) molecules introduces additional broadening due to the Doppler shift [65].

Due to the Doppler effect, the absorption frequency ν_{abs} of a molecule moving with velocity v_{\parallel} parallel to the incident radiation is shifted by [65]

$$\nu_{\text{abs}} = \nu_0 \left(1 + \frac{v_{\parallel}}{c} \right). \quad (2-15)$$

Specifically, the frequency decreases when $v_{\parallel} < 0$ (motion towards the radiation source) and increases when $v_{\parallel} > 0$ (motion away from the source).

The Doppler-broadened absorption line has a Gaussian shape with a FWHM of [64]

$$\Delta\nu_{\text{doppler}} = 2\frac{\nu_0}{c} \sqrt{\frac{2RT \ln(2)}{m}}, \quad (2-16)$$

which, using the universal gas constant $R = 8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and the speed of light $c = 3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, simplifies to

$$\Delta\nu_{\text{doppler}} = 7.16 \cdot 10^{-7} \nu_0 \sqrt{\frac{T}{M}}, \quad (2-17)$$

where ν_0 is the central line frequency and M is the molar mass.

Collisional Broadening of Spectral Lines

The collisional broadening of a spectral line¹ $\Delta\nu_{\text{collision}}$ can be modelled as the product of the system pressure and the sum of the mole fractions X_i of all species involved in collisions with the target molecule. Each species contributes according to its specific collisional broadening coefficient $2\gamma_{\text{target}-i}$, which depends on the interaction between the perturbing species and the target molecule [64]

$$\Delta\nu_{\text{collision}} = P \sum_i X_i 2\gamma_{\text{target}-i}. \quad (2-18)$$

The temperature dependence of the broadening coefficient $2\gamma(T)$ can be approximated by² [64]

$$2\gamma(T) \approx 2\gamma(T_0) \sqrt{\frac{T_0}{T}}. \quad (2-19)$$

where T_0 is the reference temperature (typically 296 K or 300 K) and $2\gamma(T_0)$ is the broadening coefficient at that reference temperature.

¹The FWHM of a Lorentzian profile.

²This equation is valid under the assumption that the collision cross-section is temperature-independent. For further details, see [64].

Line Broadening in Methane

The effects of line broadening are illustrated using methane as an example. Figure 2-5 shows the pure line spectrum of methane.

Figure 2-5: Simulated line strength S_{l_s} spectrum of methane in the emission tuning range of the ICL.

The spectral data was provided by HITRAN [2], reproduced with permission from Springer Nature.

The line strength is a measure of the probability that radiation at a given frequency will lead to excitation of the molecule, i.e. how strong the absorption is. The frequency range is chosen to approximate the tuning range of the ICL. It can be seen that three lines around 3345.7 nm are significantly more pronounced. Note that the line strength is shown on a logarithmic scale.

In Figure 2-6, the effect of line broadening as a function of pressure is illustrated in a narrow spectral region containing vibro-rotational absorption lines of methane simulated using the HITRAN database. Here, the collisional effect is dominant. The simulation parameters are set to a temperature of 20 °C, an absorption path length of 1 cm, and a methane concentration of 1 %. The pressure is varied to 0.1 atm, 1 atm, and 10 atm to demonstrate the broadening effect. At 0.1 atm, the individual absorption lines are well resolved and clearly distinct. At 1 atm, the lines begin to overlap significantly, and at 10 atm, the three lines merge into a single, broad absorption feature.

Figure 2-6: Simulated absorbance A spectrum of broadened methane absorption lines in relation to pressure. The spectral data was provided by HITRAN [2], reproduced with permission from Springer Nature.

Figure 2-7: Simulated absorbance A spectrum of broadened methane absorption lines in relation to temperature. The spectral data was provided by HITRAN [2], reproduced with permission from Springer Nature.

Analogous to the pressure dependence shown in Figure 2-6, Figure 2-7 illustrates the effect of line broadening as a function of temperature. Both Doppler broadening and collisional broadening affect the linewidth, as shown in Equation (2-16) and Equation (2-19). The simulation parameters are set to a pressure of 1 atm, an absorption

path length of 1 cm, and a methane concentration of 1 %. The temperature is varied to $-100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to demonstrate the broadening effect.

Unlike Doppler broadening, collisional broadening decreases with increasing temperature. Overall, this results in a slightly wider linewidth at higher temperatures.

Spectral Line Shifting

In addition to the physical mechanisms that broaden absorption lines, there are processes that shift the frequency of the absorption line. Two of these shift mechanisms are similar to the broadening effects introduced earlier, namely the Doppler shift and the shift due to interactions between two collision partners¹.

The Doppler shift occurs in measurements where gases have a bulk velocity relative to an incident laser beam. As there is no significant bulk flow of the sample gas in this study, no effect on the line-centre frequency due to the Doppler shift is expected.

The collisional shift is analogous to the collisional broadening discussed above. Interactions between collision partners can change the intermolecular potential and hence the line-centre frequencies of the various transitions. Just as in Equation (2-18), where the collisional half-width $\Delta\nu_{\text{collision}}$ is proportional to the pressure and a broadening coefficient, 2γ , the expression for pressure shift depends directly on pressure but contains the shift coefficient δ instead [64]

$$\Delta\nu_{\text{shift}} = P \sum_i X_i \delta_{\text{target}-i}. \quad (2-20)$$

Both 2γ and δ have units of $\text{cm}^{-1} \text{atm}^{-1}$.

The shift coefficient also scales from a reference temperature similarly to the broadening coefficient [64]

$$2\delta(T) \approx \delta(T_0) \frac{T_0}{T}. \quad (2-21)$$

Note that while $2\gamma > 0$, the pressure shift can be either negative or positive. Average values for near-infrared H_2O spectra are $\delta \approx -0.017 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{atm}^{-1}$ [64].

¹The frequency shift of the absorption line centre due to collisions is commonly referred to as the pressure shift.

For measurements of trace gases, where the carrier medium (nitrogen) remains unchanged, the shift due to concentration differences in the target is generally small. Changes in pressure and temperature may have a greater effect. As all measurements in this work are performed at ambient temperature and pressure, this effect can be considered negligible.

2.3.4 Acoustic Wave Generation

When periodically excited molecules dissipate their excitation energy as heat into the sample, an acoustic signal is produced. Since the modulation frequency is usually in the audio range^{1,2}, and in the setup used in this study ($f \approx 2\,700\text{ Hz}$), the time delay between excitation and heat release may be negligible³ [52].

A molecule in an excited state can lose energy either by radiative processes, such as spontaneous or stimulated emission, or by non-radiative deactivation. In the latter case, at least some of the absorbed energy is converted to heat [52]. In a solid, this energy appears as ionic or atomic vibrational energy (phonons), whereas in a gas it appears as kinetic energy of the gas molecules. For vibrational excitation of gas molecules, radiative emission and chemical reactions are negligible⁴. The radiative lifetime of vibrational levels is long compared with the mean free time⁵ at atmospheric pressure, so collisional deactivation dominates. Moreover, the photon energy is too low to induce reactions. Therefore, essentially all absorbed energy is dissipated as heat [5,52].

For moderate excitation rates⁶, the heat release is proportional to the absorption coefficient and the incident light intensity. At high excitation rates, caused by high light intensity or very short laser pulses, optical saturation can occur and the heat release becomes non-linear due to stimulated emission [5,52]. The DFB-ICL used here is not

¹The audible range is generally specified as 20 to 20 000 Hz.

²This range is advantageous due to the availability of high-quality microphones and resonators of an appropriate size.

³In this case the source term has the same time dependence as the light intensity.

⁴In the case of electronic excitation, radiative processes and chemical reactions may interfere with collisional deactivation [52].

⁵The mean time between two consecutive collisions of a particle.

⁶Moderate light intensity and absorption.

pulsed but sinusoidally modulated with an optical power below 10 mW. Therefore, non-linearity due to stimulated emission is not expected.

Thermal and Acoustic Waves

The PA effect is intrinsically coupled to the PT effect. When radiation interacts with a material, the absorbed energy causes a local increase in temperature, resulting in the generation of a (strongly damped) thermal wave and a subsequent (slightly damped) propagating sound wave. The thermal wave behaves like an isobaric¹ thermal expansion, where the changes in temperature and density are much greater than the changes in pressure. This wave does not propagate far from the heated region [52].

Even if the thermal wave does not travel far, the overall temperature in the PA cell will slowly increase until a thermal equilibrium is reached between the rate of heat loss by conduction and the heat energy introduced by radiation. For a closed cell of constant volume, a pressure increase will occur in response to the temperature increase. The thermodynamic state of the sample changes as the temperature and pressure increase. This effect is particularly strong for very small PA detectors, $V \leq 1 \text{ cm}^3$ [52]. The PA cell used in this work has a volume of $V \approx 26 \text{ cm}^3$, so the effect is expected to be small.

In contrast to the thermal wave, the sound wave behaves as a quasi-adiabatic² change of state, propagating at the speed of sound. The amplitude of the sound wave is proportional to the fluctuating heat power density of the thermal wave and inversely proportional to the modulation frequency [52].

Modulated PAS

For a sample with unsaturated absorption ($a \ll 1$), the wavelength dependent PA signal $S(\lambda)$ (in V) is given by [22]

$$S(\lambda) = CP(\lambda)\alpha(\lambda). \quad (2-22)$$

¹A thermodynamic process in which the pressure remains constant throughout the process.

²A thermodynamic process in which heat neither enters nor leaves the system in question. Here the orders of magnitude of the relative changes in pressure, temperature and density are the same.

with the cell constant C , the laser power $P(\lambda)$ and the absorption coefficient $\alpha(\lambda)$. The cell constant depends not only on the PAC properties such as geometry and cell wall area, but also on the beam profile, modulation frequency, and microphone sensitivity. It is typically determined experimentally from measurements with known optical power, substance absorption characteristics, and concentration [66].

The exact determination of the non-resonant cell constants is not described here, but the relationship between cell length l , volume V , and frequency f is given by [22]

$$C_{\text{non-res}} \propto \frac{l}{fV}. \quad (2-23)$$

2.3.5 Acoustic Amplification

An important concept in photoacoustic spectroscopy is acoustic amplification by excitation of resonances in the sample cell. The amplification is usually expressed as the quality factor Q of the resonator. The cell constant of a resonant PAC C_{res} is given by [22]

$$C_{\text{res}} = C_{\text{non-res}} Q, \quad (2-24)$$

where $C_{\text{non-res}}$ is the cell constant of a non-resonant cylindrical PAC.

Typically, PAC designs for frequencies between 500 Hz and 4 000 Hz have Q factors of 20 to 200 [67]. For Q values greater than 10, the quality factor is given by [66]

$$Q = \frac{f_{\text{res}}}{\Delta f}, \quad (2-25)$$

with the centre frequency of the resonance peak f_{res} and the FWHM of the resonance profile Δf .

A high Q factor is not always desirable, especially in quantitative measurements. It corresponds to a narrow resonance peak in the frequency spectrum, making it very sensitive to variations in the modulation frequency of the laser and the resonance frequency of the PAC.

The geometry of the PAC not only amplifies the PA signal but also imposes boundary conditions on the evolution of the generated acoustic waves. Theoretical analysis seems to be feasible only for highly symmetric, resonant setups with high Q

factors¹. For PA setups without these characteristics, quantitative signal analysis is not practical [52].

Most PACs are cylindrical with open or closed ends. In these cylindrical cells, three different types of resonances (known as modes) can occur: longitudinal, azimuthal and radial modes.

The cell consists of the actual resonator, a cylindrical cavity defined by its radius r_c and length l_c , open on both sides, and two adjacent buffer volumes V_1 and V_2 .

Figure 2-8: Schematic of the cross-section of a H-type photoacoustic cell with relevant dimensions to calculate the acoustic resonant frequencies of the system.

To calculate the resonant frequency f_j of the system, and hence the desired excitation frequency, the following equation is used [5],

$$f_j = \frac{\omega_0}{2\pi} = \frac{c_s}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\left(\frac{k}{l_{\text{eff}}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{a_{mn}}{r_c}\right)^2}. \quad (2-26)$$

It applies to both open and closed cylindrical resonators. The index j corresponds to the respective mode $j = [k, m, n]$. A distinction is made between longitudinal k , azimuthal m and radial n modes. The first two modes of each type for an open cylinder are shown in Figure 2-9 [66,68]. Zones of high sound pressure are indicated by dashed lines. For example, the highest sound pressure of the first longitudinal mode occurs in the cross-section at the centre of the resonator.

¹The quality factor or Q factor is proportional to the gain of the PA signal and describes the damping behaviour of the resonator.

Figure 2-9: Acoustic resonances in an open cylindrical chamber. Schematic pressure node/antinode patterns for longitudinal (k), azimuthal (m) and radial (n) modes are shown; high-pressure regions are marked by dotted lines.

For open cylinders, the longitudinal modes extend slightly outside the resonator; therefore the effective length l_{eff} must first be determined by [5]

$$l_{\text{eff}} = l_c + \frac{16}{3\pi} r_c. \quad (2-27)$$

This is commonly referred to as the open end correction. Equation (2-27) does not include the effect of buffer volumes but is a close approximation.

Table 2-2: Values for a_{nm} used to calculate the resonant frequencies of in cylindrical resonators [5,6].

$m \setminus n$	0	1	2	3
0	0	1.2198	2.2333	3.2382
1	0.5860	1.6969	2.7139	3.7261
2	0.9721	2.1346	3.1732	4.1921
3	1.3372	2.5513	3.6115	4.6429

To calculate azimuthal and radial modes, the corresponding factor a_{mn} can be taken from Table 2-2 [5]. For the normal modes of a cavity, a distinction is made between pure longitudinal modes ($m = n = 0, k \neq 0$), azimuthal modes ($k = n = 0, m \neq 0$), and radial modes ($k = m = 0, n \neq 0$). All other eigenvalues represent mixed modes. The resonant frequencies of the longitudinal modes are multiples of the fundamental mode ($f_{k00} = k f_{100}$). The radial and azimuthal modes, on the other hand, are described

by the Bessel functions; their resonant frequencies are not multiples of the fundamental frequency [5].

2.3.6 Acoustic Detection

The most common type of acoustic detector used in PAS is a capacitive microphone. In such a microphone, a diaphragm moves in response to incident sound waves, changing the capacitance between the diaphragm and a fixed electrode. This change in capacitance is converted into an electrical signal. Due to their widespread use in consumer electronics such as telephones, most capacitive microphones are optimised for the audible frequency range between 20 Hz and 20 kHz, a range that fits well with common PA resonator geometries. Their main advantages are low cost, compact size, and high sensitivity to small acoustic signals.

Alternative Acoustic Sensors

Alternative methods such as quartz tuning forks (QTFs) and cantilever sensors have gained wider acceptance in the scientific community in recent years. The characteristic properties of these two sensor types are described briefly below.

QTFs are sharply resonant acoustic transducers for the detection of weak PA excitation and allow the use of extremely small volumes. Quartz crystals are low-loss, low-cost piezoelectric materials and are commonly used as clocks in electronic devices, typically with a resonant frequency of 32 768 or 2^{15} Hz. In a vacuum, they can have Q values of over 100 000, dropping to around 10 000 at normal atmospheric pressure [31].

A cantilever-based sensor consists of a laser and photodetector system that tracks the deflection of the cantilever and converts its motion into an optical signal. Similar to a QTF, its large displacement response at resonance makes it particularly suitable for single-frequency acoustic wave measurements in PAS. The resonant frequency of the cantilever can be easily tuned by adjusting its length, width or height¹. Cantilevers can

¹For example, the resonant frequency of the cantilever shown in [69] is ~ 45 kHz and has a Q factor of ~ 200 in air.

operate in non-resonant or resonant mode, with the latter generally having a higher Q value [69,70].

2.3.7 Lock-In Amplification / Bandpass Filtering

PAS signals are often very small and can be buried in background noise. However, they have a fixed frequency and phase relationship with the radiation source. Lock-in amplification and bandpass filtering use this relationship to separate the PAS signal from the noise.

Lock-In Amplification

Lock-in amplification refers to a homodyne¹ detection method combined with low-pass filtering to determine the magnitude and phase of a signal relative to a periodic reference. This technique isolates signals within a specific frequency band centred on the reference frequency, effectively suppressing components at other frequencies. With a dynamic range of up to 120 dB, modern instruments are capable of extracting signal amplitudes and phases in extremely noisy environments [71].

Figure 2-10: Schematic of a dual-phase demodulation circuit of a lock-in amplifier.

Figure 2-10 illustrates a schematic of a lock-in amplifier. Lock-in amplification begins by multiplying the input signal V_s by a reference signal V_r (homodyne detection), followed by the application of an adjustable low-pass filter, producing the output X . Since X is phase-sensitive, the input is also multiplied in parallel by the reference signal shifted by $\frac{\pi}{2}$, yielding a second output Y . From X and Y , the magnitude R and the phase φ of the input signal relative to the reference can be calculated. The reference signal is

¹The term homodyne refers to a single frequency, whereas heterodyne detection uses two frequencies.

either generated internally by the lock-in amplifier or supplied externally to both the amplifier and the experiment [71]. The input signal is an AC voltage of the form

$$V_s(t) = \sqrt{2}R \cos(\omega_s t + \varphi) + \varepsilon_{\text{noise}}, \quad (2-28)$$

with amplitude $\sqrt{2}R$, frequency ω_s , initial phase φ and a certain amount of noise $\varepsilon_{\text{noise}}$. The reference signal is a AC voltage in the form

$$V_r(t) = \sqrt{2} \cos(\omega_r t) \quad (2-29)$$

with amplitude $\sqrt{2}$, frequency ω_r . The amplitude of the reference determines the gain of the signal, by choosing $\sqrt{2}$ no gain is applied [71].

The calculation of the first phase-sensitive output is given by

$$X = \langle V_s V_r \rangle, \quad (2-30a)$$

$$= \langle 2R \cos(\omega_s t + \varphi) \cos(\omega_r t) + \varepsilon_{\text{noise}} \sqrt{2} \cos(\omega_r t) \rangle, \quad (2-30b)$$

$$= \frac{1}{T} \int_{-\frac{T}{2}}^{\frac{T}{2}} 2R \cos(\omega_s t + \varphi) \cos(\omega_r t) + \varepsilon_{\text{noise}} \sqrt{2} \cos(\omega_r t) dt. \quad (2-30c)$$

For a time interval $T \gg \frac{1}{\omega_r}$, a DC offset is generated in the resulting signal only when $\omega_r \approx \omega_s$. This offset corresponds to the mean value of the multiplied signals $\langle V_s V_r \rangle$, given by

$$X(\omega_r = \omega_s) = R \cos(\varphi). \quad (2-31)$$

X is only the in-phase component of the signal. To determine the magnitude of the signal at the reference frequency, the process must be repeated using a second reference signal that is phase-shifted by $\frac{\pi}{2}$

$$\sqrt{2} \cos\left(\omega_r t + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) = -\sqrt{2} \sin(\omega_r t) \quad (2-32)$$

to obtain the second phase-sensitive output, commonly referred to as the quadrature¹ component

$$Y = \langle -V_s(t) \sqrt{2} \sin(\omega_r t) \rangle, \quad (2-33)$$

which, analogue to Equation (2-30), results in

¹A signal is considered to be in quadrature if its phase lags or leads a reference signal by $\frac{\pi}{2}$ radians.

$$Y(\omega_r = \omega_s) = R \sin(\varphi). \quad (2-34)$$

The results X and Y can be interpreted as the real and imaginary parts of the complex number [71]

$$Z = X + iY. \quad (2-35)$$

with the absolute value $|Z| = R$ given as the root mean square (RMS) amplitude of the signal [71]

$$R = \sqrt{X^2 + Y^2}, \quad (2-36)$$

and its argument $\arg(Z) = \varphi$ given by the phase of the input signal V_s relative to the reference signal V_r

$$\varphi(X, Y) = \begin{cases} \arctan\left(\frac{Y}{X}\right) & \text{if } X > 0, \\ \arctan\left(\frac{Y}{X}\right) + \pi & \text{if } X < 0 \text{ and } Y \geq 0, \\ \arctan\left(\frac{Y}{X}\right) - \pi & \text{if } X < 0 \text{ and } Y < 0, \\ \frac{\pi}{2} & \text{if } X = 0 \text{ and } Y > 0, \\ -\frac{\pi}{2} & \text{if } X = 0 \text{ and } Y < 0, \\ \text{undefined} & \text{if } X = 0 \text{ and } Y = 0. \end{cases} \quad (2-37)$$

Digital Bandpass Filter: Goertzel Algorithm

The Goertzel algorithm is an optimised variant of the discrete fourier transform (DFT), designed for the efficient computation of a small set of specific frequency components. Developed by Gerald Goertzel in 1958, it gained wider recognition through its application in dual-tone multi-frequency signalling systems [72–74]. The core of the algorithm operates as a digital filter, commonly known as the Goertzel filter. The infinite impulse response (IIR) filter representation of the Goertzel algorithm is shown in Figure 2-11.

Figure 2-11: Structure of an IIR filter representing the implemented Goertzel algorithm.

Its input $x(n)$ is a discrete, time-domain signal of length N samples. The filter coefficients a_1 and b_1 vary depending on the frequency bin k being analysed. They are given by [73]

$$a_1 = 2 \cos\left(2\pi \frac{k}{N}\right), \quad (2-38a)$$

$$a_2 = -1, \quad (2-38b)$$

$$b_1 = -e^{-2\pi i \frac{k}{N}}. \quad (2-38c)$$

The z^{-1} operator represents a delay of one sample in the time domain. After processing N samples, the filter output is the complex value $y(N)$ that would be obtained from a DFT on the same frequency bin [73]

$$y(n) = q(n) - q(n-1)e^{-2\pi i \frac{k}{N}}, \quad (2-39)$$

with

$$q(n) = 2 \cos\left(2\pi \frac{k}{N}\right)q(n-1) - q(n-2) + x(n), \quad (2-40)$$

with the initial conditions $q(-1) = q(-2) = 0$.

The exponential factor on the right-hand side of the filter, $e^{2\pi i \frac{k}{N}}$, can be deferred until the final calculation step, thereby reducing the computational load [73].

As with the RMS amplitude of the lock-in amplifier introduced in Equation (2-36), this value can be obtained from the Goertzel filter by [73]

$$R = \sqrt{y(N)y^*(N)}, \quad (2-41a)$$

$$= \sqrt{\left(q(N) - q(N-1)e^{-2\pi i \frac{k}{N}}\right)\left(q(N) - q(N-1)e^{2\pi i \frac{k}{N}}\right)}, \quad (2-41b)$$

$$= \sqrt{q^2(N)q^2(N-1) - 2 \cos\left(2\pi \frac{k}{N}\right)q(N)q(N-1)}. \quad (2-41c)$$

With the signals' complex conjugate y^* .

2.3.8 Phase Relation Between Radiation and Acoustic Wave

The phase relationship between the laser modulation and the microphone signal can be determined using the lock-in amplification described in Section 2.3.7. The phase is of interest for a variety of reasons, for example to determine or track the resonant frequency of the acoustic resonator.

The acoustic response, i.e. the sound pressure p at the microphone position in the H-cell, can be approximated using a model of a damped harmonic oscillator. The damped harmonic oscillator model presented below is based on the textbook *Mechanics and Thermodynamics* by Wolfgang Demtröder [75].

As with any harmonic oscillator, the sound pressure in the acoustic resonator follows the equation of motion

$$\ddot{p} + \gamma\dot{p} + \omega_0^2 p = \xi \cos(\omega t) \quad (2-42)$$

with the natural frequency of the oscillator $\omega_0 = 2\pi f_0$, the damping factor¹ γ , the amplitude of the driving force ξ , and its frequency ω .

Equation (2-42) can be solved using the ansatz $p = \tilde{A}e^{i\omega t}$, where \tilde{A} is a complex amplitude, and the physical solution is given by the real part of this expression. Similarly,

¹The damping factor describes the acoustic resistance, such as energy dissipation due to friction or thermal effects.

the driving term $\xi \cos(\omega t)$ may be rewritten as $\xi e^{i\omega t}$, transforming the original equation into its complex form

$$(-\omega^2 + i\gamma\omega + \omega_0^2)\tilde{A}e^{i\omega t} = \xi e^{i\omega t} \quad (2-43)$$

Solving \tilde{A} for gives

$$\tilde{A} = \frac{\xi}{\omega_0^2 - \omega^2 + i\gamma\omega}. \quad (2-44)$$

The amplitude of the driven motion is of interest as this is the amplitude of the acoustic response. This can be seen by writing \tilde{A} in its polar form $\tilde{A} = Ae^{i\theta_0}$, then

$$p = Ae^{i(\omega t + \theta_0)}, \quad (2-45)$$

which is exactly the form of a harmonic oscillation with an amplitude of

$$A = |\tilde{A}| = \sqrt{\frac{\xi^2}{(\omega_0^2 - \omega^2)^2 + \gamma^2\omega^2}} \quad (2-46)$$

and a phase shift of

$$\varphi = \arg(\tilde{A}) = -\arctan\left(\frac{\gamma\omega}{\omega_0^2 - \omega^2}\right). \quad (2-47)$$

Even if the natural and the driving frequencies are very different, the system is still forced to oscillate at the driving frequency rather than at its natural frequency.

2.4 The Mach–Zehnder Interferometer

Today, the concept of the wave-particle duality of light is widely accepted. In the 17th century, however, the nature of light was the subject of much debate, with scientists divided between particle and wave theories. While Isaac Newton strongly advocated the particle hypothesis, Christiaan Huygens significantly advanced the wave theory. Huygens correctly deduced that light slows down when it travels through denser media, and used his wave model to derive the laws of reflection and refraction. His theory even provided an explanation for the birefringence observed in calcite crystals [76].

In the early 19th century, Dr Thomas Young revived the wave theory of light by introducing a fundamental concept, the interference principle [76,77]:

“When two or more optical waves are simultaneously present in the same region of space and time, the total wavefunction is the sum of the individual wavefunctions.”

The fundamental superposition principle does not apply to optical intensity. The intensity of two or more superimposed waves is not necessarily equal to the sum of their individual intensities. Coherent interference (which requires light beams of the same frequency, a fixed phase relationship, spatial overlap with parallel polarisation states, and path differences within the coherence length of the source) causes the electric field amplitudes to add rather than the intensities. This behaviour cannot be explained by ray optics, as it depends on the phase relationship between the superimposed waves [77].

Interference can be produced artificially in a device called an interferometer. This optical instrument uses a beam splitter to divide a light beam into two, introduces unequal delays, redirects the beams using mirrors, and recombines them using the same (or a different) beam splitter. Because of interference, the intensity of the recombined beam varies with the relative delay between the beams. Common interferometers include the Michelson, Sagnac and MZIs [77].

The MZI was invented by Ludwig Mach and Ludwig Zehnder in the 1890s. Zehnder first described the interferometer in 1891 [78] and Mach independently developed a similar design in 1892 [79]. The device is now widely known as the MZI, in recognition of both scientists. A basic MZI with balanced path lengths is shown in Figure 2-12. It consists of a pair of beam splitters (BS_1 and BS_2) and a pair of mirrors (M_a and M_b), one in each optical path. At the first beam splitter BS_1 , the incoming laser light I_e is split and propagates along two distinct paths, labelled as l_a and l_b . The light is then recombined at the second beam splitter BS_2 , resulting in two outputs (I_{MZI} and I'_{MZI}). The interference pattern observed at the output is highly sensitive to phase differences that result from path-length differences.

Adding a tunable phase shifter (PS) to one of the interferometer paths enables the MZI to be used for intensity modulation. This is achieved by alternating between constructive and destructive interference. This special use case is referred to as an Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM). A common application of the MZM is the modulation of the intensity of optical signals in fibre-optic communications [77]. It has also

Figure 2-12: Schematic of a balanced Mach-Zehnder interferometer.

gained significant importance as an electro-optic modulator (EOM) for spectroscopic applications (e.g. PAS).

In particular, PAS requires modulated radiation to excite the sample in a way that an acoustic signal is generated [45]. Frequency stability is very important in this application because the PAC usually acts as a band-pass filter and hence attenuates signals outside the band-pass. Compared to the mechanical chopper, a MZM can provide a pure sinusoidal signal, free of mechanical influences, which leads to an improvement in precision and stability. Another key advantage of MZMs is their ability to provide high modulation frequencies.

In MZMs, modulation arises from the interference between two partial beams with different phases. The phase difference depends on several factors but can be adjusted using a voltage applied to the MZM's PS. The modulation is affected by temperature, displacement and wavelength variations, which appear in the interference and thus in the optical signal. Systematic control of the MZM can compensate for these effects. State of the art bias voltage control is implemented by monitoring the output power and adjusting the bias to maintain the MZM operating point [80]. An alternative approach is to monitor the harmonics of the output signal rather than its power [81]. The bias voltage is the DC component of the PS control voltage. There are also initial approaches to model-based controls [82].

The advantage of using an MZI over other interferometers is that back reflections can be avoided entirely, protecting the semiconductor laser. Alternatives to the MZI include the Michelson or Fabry–Pérot interferometers.

Transmission and Phase of the Mach–Zehnder Interferometer

The MZI input beam has the intensity I_e , and the output beams have the intensities I_{MZI} and I'_{MZI} , respectively. The relationship between output and input intensity I_{MZI}/I_e can be described as transmission τ , which is a function of the phase difference ϕ between the two counter-rotating partial beams [77]

$$\tau = \cos^2\left(\frac{\phi}{2}\right), \quad (2-48a)$$

$$\tau = \frac{1 + \cos(\phi)}{2}. \quad (2-48b)$$

Equation (2-48b) is an alternative variant of the commonly used Equation (2-48a), which allows an easier conversion of the output signal into the frequency domain. The corresponding transmission τ' can be calculated analogously by replacing ϕ with $\phi + \pi$.

By changing the voltage $V(t)$ applied to the PS, ϕ and the corresponding transmission τ and τ' can be adjusted due to the Pockels effect [77]

$$\phi = \pi \frac{V(t)}{V_{\lambda/2}} + C. \quad (2-49)$$

The half-wave voltage $V_{\lambda/2}$ is the voltage required to shift the phase ϕ by π . It is material and wavelength dependent. For the transverse Pockels effect, the voltage is applied perpendicular to the optical axis. The half-wave voltage is a function of the electrode distance d_{PS} and the crystal length l_{PS}

$$V_{\lambda/2} = \frac{\lambda}{n_e^3 r_{33}} \frac{d_{\text{PS}}}{l_{\text{PS}}}. \quad (2-50)$$

Besides the intentional modulation by $V(t)$, the phase depends on semi-constant factors like the difference in optical path length and the PS's temperature, summarized as C . One of these factors is the voltage free phase shift $\phi_{\text{PS}} \in C$ of the PS, calculated using

Equation (2-51a) [83]. Another factor is the inequality of the optical length l_{imb} of the MZM in combination with temperature and wavelength fluctuations. For imbalanced MZMs, the phase $\phi_{\text{imb}} \in C$ of the MZI is calculated using Equation (2-51b) [84,85]

$$\phi_{\text{PS}} = \frac{2\pi n_e l_{\text{PS}}}{\lambda}, \quad (2-51a)$$

$$\phi_{\text{imb}} = \frac{2\pi n_{\text{air}} l_{\text{imb}}}{\lambda}, \quad (2-51b)$$

with the refractive index of air n_{air} , the optical length inequality l_{imb} between the two arms of the MZM, and the wavelength λ of the input beam.

2.5 Multivariate Data Analysis

Univariate refers to the dependence of the target¹ variable y on a single independent² variable x ,

$$y = f(x). \quad (2-52)$$

The term multivariate refers to the dependence on several influence variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n

$$y = f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n). \quad (2-53)$$

In the context of PAS, each value in the PA spectrum is an independent variable x , while the concentration of each component of a sample is a target variable y .

For data analysis, m spectra, each consisting of n measured values x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , are combined into a single matrix of predictor variables. This matrix, of size (m, n) , is hereafter referred to as the data matrix \mathbf{X} .

The wavelength ranges in which the spectra of the individual components differ are of interest for the regression. Indicators of the importance of the different variables in \mathbf{X} are the variance, covariance and the correlation coefficients.

The variance of a column of the data matrix $\text{var}(x_i)$ shows the dispersion of the individual measurements at that point in the spectrum. The covariance is a measure

¹The target variable is often referred to as the dependent or response variable.

²The independent variable is also known as the explanatory variable.

of the linear relationship between two variables. In this case, the linear relationship between the measurements at two different points of the spectrum (\mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j). The covariances of the data matrix are summarised in the variance-covariance matrix \mathbf{V} [86]

$$\mathbf{V} = \text{cov}(\mathbf{X}). \quad (2-54)$$

\mathbf{V} is a square, symmetric matrix of type (n, n) , where n is the number of potential explanatory variables. Each element v_{ij} of the matrix is the covariance of columns i and j . The main diagonal of \mathbf{V} contains the variances of the columns

$$v_{ij} = \text{cov}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j), \quad (2-55a)$$

$$v_{ii} = \text{var}(\mathbf{x}_i). \quad (2-55b)$$

Like covariance, correlation is a measure of the degree of linear relationship between variables. Unlike v , the correlation coefficient r is normalised to values between -1 and 1 . The numerical value indicates the strength, and the sign indicates the direction of the correlation¹. In the correlation matrix \mathbf{R} , the individual correlation coefficients for the columns of the data matrix are given [86]

$$\mathbf{R} = \text{corr}(\mathbf{X}), \quad (2-56a)$$

$$r_{ij} = \text{corr}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j). \quad (2-56b)$$

Correlation analysis is usually an intermediate step towards other methods such as factor analysis or regression. It can be used to determine the strength of the linear dependence between columns of the data matrix. For regression, it is advantageous if the columns of the data matrix are linearly independent. Linear independence means that, in a set of vectors, none of the vectors can be expressed as a linear combination of the others. From a mathematical point of view

$$\sum \alpha_i \mathbf{x}_i = 0 \rightarrow \alpha_i = 0 \quad (2-57)$$

must be satisfied. A set of vectors that are not linearly independent is said to be linearly dependent.

¹Negative correlation means inverse dependence.

A linear combination of a set of vectors $\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n$ corresponds to an expression of the type $\sum \alpha_i \mathbf{x}_i$ with $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, where α_i is a scalar. A linear combination is considered normalised or standardised if the sum of the absolute values is 1

$$\sum |\alpha_i| = 1. \quad (2-58)$$

2.5.1 Regression

For relatively low absorption in the PA sample, the PA signal is linearly related to the concentration of the absorbing substance. Consequently, linear regression methods are well-suited to the analysis of such data. Other regression methods are also available. For example, when the target variable is binary (as in classification), logistic regression is typically used.

Linear Regression

Simple linear regression is not used for multivariate analysis of the spectra, but is presented here as an introductory example of regression analysis. It is also used to introduce variables for the evaluation of the regression, such as the root mean square error (RMSE).

Given a dataset of pairs of values, each consisting of the target variable y and an explanatory variable x . The goal of simple linear regression is to find the parameters a and b of the linear regression equation

$$f(x) = a + xb. \quad (2-59)$$

with the minimum deviation between the predicted value $\hat{y} = f(x)$ and the target variable y . The following applies

$$b = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x}) \cdot (y_i - \bar{y})}{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (2-60a)$$

$$a = \bar{y} - b\bar{x} \quad (2-60b)$$

where \bar{x} and \bar{y} are the mean values of all x_i and y_i , respectively. In reality, however, measurements are subject to uncertainty, and the relationship described is not necessarily strictly linear. These discrepancies can be expressed by the error term e ,

$$e_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i. \quad (2-61)$$

The RMSE is often used to provide a meaningful description of this error

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n e_i^2}. \quad (2-62)$$

Multiple Linear Regression

In contrast to the simple linear regression discussed earlier, in multiple linear regression the target variable y depends on several explanatory variables x_i . Thus, the regression in Equation (2-59) becomes

$$y = a + \sum_{i=1}^n b_i x_i, \quad (2-63)$$

with n different explanatory variables. In vector notation, multiple linear regression is given by

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{b} + \mathbf{e}, \quad (2-64a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{b}. \quad (2-64b)$$

This is the result vector \mathbf{y} of the target variables y_i , the data matrix \mathbf{X} of explanatory variables x_{ij} , and the parameter vector \mathbf{b} , containing the regression parameters b_j . The error $\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{y} - \hat{\mathbf{y}}$ is also a vector quantity. It indicates the difference between the true target values \mathbf{y} and the estimated target values $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$.

2.5.2 Reduction of the Explanatory Variables

When analysing spectra, it is possible that many of the explanatory variables have a high degree of inter-correlation. This effect occurs when an absorption feature contains several measured values. A high degree of correlation between the predictor variables increases the variance of the regression parameter estimates, which can vary with small changes in the data. This problem is known as multicollinearity [87]. Generally, the

relevance of a group of explanatory variables increases with the correlation between the explanatory and target variables, but decreases as inter-correlation grows [88].

The rank of a matrix is the maximum number of linearly independent rows or columns. As the data matrix contains many correlated variables that require reduction, the rank of the data matrix $\mathbf{X}_{m,n}$ is less than or equal to the number n of possible explanatory variables. Reduction of interdependent explanatory variables can be achieved by two primary approaches: Variable selection and dimensionality reduction.

Variable Selection

The aim of the regression analysis is to determine the individual components of a sample from the PA spectrum. However, only a few measured values of the spectrum may be relevant. Once the relevant parts have been identified, it is no longer necessary to record the entire spectrum, which significantly reduces the measurement time. Another advantage of variable selection over dimension reduction is that the explanatory variables remain comprehensible. There are several methods for selecting variables, some of which are described below:

- **Low variance filter:** The variance of each column in the data matrix is calculated. Variables with a low variance are dropped because they have no influence on the target variable. For example, low variance occurs in regions of the spectrum where none of the components of the sample absorb radiation.
- **High correlation filter:** The correlation between the columns of the data matrix is calculated. If the correlation coefficient exceeds a certain threshold, one of the two variables (columns) is removed because the variables contain similar information [88].
- **Backward elimination:** A fully trained model is considered and compared with a model in which one variable has been removed. The variable that has the least impact on the model is removed. This process is repeated until only the most important variables remain [88].

- **Forward elimination:** Forward elimination starts with an untrained model. Then the most important variables are added one at a time until the model is sufficiently accurate [88].

Dimensionality Reduction

Compared with the variable selection introduced above, dimensionality reduction loses less information. However, the newly computed explanatory variables are more difficult to interpret. There are several methods for dimensionality reduction, some of which are briefly described below:

- **Factor analysis:** In factor analysis, variables are grouped according to their correlations, i.e. variables in a particular group are highly correlated with each other but have low correlation with variables in other groups. Each of these groups is called a factor, and the number of factors is small compared with the size of the original dataset [89].
- **Principal component analysis:** Principal component analysis (PCA) creates a new set of variables¹ from an existing dataset. A PC is a linear combination of the original variables. PCs are extracted such that the first PC explains the maximum variance and each subsequent PC explains the maximum remaining variance in the dataset.
- **Partial Least Squares Regression:** PLSR also involves dimensionality reduction, taking the target variables into account when determining the PCs.

The variable selection and dimensionality reduction methods presented in this thesis are only a small subset of all available methods. Further information can be found elsewhere, for example in a benchmark of 16 different feature selection methods on biodiesel data [90].

¹The newly created variables are called principal components (PCs).

2.5.3 Partial Least Squares Regression

The PLSR¹ combines dimensionality reduction with regression. Its basic functionality and the associated nonlinear iterative partial least squares (NIPALS) algorithm are discussed below.

PLSR is closely related to PCA / principal component regression (PCR), whereas PCA, in its original form, produces a set of linear combinations that capture only the characteristics of \mathbf{X} . It does not take into account how each explanatory variable may be related to the target variable. In contrast, PLSR generates a set of linear combinations that capture much of the information in \mathbf{X} , as well as the relationship between \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} [92].

PLSR and the associated iterative solution method NIPALS were developed by H. Wold and published in the *European Economic Review* in 1974 [93]. Five years later, in collaboration with R. W. Gerlach and B. R. Kowalski, the first paper on the application of PLSR to chemometrics was published [94]. Since then, PLSR has become the standard for analysing near-infrared spectra. A good summary of the historical background and of how PLSR works can be found in *Notes on the history and nature of Partial Least Squares (PLS) modelling* [95].

The partial least squares (PLS) method decomposes both the matrix of explanatory variables \mathbf{X} and the target matrix \mathbf{Y} into their corresponding linear combinations \mathbf{TP}^\top and \mathbf{UQ}^\top [92]

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{TP}^\top + \mathbf{E}, \quad (2-65a)$$

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{UQ}^\top + \mathbf{F}, \quad (2-65b)$$

with the matrices involved [92]

$$\mathbf{T} = \text{Scores}(\mathbf{X}), \quad \mathbf{P} = \text{Loadings}(\mathbf{X}), \quad \mathbf{E} = \text{Residuals}(\mathbf{X}), \quad (2-66a)$$

$$\mathbf{U} = \text{Scores}(\mathbf{Y}), \quad \mathbf{Q} = \text{Loadings}(\mathbf{Y}), \quad \mathbf{F} = \text{Residuals}(\mathbf{Y}). \quad (2-66b)$$

¹If there is only one target variable, it is called PLS 1; if there are several, it is called PLS 2. Since PLS 1 is a special case of PLS 2 in which only the first iteration of the algorithm is performed, the procedure for solving PLS 2 is described in more detail here [91].

The decomposition is based on the successive extraction of factors from \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} , and always maximising the covariance between the extracted factors \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{U}

$$\max \text{cov}(\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{U}) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{P}^\top + \mathbf{E}, \\ \mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{Q}^\top + \mathbf{F}. \end{cases} \quad (2-67)$$

The PLS method is suitable for the evaluation of univariate and multivariate target variables, allowing the analysis of multi-component gas mixtures.

The relationship between the dimensions of the matrices involved is shown graphically in Figure 2-13. The following relationships apply to the dimensionality reduction of the spectra considered:

- n is the number of data points within a spectrum,
- m is the number of spectra available,
- l is the number of principal components selected and
- k is the number of known compound concentrations in the sample.

Figure 2-13: Schematic representation of PLS and the involved matrices.

After introducing the matrices involved in PLSR, the general idea behind the NIPALS algorithm, which is used to obtain the scores employed in the regression, is explained. Figure 2-14 shows the exchange of information between the matrices involved in the PLSR as solved by the NIPALS algorithm.

Figure 2-14: Graphical representation of the steps performed by the NIPALS algorithm for PLSR.

The steps 1...9 performed by the NIPALS algorithm and shown in Figure 2-14 are explained in simplified terms as follows [88]:

- 0 The data matrix \mathbf{X} is centred.
- 1 The first score vector \mathbf{u} is initialised with the first column of the data matrix \mathbf{Y} .
- 2...5 The score vectors \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{t} are computed from the least squares solution for $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{t}\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{e}$ and $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{t}\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{f}$ (**inner loop**).
- 6 The load vectors \mathbf{p} and \mathbf{q} are calculated from the scores.
- 7 The residual matrices \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{F} are updated.
- 8 The next score vector \mathbf{u} is initialised with the first column of the residual matrix \mathbf{F} (**outer loop**).
- 9 This step is only necessary for the regression: The regression coefficient matrix \mathbf{B} is calculated.

A more detailed description of these steps can be found in Table D-2 in Appendix D.

For regression, the regression parameters \mathbf{B} are determined according to PLSR [96]

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{B}, \quad (2-68a)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{W}(\mathbf{P}^\top \mathbf{W})\mathbf{Q}^\top. \quad (2-68b)$$

This results in the following regression equation

$$y_{ik} = b_0 + \mathbf{x}_i^\top \mathbf{b}_k, \quad (2-69a)$$

$$b_0 = \bar{\mathbf{y}}^\top - \bar{\mathbf{x}}^\top \mathbf{B}. \quad (2-69b)$$

Chapter 3

Design of the PA Sensor

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the design, characterisation, and experimental validation of a PA sensor developed for TDL-based PAS. The entire process of photoacoustic signal generation and detection is described, from the selection and characterisation of the radiation source to the analysis of the detected acoustic signals.

The chapter begins with a detailed description of the experimental setup, including the ICL used as the radiation source, the custom-designed H-type PAC, and the detection and signal processing instrumentation. The ICL is characterised in terms of its wavelength-current relationship, optical power output, and spectral properties, establishing the operational parameters for subsequent measurements (see Section 3.2 and Section 3.3).

The design of the PAC is presented, with good acoustic resonance of the first longitudinal resonance mode prioritised. The resonator geometry is analytically determined based on acoustic wave theory. Calculated resonance frequencies and quality factors are validated through frequency response measurements, demonstrating excellent agreement between theory and practice (see Section 3.4).

A novel aspect of this work is its comprehensive analysis of the magnitude and phase of the photoacoustic signal. The phase behaviour is modelled using a damped harmonic oscillator and compared with experimental observations across the resonance spectrum. This approach provides deeper insight into the signal generation mechanism and offers a potential method for continuous resonance tracking (see Section 3.5.1).

The chapter extensively examines wavelength modulation techniques, comparing first harmonic $1f$ and second harmonic $2f$ detection. Measurements using ambient air,

methane, ethane, and propane demonstrate how the modulation depth affects spectral resolution and signal strength. The relationship between the modulated wavelength and the absorption line profile is explored, revealing the optimal modulation parameters for different analytical scenarios (see Section 3.5.2 and Section 3.5.3).

Particular attention is given to the in-phase and quadrature components of the lock-in amplified signal, revealing the presence and behaviour of RAM. The analysis shows that while the derivative of the absorption spectrum can be isolated in the X component through phase adjustment, RAM contributions partially remain in the Y component, introducing potential non-linearities that may affect quantitative analysis (see Section 3.5.4).

Finally, the analytical performance of the PA sensor is assessed through determination of the SNR, LOD, and limit of quantification (LOQ) for methane detection. Allan deviation analysis is employed to evaluate measurement stability and to project achievable detection limits with extended integration times (see Section 3.6). The results establish the baseline performance characteristics that represent the foundation for the multivariate analysis presented in subsequent chapters.

3.2 Experimental Setup

The experimental setup is shown in Figure 3-1, and all relevant components and their manufacturers are listed in Table 3-1.

Figure 3-1: Experimental setup for TDL-based PAS.

Electrical signals are represented by arrows in the direction of information flow.¹ The optical signal (laser beam) is shown as a solid red line and is emitted by a DFB-ICL with a centre wavelength of 3 349.7 nm. The laser current is controlled by a laser diode driver (LDD), while the laser temperature is kept constant by a thermoelectric cooler (TEC). A waveform generator (WG) provides the laser current set point to the driver.

Table 3-1: Components of the experimental setup.

Qty	Component	Model	Company	Address
1	Waveform generator	33511b	Keysight Technologies	Loveland, CO, USA
1	Interband cascade laser	DFB-280400	Nanoplus GmbH	Meiningen, Germany
1	Data acquisition card	USB-6210	National Instrumens	Austin, TX, USA
1	Laser diode driver	KLD101	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
1	Laser TEC controller	TTC001	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
1	Photo detector	PDA07P2	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
1	Lock-in amplifier	7265	Signal Recovery	Berwyn, PA, USA
1	Microphone	TOM-1537L- HD-R	PUI Audio Inc	Dayton, OH, USA

A vacuum-sealed PAC with 2 mm thick CaF_2 windows was positioned in the beam path. A detailed description of the PAC can be found in Section 3.4. The PAC was equipped with a highly sensitive, high SNR electret condenser microphone (ECM) to detect the generated sound. Its sensitivity was specified as (37 ± 3) dB², with an SNR of 68 dB³.

A fixed-gain indium arsenide antimonide (InAsSb) amplified photodetector (PD), sensitive to wavelengths from 2.7 μm to 5.3 μm , with a transimpedance gain at Hi-Z of 300 kV A^{-1} , was used to detect the PAC transmission. The active area of the detector measured 0.7 mm times 0.7 mm, which is smaller than the beamwidth of 2.42 mm. The sensitivity of the sensor at a temperature of 19 °C and a wavelength of 3.35 μm was $(4.7 \pm 0.2) \text{ mA W}^{-1}$. This gave a gain of $(1.41 \pm 0.06) \text{ V mW}^{-1}$ at the detector output.

¹Communication between the PC and LIA takes place via serial interfaces (RS-232). Communication between the PC, DAQ and WG takes place directly via a USB interface. Output signals from WG, PAC and PD are analogue voltages. The LDD regulates the laser current of the ICL.

²The sensitivity was measured at 1 kHz with the source separated by 50 cm. 0 dB corresponds to 1 V Pa^{-1} .

³The SNR is measured at 1 kHz with a 94 dB input, A-weighted.

A 14 bit, 250 kS s^{-1} data acquisition card converted the analogue detector signal to a digital signal, which was then stored and processed.

Unless otherwise specified, a dual-phase digital signal processing LIA was used in this work to detect and filter the analogue microphone signal. The LIA was configured with the following settings: external reference mode, 0 dB AC gain, 0.5 s integration time, and 100 mV sensitivity.

3.3 Characterisation of Interband Cascade Laser

In order to characterise the wavelength behaviour of the laser as a function of its current and temperature, the data provided by the manufacturer, Nanoplus (Meiningen, Germany), were used. Figure 3-2 a illustrates the current–wavelength dependency at three distinct temperatures. Using linear regression, the slope between wavelength and current was determined as $(0.0907 \pm 0.0020) \text{ nm mA}^{-1}$ and the slope between wavelength and temperature as $(0.3386 \pm 0.0032) \text{ nm}^{-1}$. The slight non-linearities observed in the current–wavelength relationship are consistent with interferometric measurements presented in Section 4.3.3. The stated uncertainties correspond to the calculated standard deviation. Figure 3-2 b illustrates the relationship between laser current and optical power. The threshold current of the laser was measured at 30 mA, and the emission power–current slope was 0.181 mW mA^{-1} , assuming linear regression. This resulted in output powers of up to 11 mW and a beam width of $(2.42 \pm 0.12) \text{ mm}$ (90 % fit).

A key parameter of the laser is its spectral linewidth γ , which directly impacts the coherence length $l_{\text{coherence}}$ of the emitted radiation [97,98]

$$l_{\text{coherence}} = \frac{\lambda_{\text{centre}}^2}{\lambda_{\text{FWHM}}}. \quad (3-1)$$

For a centre wavelength λ_{centre} of 3350 nm and γ of 3 MHz, or $\lambda_{\text{FWHM}} = 0.11$, this results in a coherence length of $l_{\text{coherence}} = 30 \text{ m}$.

Figure 3-2: (a) Wavelength λ of ICL for currents I_{electric} from 30 mA to 120 mA at three different temperatures. (b) Optical power P of ICL for currents I_{electric} up to 120 mA. The data were provided by Nanoplus (Meiningen, Germany).

3.4 Design of the PA Resonator

The PAC used in this work was designed with manufacturability, acoustic properties and system integration in mind. The H-shaped design was optimised to utilise the first longitudinal mode of the acoustic resonator [6]. More information about the fundamentals of photoacoustic resonators can be found in Section 2.3.5. Further investigations into the optimisation of the standard H-type cell can be found elsewhere [99–101]. The dimensions were adjusted to achieve the desired resonant frequency and a practical sample volume, while taking into account the constraints of the beam profile and the available manufacturing tools.

A sectional view of the aluminium PAC designed and used in this study is shown in Figure 3-3. The laser beam passed through the centre of the cell. The cylindrical resonance tube had a length of $l_c = 59$ mm and a radius of $r_c = 3$ mm. The two buffer volumes each had a length of $l_{\text{buff}} = 32$ mm¹ and a radius of $r_{\text{buff}} = 11$ mm. The ends of the cell were sealed with 2 mm thick CaF₂ windows, which had an overall transmission greater than 93% at a laser wavelength of 3.35 μm . All connections, including the two CaF₂ windows, were sealed with 1 mm thick fluoro-elastomer,

¹The 32 mm length includes a 31 mm borehole and a 1 mm seal.

German "Fluorkautschuk Material" (FKM) flat seals. The gas inlet and outlet were located in each buffer volume to minimise their effect on the acoustic resonance. The analogue condenser microphone was placed at the centre of the resonator, where the sound pressure level is at its maximum.

Figure 3-3: CAD drawing of the H-type photoacoustic resonator (sectional view). All relevant dimensions are indicated.

Due to the open ends of the resonator, its effective length l_{eff} , which determines the resonant frequencies, exceeded its physical length l_c ¹

$$\begin{aligned}
 l_{\text{eff}} &= l_c + \frac{16}{3\pi}r_c, \\
 &= 59 \text{ mm} + \frac{16}{3\pi}3 \text{ mm}, \\
 &= 64 \text{ mm}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3-2}$$

The sound pressure $p(r, \omega)$ within the cell result from the sum of all normal modes. In order to examine whether the longitudinal and radial or azimuthal modes overlap, the resonance frequencies were calculated. Equation (2-26) can be simplified for the normal modes as follows [5]

¹The effective length is introduced in Section 2.3.5 Equation (2-27).

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{k00} &= \frac{kc_s}{2l_{\text{eff}}}, \\
f_{0m0} &= \frac{\alpha_{m0}c_s}{2r_c}, \\
f_{00n} &= \frac{\alpha_{0n}c_s}{2r_c}.
\end{aligned} \tag{3-3}$$

The speed of sound in dry air $c_{s, \text{air}}$ at 20 °C and 1 atm is 343.2 m s⁻¹. By comparison, the speed of sound in pure nitrogen $c_{s, \text{nitrogen}}$ at 20 °C and 1 atm is 333.6 m s⁻¹. This gives, for the fundamental longitudinal mode,

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{100} &= \frac{c_{s, \text{air}}}{2l_{\text{eff}}}, \\
&= \frac{343.2 \text{ m s}^{-1}}{2 \cdot 64 \text{ mm}}, \\
&= 2.68 \text{ kHz},
\end{aligned} \tag{3-4}$$

for a PAC filled with air (2.61 kHz for a PAC filled with nitrogen) and for its odd harmonics

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{300} &= 8.04 \text{ kHz}, \\
f_{500} &= 13.40 \text{ kHz}, \\
f_{700} &= 18.76 \text{ kHz}.
\end{aligned} \tag{3-5}$$

For the first azimuthal mode

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{010} &= \frac{\alpha_{10}c_{s, \text{air}}}{2r_c}, \\
&= \frac{0.5860 \cdot 343.2 \text{ m s}^{-1}}{2 \cdot 3 \text{ mm}}, \\
&= 33.52 \text{ kHz}
\end{aligned} \tag{3-6}$$

and for the first radial mode

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{001} &= \frac{\alpha_{01} c_{s, \text{air}}}{2r_c}, \\
&= \frac{1.2198 \cdot 343.2 \text{ m s}^{-1}}{2 \cdot 3 \text{ mm}}, \\
&= 69.77 \text{ kHz}.
\end{aligned} \tag{3-7}$$

Since $f_{010} \gg f_{001}$ and $f_{001} \gg f_{001}$, these modes were not expected to affect the signal at f_{001} .

The PA signal increases with increasing buffer volume, but the effect diminishes for larger buffer volumes. The recommended radius of the buffers is at least three times that of the resonator, $r_{\text{buf}} \geq 3r_{\text{res}}$ [102]. The background signal is minimised if the buffer length equals a quarter of the acoustic wavelength, $\frac{\lambda}{4}$ [102]. For the first longitudinal mode $\lambda \approx 2l_{\text{eff}}$, the buffer length should be

$$\begin{aligned}
l_{\text{buf}} &= \frac{\lambda}{4}, \\
&\approx \frac{2l_{\text{eff}}}{4}, \\
&\approx \frac{2 \cdot 64 \text{ mm}}{4}, \\
&\approx 32 \text{ mm}.
\end{aligned} \tag{3-8}$$

To meet the above criteria, buffer volumes with a radius of $r_{\text{buf}} = 11 \text{ mm}$ and a length of $l_{\text{buf}} = 32 \text{ mm}$ were chosen.

3.5 Comparisson of Experimental and Analytical Results

The experimental setup described is used to validate the analytically determined properties of the PA resonator and the resulting WM PA spectrum. In addition to the PA magnitude, special attention is paid to the PA phase.

3.5.1 PA Resonance

To validate the calculated modes, a frequency response measurement was performed from 200 Hz to 10 000 Hz. The modulation frequency was gradually increased in steps of $\Delta f = 5$ Hz, with a pause of 600 ms between steps. The PAC was filled with 100 ppm methane in nitrogen under ambient conditions ($p_{\text{gas}} = 1$ atm, $t_{\text{room}} = 21$ °C). Changes in the resonant frequency due to the gas sample were negligible, as the nitrogen concentration was greater than 99 %. The ICL operated with wavelength modulation at a centre wavelength of 3 347.7 nm and a modulation wavelength of 0.364 nm, with an output power of ~ 8 mW, which matched a strong methane absorption line.

The raw recorded spectrum can be found in Appendix A, Figure A-1. In Figure 3-4, the measurement is shown compared to a harmonic oscillator model of the PAC, as described in Section 2.3.8.

Figure 3-4: Comparison between measurement and simulation of the acoustic resonances of the PAC.

The upper plot shows the lock-in amplified RMS amplitude R of the microphone signal. The frequency range covered the first and third harmonics. It can be seen that the measurement (blue solid line) agrees well with the theory (orange dashed line). The 1st harmonic was significantly higher than the 3rd. As the microphone was placed in the centre of the resonator, no significant signal was detected at the 2nd harmonic. The phase φ of the PA signal between the 1st and 3rd harmonics remained stable because the PA signal in this region was well above the background noise level. In regions where the PA signal could not be separated from the background noise, the phase became unstable. This was observed for frequencies below 2 kHz and above 9 kHz. The phase transition at the harmonics was clearly visible (vertical green dashed line).

The phase shown in Figure 3-4 was unwrapped and corrected for a linear phase shift of $0.022^\circ \text{ Hz}^{-1}$. The phase shift was caused by a time delay in the signal path from the WG to the laser's optical emission¹.

The maximum PA response occurred at 2 680 Hz with a resonance FWHM of 111.69 Hz. The 3rd harmonic perfectly matched $f_3 = 3f_1 = 8 040 \text{ Hz}$. Based on Equation (2-25), the quality factor of the PAC was determined to be

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q &= \frac{f_{\text{res}}}{\Delta f}, \\
 &= \frac{2\,680 \text{ Hz}}{111.69 \text{ Hz}}, \\
 &= 24.22.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3-9}$$

3.5.2 Wavelength Modulated PA Spectrum

The effect of line broadening has been theoretically demonstrated for methane in Section 2.3.3, in which absorption lines overlap and produce a more complex structure. To illustrate the direct relationship between the absorption spectrum and the wavelength-modulated PA spectrum, ambient air at natural humidity is used as the sample gas. The pure absorption line spectrum of water at $\chi = 1\%$ is shown in Figure 3-5.

¹This was confirmed by analysing the phase of the optical signal obtained from the PD rather than from the PAC's microphone.

Figure 3-5: Simulated line spectrum of water in the emission tuning range of the ICL. The spectral data was provided by HITRAN [2], reproduced with permission from Springer Nature.

It can be seen that the main absorption lines are well spaced so that they do not overlap¹. The resulting absorbance spectrum and its first and second derivatives are shown in Figure 3-6. The absorption spectrum was obtained from HITRAN [2] with simulation parameters $\chi = 1\%$, $T = 293.15 \text{ K}$, $P = 1 \text{ atm}$ and $L = 1 \text{ cm}$. The derivatives were then computed.

The dotted lines in the derivative spectra indicate the absolute value of the derivative. With WM, the PA spectrum is expected to resemble the absolute value of the first derivative for $1f$ modulation and the absolute value of the second derivative for $2f$ modulation. In $1f$ modulation, the emission wavelength is modulated at the resonant frequency of the PAC and the same frequency is used as the reference for the lock-in amplifier. In $2f$ modulation, the reference frequency of the lock-in amplifier is set to twice the modulation frequency of the emission wavelength. The modulation frequency of the emission wavelength is set to half the resonant frequency of the PAC.

¹Assuming a pressure of 1 atm and a concentration of less than 10 %.

Figure 3-6: Top: Simulated absorbance spectrum of water. Middle: Derivative of the absorbance spectrum. Bottom: Second derivative of the absorbance spectrum. The spectral data shown in the top plot was provided by HITRAN [2], reproduced with permission from Springer Nature.

3.5.3 Magnitude and Phase of PA Spectrum

In this study, the magnitude of the PA signal refers to the RMS amplitude obtained from the LIA, and the phase is the angle between the PA signal and the reference provided to the LIA. Further details are provided in Section 2.3.7.

Figure 3-7 shows the measured $1f$ WM PA spectra of ambient air at different modulation depths. The modulation depth I_{lc} was increased in steps of 2 mA from 2 mA to 20 mA, corresponding to a modulation wavelength from 0.091 nm to 1.820 nm. Measurements were carried out under ambient conditions of $P = 1$ atm, $T = 21$ °C, and $\phi_{\text{humidity}} = 45$ %.

Figure 3-7: Measured $1f$ WM PA spectra of water at different laser current modulation depths.

The measured $1f$ WM PA spectra in Figure 3-7 differ from the derivative of the absorption spectrum in Figure 3-6 in the following ways:

- At shorter wavelengths the strength of the PA signal decreased due to reduced laser power.
- The rising edges of the absorption band (to the left of the absorption line) produced a greater signal than the falling edges (to the right of the absorption line), which is attributed to RAM.
- The apparent linewidth increased with the width of the WM.

The modulation wavelength corresponding to the laser modulation current is given in Table 3-2.

Table 3-2: Modulated laser current ΔI_{lc} and modulation wavelength $\Delta\lambda$.

$\Delta I_{lc} / \text{mA}$	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18	20
$\Delta\lambda / \text{nm}$	0.182	0.364	0.546	0.728	0.910	1.092	1.274	1.456	1.638	1.820

An increased modulation depth from 2 mA to 4 mA resulted in an increase of the maximum PA signal R_{1f} from 19.51 μV to 21.22 μV . This is because, with a small modulation depth, only a small portion of the absorption line flank is modulated. When the modulation ΔI_{lc} was applied beyond the width of the absorption band (from 4 mA to 20 mA), the PA signal R_{1f} decreased from 21.22 μV to 17.29 μV .

Analogous to the $1f$ WM PA spectra, $2f$ WM PA spectra were recorded at different modulation depths. Similar to the $1f$ WM PA spectra, differences can be seen in the $2f$ WM PA spectra in Figure 3-8 when compared to the second derivative of the absorption spectrum in Figure 3-6:

- Towards shorter wavelengths, the strength of the PA signal decreased due to reduced laser power.
- The rising edges of the absorption band (left of the absorption line) resulted in a larger signal than the falling edges (right of the absorption line), this is attributed to RAM.
- The apparent linewidth increased with the depth of the wavelength modulation.

Compared with $1f$ WM, the generated PA signal peaked at the centre wavelength of the absorption line, but its maximum was smaller overall

$$\begin{aligned} R_{1f} &= 22.6 \mu\text{V}, \\ R_{2f} &= 12.9 \mu\text{V}. \end{aligned} \tag{3-10}$$

Not only is the magnitude of the PA signal of interest, but also its phase. Figure 3-9 shows the magnitude and phase of the $1f$ WM PA spectrum of humid air. The modulation amplitude was set to 4 mA, corresponding to 0.182 nm. Wherever the derivative of the absorption spectrum changed sign, the phase was shifted by 180° . From this behaviour it is possible to determine whether the PA signal was generated by a rising or falling flank

Figure 3-8: Measured $2f$ WM PA spectra of water at different laser current modulation depths.

of the absorption line. Here, the phase of all PA signals generated on rising flanks was approximately 90° , while that of signals generated on falling flanks was approximately -90° . In places where the PA signal was very weak, the phase was unreliable because it was heavily influenced by noise.

Figure 3-9: Measured $1f$ WM PA spectrum of water. Top: PA signal magnitude. Bottom: PA signal phase.

Figure 3-10 shows the magnitude and phase of the $2f$ WM PA spectrum of humid air. The modulation amplitude was likewise set to 4 mA. Whenever the second derivative of the absorption spectrum changed sign, the phase was shifted by 180° . From this behaviour, it is possible to determine whether the PA signal was generated in the region of the absorption line. Here, the phase of all PA signals generated when the absorption line was covered by the wavelength modulation (0.182 nm) was approximately 170° , while the phase of all PA signals generated when the wavelength modulation was next to the absorption line¹ was approximately -10° . In regions where the PA signal was very weak, the phase was unreliable because it was heavily influenced by noise.

Figure 3-10: Measured $2f$ WM PA spectrum of water. Top: PA signal magnitude. Bottom: PA signal phase.

3.5.4 X and Y of Wavelength Modulated PA Spectrum

If both the magnitude R and the phase φ are available from the PA spectrum, the in-phase component X and the quadrature component Y can be expressed as

¹The wavelength modulation must at least partially cover a flank of the (broadened) absorption profile.

$$\begin{aligned} X &= R \cos(\varphi), \\ Y &= R \sin(\varphi). \end{aligned} \tag{3-11}$$

More information on the in-phase and quadrature components, their relationship to the magnitude and phase, and the concept of lock-in amplification can be found in Section 2.3.7.

To bring the signal into phase with the modulation, the phase was rotated until Y was at a minimum. After the rotation, the shape of X corresponded to the derivative of the absorption band. Figure 3-11 shows the X and Y components of the $1f$ WM PA spectrum of ambient air at $T = 21.4^\circ\text{C}$ and $\phi_{\text{humidity}} = 40\%$. In this measurement, the

Figure 3-11: Measured X and Y of $1f$ WM PA spectrum of ambient air with 40 % rel humidity at 21.4°C .

phase was rotated to bring Y to a minimum¹. Nevertheless, it is interesting to take a closer look at Y . The shape of the residual in Y does not correspond to the derivative, but to the absorption spectrum itself. This is due to the presence of an out-of-phase RAM. This phenomenon has been observed in frequency modulation, where a phase difference between wavelength and intensity can occur, depending on the modulation frequency [40,103]. In the $1f$ WM PA spectrum, the RAM was partially or completely present in Y .

The same behaviour could be seen in the X and Y components of the spectrum of methane, shown in Figure 3-12, and the spectrum of ethane, shown in Figure 3-13.

Figure 3-12: Measured X and Y of $1f$ WM PA spectrum of methane at 100 ppm in nitrogen.

¹The minimum refers to the iterative solution of the least-squares algorithm.

What is particularly interesting about the ethane spectrum is that, while the actual WM PA signal was scaled by the average laser power (the signal was smaller at shorter wavelengths), the RAM was scaled by the modulation intensity and remained approximately constant. The Y component of the PA signal at $\lambda = 3344.5$ nm was still half as strong as that at $\lambda = 3348.8$ nm. For the X component, the signal at $\lambda = 3344.5$ nm was several times weaker and did not follow the expected derivative. This indicated that some of the RAM remained in X . The RAM introduces non-linearities into the $1f$ WM PA spectrum and could therefore adversely affect quantification.

Figure 3-13: Measured X and Y of $1f$ WM PA spectrum of ethane at 100 ppm in nitrogen.

3.6 Limit of Detection and Signal-to-Noise Ratio

Three key parameters are determined to assess the quality of the photoacoustic setup: the SNR, the LOD and the LOQ.

The following discussion is consistent with the well-established criteria for assessing the measured signal response, its variability, and the statistical significance of the numerical results [7].

In principle, PAS is a background-free technique and no PA signal is generated in the absence of an absorber. In reality, there is always a background signal S_{bg} present in every PA measurement, e.g. due to window absorption or electronic noise. The observed signal S_x of a PA measurement in the presence of an analyte x in the sample is given by

$$S_x = S_{eff} + S_{bg}, \quad (3-12)$$

with the effective instrument response S_{eff} due to the presence of the analyte x and a background signal S_{bg} .

The SNR is here defined as the ratio of the effective signal S_{eff} to the effective noise σ_{eff} ,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SNR} &= \frac{S_{eff}}{\sigma_{eff}}, \\ &= \frac{S_x - S_{bg}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_{bg}^2}}, \end{aligned} \quad (3-13)$$

where the effective PA signal S_{eff} is defined as the highest PA signal of the target substance minus the background PA signal, i.e. $S_{eff} = S_x - S_{bg}$. The term σ_{bg} denotes the standard deviation of the background PA signal measured in the absence of the target substance. Any offset of the PA signal, e.g. due to window absorption, is accounted for in the effective PA signal.

Following the recommended ranges of analyte measurement shown in Table 3-3, the LOD is defined as the lowest reliably detectable quantity of a substance with a 7% risk of false positives¹ and false negatives² [7]

¹False positives are conclusions that suggest the analyte is present when it is not.

$$\text{LOD} = \frac{3c_x}{\text{SNR}}. \quad (3-14)$$

For higher confidence requirements, the LOD must be set higher.

The signal at the LOD is not sufficient to provide significant information about the quantity of the analyte. As a minimum, the quantification range should be well above the LOD. Following the recommended ranges of analyte measurement shown in Table 3-3, the LOQ can be determined by

$$\text{LOQ} = \frac{10c_x}{\text{SNR}}. \quad (3-15)$$

It should be noted that the determination of the SNR, LOD and LOQ is performed according to *Guidelines for Data Acquisition and Data Quality Evaluation in Environmental Chemistry* [7] and may not be directly comparable with values reported elsewhere in the literature.

Table 3-3: Regions of Analyte Measurement analyte signal [7].

PA signal	Detectability
$S_{\text{eff}} < 3\sigma$	analyte not detected
$3 \leq S_{\text{eff}} \leq 10\sigma$	region of detection
$S_{\text{eff}} > 10\sigma$	region of quantitation

The SNR, LOD and LOQ for a single methane measurement were determined at a sample concentration of 100 ppm in nitrogen. The integration time of the lock-in amplifier was set to 0.5 s and the modulation frequency was adjusted to the resonance frequencies of the PA cell, which were determined separately for $1f$ and $2f$ modulation. Similarly, the laser current (and thus the emission wavelength) was adjusted to the value that gave the highest PA signal. The measurement was repeated 100 times. All relevant parameters are listed in the Table 3-4.

With the selected settings, the SNR of the $1f$ measurement was significantly higher than that of the $2f$ measurement, resulting in lower LOD and LOQ for the $1f$ modulation.

²Conversely, false negatives are conclusions that suggest the analyte is not present when it is.

Table 3-4: LOD and LOQ of methane, $N = 100$.

Parameter	$1f$	$2f$
Frequency / Hz	2729	1370.5
Laser Current / mA	57.25	56.25
Wavelength / nm	3346.356	3346.265
Methane Mean / μV	38.1068	18.9843
Nitrogen Mean / μV	0.3392	0.3492
Methane Variance / μV^2	0.09386	0.08793
Nitrogen Variance / μV^2	0.03627	0.03590
Signal / μV	37.7677	18.6351
Noise / μV	0.3607	0.3519
SNR	104.70	52.96
LOD / ppm	2.9	5.7
LOQ / ppm	9.6	18.9

The reported SNR and corresponding LOD can be further improved by increasing the measurement time. A common approach to analyse the relationship between variance (used for SNR calculation) and measurement time is the Allan deviation σ . The Allan deviation is a statistical measure of signal stability and is used to determine the optimal integration time τ for a measurement. It is calculated as the square root of the variance of the difference between two consecutive measurements [104].

The Allan deviation was calculated from the 100 methane measurements in nitrogen at a concentration of 100 ppm, considering only the $1f$ modulation. The implemented algorithm to calculate the Allan deviation can be found in Algorithm A-1. The results are shown in Figure 3-14. As the Allan deviation was linearly correlated with the integration time¹ over the entire time range considered, it can be assumed that, with sufficient total integration time, the LOD could be improved by at least a factor of 10, if required.

¹The total integration time is the sum of the integration time of each measurement.

Figure 3-14: Allan deviation from 100 measurements of methane at 100 ppm in nitrogen.

3.7 Discussion

Chapter 3 presents the experimental setup, followed by the design of the PAC and its validation. Furthermore, $1f$ and $2f$ WM PA spectra are presented for sample gases such as ambient air, methane, ethane, and propane. The LOD and LOQ have also been determined for the specific case of methane detection. Some of the results presented offer novel insights and may lead to new research opportunities, which will be discussed in more detail below.

Design of the PAC

The PAC has been designed to provide a balance between size, sensitivity and stability. The main features of the design are listed here, together with the advantages offered by the chosen parameters, possible alternatives, and the degree of agreement between the design and the actual measurements.

The PAC was designed to have a 1st harmonic longitudinal mode at $\sim 2\,700$ Hz. The measured value in nitrogen¹ at 21 °C was $f_1 = 2\,680$ Hz, which agreed well with the target frequency. The 3rd harmonic longitudinal mode was measured at 8 040 Hz,

¹As pure nitrogen is IR inactive, 100 ppm methane in nitrogen is used instead.

as expected. A frequency in the audible range was chosen because microphones and additional signal processing equipment are widely available as consumer electronics.

The volume of the PAC is approximately 26 cm^3 , allowing the measurement of small sample volumes. A 6 mm diameter acoustic resonator allows the collimated laser beam to pass through the PAC without the need for additional focusing. A smaller volume is possible, but will increase the resonant frequency of the PAC. Since most microphones are rated up to 20 000 Hz, there is scope for adjustment. For even smaller designs, QTFs or cantilevers are generally preferred.

With a Q factor of 24.22, the PAC provides reasonable gain while remaining relatively stable to small variations in resonant frequency, such as those caused by temperature changes. Under more stable conditions, for example by temperature control of the PAC, a higher Q factor may be advantageous.

It has been demonstrated that the amplitude and phase of the PA signal are consistent with the simulation of a harmonic oscillator. The method described in this study is new to PAS and could enable continuous tracking of the resonant frequency by monitoring the phase.

WM PA Spectrum

The optimal modulation current was determined for the detection of 100 ppm methane. The PA signal was highest at a modulation laser current of 4 mA, corresponding to a modulation wavelength of 0.364 nm. For the 1st harmonic modulation, a maximum PA signal of $R_{1f} = 22.6 \text{ } \mu\text{V}$ was measured. For the 2nd harmonic modulation, the value decreased to $R_{2f} = 12.9 \text{ } \mu\text{V}$. Although the PA signal strength was chosen for evaluation here, this is not the only way to determine the performance of the modulation. For example, a lower modulation laser current may be preferred to resolve fine structures in the spectrum.

In addition to the magnitude of the PA signal R , its phase φ has also been considered. Alternatively, the signal can be expressed in terms of its X and Y components. By adjusting the phase, the WM PA signal can be isolated in X . The magnitude represents the absolute value of the derivative of the absorption spectrum, whereas X represents

the derivative itself. Some, but not all, of the RAM remains in Y . The phase is not of interest for all applications. It remains to be seen whether removing the RAM is advantageous for quantitative analysis.

LOD and LOQ

The LOD and LOQ are estimated from 100 PA measurements of a single 100 ppm methane sample. For $1f$ WM, the LOD is 2.9 ppm and the LOQ is 9.6 ppm. For $2f$ WM, the LOD is 5.7 ppm and the LOQ is 18.9 ppm. Based on these estimates, $1f$ WM is the preferred method. These values are preliminary estimates. A more detailed consideration of quantifiability is given in Chapter 5.

If a lower LOD or LOQ is required, there are several optimisation possibilities. The Allan deviation indicates that increasing the integration time can improve accuracy. Increasing the integration time has the advantage that no changes to the experimental setup are required.

Chapter 4

Interferometrically Enhanced Modulation

4.1 Introduction

This chapter addresses a fundamental challenge in TDLS: the intrinsic coupling between emission wavelength and intensity in semiconductor lasers, which leads to RAM in WMS. A novel approach is presented that exploits optical interference in a MZI to partially decouple these interdependent effects, enabling enhanced spectroscopic measurements with improved spectral resolution and reduced artifacts.

The chapter begins with the development of a comprehensive mathematical framework for analyzing the MZM in both frequency and time domains. Unlike conventional approaches that calculate the modulator output in the time domain and subsequently transform it to the frequency domain, this work presents a novel method for direct calculation of the frequency spectrum. The model accounts for triangular phase modulation required to produce sinusoidal intensity output and derives analytical expressions for the discrete spectrum (see Section 4.2.1).

Experimental validation is performed using a custom-built free-beam MZM operating in the mid-infrared region around $3.4\ \mu\text{m}$, using a lithium tantalate (LT) electro-optic phase shifter. The half-wave voltage is experimentally determined to be 1.697 kV, and measurements are compared with analytical predictions across different phase modulation amplitudes and offset phases. The normalized mean absolute error between calculation and measurement is approximately 20%, with discrepancies attributed to external factors such as temperature fluctuations and wavelength variations during measurement (see Section 4.2.2 and Section 4.2.3).

The concept of interferometrically enhanced (IE) modulation is then introduced, offering two distinct operational modes. In IE intensity modulation, the laser current is modulated to alternate between destructive and constructive interference, achieving strong intensity modulation with significantly reduced residual wavelength modulation, demonstrated experimentally with an 83 % reduction. Conversely, in IE wavelength modulation, the system operates at stationary points of the interference pattern where intensity changes are minimal despite wavelength variation, thereby reducing the derivative of intensity with respect to wavelength by over 90 % (see Section 4.3).

The experimental implementation utilised a DFB-ICL with a center wavelength of 3 349.7 nm, characterised by its narrow linewidth (less than 3 MHz) and corresponding coherence length of approximately 30 m. A free-beam MZI with adjustable path lengths was constructed, incorporating a tilting window for phase control. It is operated at the Brewster angle for enhanced stability and reduced reflection losses (see Section 4.3.1).

The analytical description introduces an interference efficiency factor η_{MZI} to account for practical limitations such as beam divergence, misalignment, and spectral linewidth effects. Experimental measurements yield an efficiency factor of (0.51 ± 0.04) , demonstrating that careful alignment and collimation are essential for maximising interference contrast. The model successfully predicts the wavelength-dependent transmission pattern, with the optical path difference determined to be (10.55 ± 0.21) mm from consecutive interference maxima and minima (see Section 4.3.2 and Section 4.3.3).

The chapter demonstrates that the path length difference of the interferometer can be optimized for specific applications: larger path differences favor intensity modulation with minimal wavelength variation, while smaller path differences favor wavelength modulation with minimal intensity variation. A balanced design enables both modes of operation within a single setup, allowing simultaneous measurement of spectral amplitudes and their derivatives. This approach complements existing techniques such as $1f$ and $2f$ wavelength modulation spectroscopy and offers a practical solution to the long-standing problem of residual amplitude modulation in TDLS.

4.2 Mach–Zehnder Modulator in Frequency and Time Domain

Remark: Section 4.2 is largely based on the publication *Mach-Zehnder Modulator Output in Time and Frequency Domain – Calculation and Experimental Confirmation*, published in the special issue *Emerging Frontiers in Photoacoustic Spectroscopy Detection* in MDPI Photonics [37].

The MZI and MZM were introduced in Section 2.4, covering their historical development from Young’s interference principle through Zehnder’s and Mach’s independent designs. The working principle was established through the relationships between phase difference ϕ , transmission τ , and output intensity I_{MZI} , with key parameters including the half-wave voltage $V_{\lambda/2}$ and the phase dependence on optical path difference d .

In the following, a mathematical model of the characteristics of the interfering optical signal in the frequency (and time) domain is evaluated. This novel model allows the direct calculation of the modulator output signal in the frequency domain, based on the applied phase modulation. A possible application is its integration into a control algorithm, allowing optimised modulation.

4.2.1 Calculation of Mach–Zehnder Modulator Output Signal

The transmission of the MZM is a function of \cos^2 of ϕ (see Equation (4-48a) and Equation (4-48b)). Therefore, a triangular phase modulation of the PS is required to obtain a pure sinusoidal output signal. Since voltage and phase of the PS are proportional (see Equation (2-49)), the voltage modulation of the PS needs to be triangular as well. In Figure 4-1 the modulated phase $\phi(t)$ of the PS is shown.

Figure 4-1: Phase ϕ modulation of the PS. Solid line: within one period T_m , dashed line: outside the period.

The triangular voltage and phase modulation ϕ can be described as

$$\phi(t) = \phi_0 + |2\phi_m f_m t| \quad \text{for} \quad -T_m/2 \leq t < T_m/2, \quad \text{or} \quad (4-1a)$$

$$\phi(t) = \begin{cases} \phi_0 - 2\phi_m f_m t & \text{for} \quad -T_m/2 \leq t < 0, \\ \phi_0 + 2\phi_m f_m t & \text{for} \quad 0 \leq t < T_m/2, \end{cases} \quad (4-1b)$$

with the modulation frequency f_m and its period $T_m = 1/f_m$. The modulated phase ϕ_m depends on the peak-to-peak amplitude of the triangular voltage V_m (see Equation (4-2a)), the phase ϕ_0 depends on the voltage offset V_0

$$\phi_m = \pi V_m / V_{\lambda/2}, \quad (4-2a)$$

$$\phi_0 = \pi V_0 / V_{\lambda/2} + C. \quad (4-2b)$$

C stands for the voltage independent factors introduced in Equation (2-49). A resulting exemplary transmission according to Equation (4-48a) and Equation (4-1) with $\phi_0 = 0.8\pi$ and $\phi_m = 1.2\pi$ is shown in Figure 4-2 [3].

The transmission will be purely sinusoidal as long as $\phi(t)$ represents a linear sweep. Since the function is not differentiable (its derivative is not continuous), harmonics arise, which is undesirable in many applications. These harmonics will be further analyzed in the following.

Figure 4-2: Transmission τ_a of the MZM with $\phi_0 = 0.8\pi$ and $\phi_m = 1.2\pi$. Solid line: within one period T_m , dashed line: outside the period.

The phase-dependent cosine component of Equation (4-48b) is considered as the signal

$$s = \cos(\phi) \quad (4-3)$$

and this signal is assumed to be extended periodically for all time. This aspect will become important for the calculation of the resulting spectrum. Combining the triangular phase from Equation (4-1b) with the signal from Equation (4-3) and taking advantage of the fact that $\cos(x) = \cos(-x)$ leads to

$$s(t) = \cos(2\varphi_m f_m t + \varphi_0) \operatorname{rect}\left(\frac{t - \frac{T_m}{4}}{\frac{T_m}{2}}\right) + \cos(2\varphi_m f_m t - \varphi_0) \operatorname{rect}\left(\frac{t + \frac{T_m}{4}}{\frac{T_m}{2}}\right). \quad (4-4)$$

Hereby, the shifted rectangular function serves as a window function of width $T_m/2$ to translate the section-wise defined phase into an easy-to-transform mathematical form. It is centered at $\pm T_m/4$ and, thus, incorporates the sign difference shown in Equation (4-1b) at negative and positive time. By applying a Fourier transform, the complex spectrum $\underline{S}(f)$ of the signal can be calculated

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{S}(f) &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\delta \left(f - \frac{\varphi_m f_m}{\pi} \right) e^{j \varphi_0} + \delta \left(f + \frac{\varphi_m f_m}{\pi} \right) e^{-j \varphi_0} \right] * \frac{T_m}{2} \operatorname{sinc} \left(\frac{\pi f T_m}{2} \right) e^{-j \pi f \frac{T_m}{2}} \\
&+ \frac{1}{2} \left[\delta \left(f - \frac{\varphi_m f_m}{\pi} \right) e^{-j \varphi_0} + \delta \left(f + \frac{\varphi_m f_m}{\pi} \right) e^{j \varphi_0} \right] * \frac{T_m}{2} \operatorname{sinc} \left(\frac{\pi f T_m}{2} \right) e^{j \pi f \frac{T_m}{2}} \quad (4-5) \\
&+ s_{\text{DC}}(\varphi_m, \varphi_0) \delta(f) * T_m \operatorname{sinc}(\pi f T_m).
\end{aligned}$$

In Equation (4-5), the sinus cardinalis function is used in its unnormalized form $\operatorname{sinc}(x) = \sin(x)/x$ and $\delta(x)$ refers to the Dirac delta distribution

$$\delta(x) = \begin{cases} \infty & \text{for } x = 0, \\ 0 & \text{for } x \neq 0, \end{cases} \quad (4-6)$$

with a constraint to satisfy $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(x) dx = 1$. The * operator represents the convolution of the two functions. The term $s_{\text{DC}}(\phi_m, \phi_0)$ represents a possible DC offset of $s(t)$. This offset depends on ϕ_m and ϕ_0 but independent of time. As $s(t)$ is symmetric with respect to the y-axis, we can calculate it to be

$$s_{\text{DC}} = \frac{2}{T_m} \int_0^{\frac{T_m}{2}} s(t) dt \quad (4-7a)$$

$$= \frac{2}{T_m} \int_0^{\frac{T_m}{2}} \cos(2\varphi_m f_m t + \varphi_0) dt \quad (4-7b)$$

$$= \frac{2}{T_m} \frac{\sin(2\varphi_m f_m t + \varphi_0)}{2\varphi_m f_m} \Big|_0^{\frac{T_m}{2}} \quad (4-7c)$$

$$= \frac{\sin(\varphi_m + \varphi_0) - \sin(\varphi_0)}{\varphi_m}. \quad (4-7d)$$

The expression for $\underline{S}(f)$ in Equation (4-5) can be simplified using the properties of the convolution with a Dirac function (Equation (4-6)) as well as rearranging the phase shifts. The result is a purely real spectrum

$$\begin{aligned}
S(f) &= \frac{T_m}{2} \operatorname{sinc}\left(\frac{\pi f T_m - \varphi_m}{2}\right) \cos\left(\varphi_0 - \frac{\pi f T_m - \varphi_m}{2}\right) \\
&+ \frac{T_m}{2} \operatorname{sinc}\left(\frac{\pi f T_m + \varphi_m}{2}\right) \cos\left(\varphi_0 + \frac{\pi f T_m + \varphi_m}{2}\right) \\
&+ s_{\text{DC}} T_m \operatorname{sinc}(\pi f T_m).
\end{aligned} \tag{4-8}$$

The interim steps to get from Equation (4-5) to Equation (4-8) can be found in Appendix B.

Periodic repetition of the signal leads to a discrete spectrum $S_p(f)$. This discrete spectrum is defined only at multiples of the fundamental frequency $f = k f_m$ where $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Additionally, a factor of $1/T_m$ in the spectrum is obtained by changing the description of the signal to a periodic form. Depending on ϕ_m , the resulting spectrum may be at the peak of the sinc function or on the side slopes

$$\begin{aligned}
S_p(f) &= \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(f - k f_m) \left[\frac{1}{2} \operatorname{sinc}\left(\frac{\pi k - \varphi_m}{2}\right) \cos\left(\varphi_0 - \frac{\pi k - \varphi_m}{2}\right) \right. \\
&\left. + \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{sinc}\left(\frac{\pi k + \varphi_m}{2}\right) \cos\left(\varphi_0 + \frac{\pi k + \varphi_m}{2}\right) + s_{\text{DC}} \operatorname{sinc}(\pi k) \right].
\end{aligned} \tag{4-9}$$

The final result is a purely real, discrete, and symmetric spectrum. In Figure 4-3, the amplitude spectrum (frequency domain) of the previous example in Figure 4-2 (time domain) is shown. A numerical values of the discrete spectrum are given in Table B-1.

The amplitude spectrum at each valid frequency $f = k f_m$ can easily be calculated by taking the absolute value of the expression in the square brackets with the following k . All other frequencies have, per the definition of periodicity, an amplitude of 0. The solid green line in Figure 4-3 corresponds to the absolute value of the spectrum $|S(f)|$, normalized by T_m , and the blue stems are the absolute value of the end result when the signal is periodically extended $|S_p(f)|$. Additionally, the three summands of Equation (4-8) are plotted separately: the left shifted sinc function $B = 0.5 T_m \operatorname{sinc}\left(\frac{\pi f T_m + \varphi_m}{2}\right) \cos\left(\varphi_0 + \frac{\pi f T_m + \varphi_m}{2}\right)$, the right shifted sinc function $C = 0.5 T_m \operatorname{sinc}\left(\frac{\pi f T_m - \varphi_m}{2}\right) \cos\left(\varphi_0 - \frac{\pi f T_m - \varphi_m}{2}\right)$ as well as the DC part $A = s_{\text{DC}} T_m \operatorname{sinc}(\pi f T_m)$.

Figure 4-3: Amplitude spectrum of MZM output signal with $\phi_0 = 0.8\pi$ and $\phi_m = 1.2\pi$ and the summands of $\underline{S}(f)$: DC part A , left shifted sinc function B , and right shifted sinc function C .

4.2.2 Experimental Setup

The experimental setup used to validate the theoretical model of the interferometer is part of a project to detect volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in the air [105]. Since the VOCs have broadband absorption spectra, an OPO with a tunable wavelength of $3.2\ \mu\text{m}$ to $3.5\ \mu\text{m}$ is used as a light source. The pump laser is a high-power diode-pumped ytterbium fiber laser, with an emission wavelength of $1.064\ \mu\text{m}$ and a maximum output power of 10 W. Further details regarding the OPO used in this setup can be found elsewhere [106,107].

A schematic of the MZM setup is shown in Figure 4-4, with all important parts listed in Table 4-1. The free-beam MZM used is a self-construction and uses a LT PS two beam splitters and two protected silver mirrors. The LT crystal is coated with a broadband anti-reflection coating that reduces reflections to less than 1% in the wavelength range from $3\ \mu\text{m}$ to $4.5\ \mu\text{m}$. Floating electrodes allow differential voltage operation. The PS's voltage is controlled with a function generator and a high voltage linear amplifier including internal DC bias source ($V_{AC} = 0\ \text{kV}$ to $0.75\ \text{kV}$ and $V_{DC} = 0\ \text{kV}$ to $1.5\ \text{kV}$).

Figure 4-4: Mach-Zehnder intensity modulator (MZM) including PS for phase modulation, input I_e , and outputs I_{MZI} and I'_{MZI} .

To detect the MZM's transmission, an InAsSb fixed gain amplified PD with a range from $2.7 \mu\text{m}$ to $5.3 \mu\text{m}$ is used. The PD's transimpedance gain at Hi-Z is 300 kV A^{-1} . It is used at constant room temperature of 19°C and wavelength of $3.4 \mu\text{m}$, the sensor's responsivity at these conditions equals $(4.7 \pm 0.2) \text{ mA W}^{-1}$. This leads to an amplification of $(1.41 \pm 0.06) \text{ V mW}^{-1}$ at the PD's output. The signal is then processed by a data acquisition card.

Table 4-1: Components of the experimental setup.

Qty	Component	Model	Company	Address
1	Fiber laser	YLR-10-1064-LP	IPG Photonics	Oxford, MA, USA
1	OPO	Argos 2400-BB-5 Module C	Lockheed Martin	Bothell, WA, USA
1	Phase shifter	PS3T-MWIR1	QUBIG	Munich, Germany
1	HV amplifier	HVA-A075-D1.5	QUBIG	Munich, Germany
2	Beam splitter	BSW510	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
2	Mirror	PF10-03-P01	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
1	Photo detector	PDA07P2	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
1	DAQ	USB-6210	National Instruments	Austin, TX, USA
1	Function generator	33220A	Agilent Technologies	Santa Clara, CA, USA

4.2.3 Comparison of Experimental and Analytical Results

In order to validate the analytical results, they are compared with the measurements. First, the half-wave voltage of the PS was determined by measuring the radiation intensity in one of the interferometer arms while continuously increasing the applied

DC voltage from 0 kV to 1.4 kV, close to the upper limit of the voltage amplifier. The normalized measured values (orange crosses) with fitted squared cosine function I_{fit} (blue line) are shown in Figure 4-5. Scipy's¹ `curve_fit()` function was used to fit the data, which is a non-linear least squares optimization. Normalization was achieved by dividing the measured transmission by the maximum transmission of the fitted function $\tau = I_{\text{MZM}} / \max(I_{\text{fit}})$. At maximum destructive interference, 10 % of the normalized transmission was retained, resulting in a modulation depth of 90 %.

Figure 4-5: Normalized transmission τ of MZM dependent on applied Voltage V .

The half-wave voltage $V_{\lambda/2}$ corresponds to the difference between the applied voltage at minimum transmission (left blue marker) and the applied voltage at maximum transmission (right blue marker). The so-called quadrature point (middle blue marker) is exactly in between the two points of maximum and minimum transmission. It is often used as the preferred operating point of the MZM in bias voltage control algorithms. The half-wave voltage, according to a \cos^2 fit, turns out to be

$$V_{\lambda/2} = (1.697 \pm 0.083) \text{ kV} . \quad (4-10)$$

From the estimated variance σ_V^2 of the fit, provided by Scipy's `curve_fit()` function, the standard deviation error of the applied voltage $\pm \Delta V_{\lambda/2} = \sqrt{\sigma_V^2}$ were calculated.

¹Scipy is a Python library for scientific computing.

Since the PS power supply was limited to 1.5 kV, the phase could only be changed up to $\max(\phi_m) = 0.88\pi$, calculated by Equation (4-2a). For a pure sinusoidal signal, $\max(\phi_m) = \pi$ would have been required; this is also reflected in the further measurements.

From the presented analytical description of the MZM, the frequency-dependent signal $S_{p, \text{calc}}(f)$ can be determined for any ϕ_0 , ϕ_m , and f_m . Figure 4-6 presents the results from the analytical model, as well as amplitudes of the measured signal $S_{p, \text{meas}}(f)$ with the same parameters for ϕ_0 , ϕ_m , and f_m . The modulation frequency of the measurement f_m was set to 2.5 kHz and the sampling rate to 125 kHz with a duration of 2 ms. Matlab's implementation of the Goertzel algorithm [73,74] was used to determine the signal amplitudes of single selectable frequencies $S_{p, \text{meas, raw}}(f)$, which were then normalized by

$$S_{p, \text{meas}}(f) = S_{p, \text{meas, raw}}(f) \frac{\max(S_{p, \text{calc}}(f))}{\max(S_{p, \text{meas, raw}}(f))}. \quad (4-11)$$

The top row shows the fundamental signal $S_p(f_0)$ and the bottom row first harmonic signal $S_p(2f_0)$. The analytical results are on the left side, while the right side shows the measured values. In each diagram, the x-axis represents ϕ_m , while the y-axis represents ϕ_0 . The color shows the amplitude of the resulting signal $|S_p(f)|$ for the respective constellation: dark blue represents a high and light yellow a low amplitude.

To compensate, the external factors C in Equation (4-2b), the calculations were shifted along the y-axis by $C = 0.12\pi$. Qualitatively, calculation and measurement match well. The difference can quantitatively be expressed by the nMAE

$$\text{nMAE} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |(S_{p, \text{calc}})_i - (S_{p, \text{meas}})_i|}{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_{p, \text{calc}})_i}, \quad (4-12)$$

where $(S_{p, \text{meas}})_i$ is a single measured signal and $(S_{p, \text{calc}})_i$ is a single calculated signal.

For the fundamental a nMAE $(S_p(f_0)) = 19.40\%$ was calculated and for the 1st harmonic nMAE $(S_p(2f_0)) = 20.83\%$ was calculated. Fluctuations of ϕ_0 caused by external factors C , e.g. slight temperature changes or fluctuations in the OPO's emission

Figure 4-6: Calculated and measured signal power of fundamental f_0 and first harmonic $2f_0$.

wavelength during the measurement, are suspected to be the reason for the deviations of the experimental results.

In real-world applications, the extinction ratio can be rather small; this leads to a smaller amplitude of $S_p(f_m)$ and may also introduce a higher DC part of the signal $S_{p, meas}(f = 0)$. The response of the transmission to the phase difference and the phase difference to the voltage of the setup was consistent with the assumption of an ideal MZM.

4.2.4 Discussion

Instead of calculating the MZM signal in the time domain and then transferring it to the frequency domain, a mathematical model is provided with which the MZM signal can be determined directly in the frequency domain. Thanks to this novel method, the signal amplitudes of different frequencies can be determined efficiently and easily. The model of a MZM is valid for the case of the triangular voltage modulation of the PS. The

analytical results were validated by measurements with matching parameters for ϕ_0 and ϕ_m . Any remaining difference between measurement and calculation can be attributed to experimental uncertainties. To reduce the experimental uncertainties, the MZM's path length difference should be reduced to minimize the influence of wavelength and temperature on the interferometer.

The new understanding of the frequency domain of the MZM could be incorporated into a new voltage-control scheme for the PS. It is also conceivable to determine the wavelength from the signal of the MZM, which would eliminate the need for an additional wavemeter and would represent both a cost reduction and a simplification of the experimental setup.

The presented MZM operates in the mid-infrared region, which is of interest for many spectroscopic applications, but not easily accessible. It is not often used because the wavelength dependency of the PS leads to very high half-wavelength voltages, which is also the reason why the validation is limited to the range of the phase $\phi_{0, m}$ from 0 to 0.82π due to the maximum possible PS voltage.

4.3 Interferometrically Enhanced Modulation and Tunable Diode Lasers

Remark: Section 4.3 is largely based on the publication *Interferometrically Enhanced Intensity and Wavelength Modulation in Tunable Diode Laser Spectroscopy*, published in the special issue *Photonics: 10th Anniversary* in MDPI Photonics [38].

In Section 2.2, TDLS was introduced. In TDLS, a narrow linewidth semiconductor laser is used and current modulation is applied to scan gas absorption by direct absorption or WMS. Modulation improves SNR through phase-sensitive detection, but it intrinsically couples emission intensity and wavelength, producing combined IM and WM with a laser-dependent phase. In WMS, the resulting intensity artefact (RAM) distorts derivative spectra and reduces sensitivity.

Common solutions to address unwanted contributions from wavelength dependencies in the intensity and detector responsivity are dual-beam single-detector spectrophotometers with alternate sampling [48,108] and dual-beam double-detector spectrophotometers with simultaneous sampling [49].

In the following, an alternative method is presented that combines TDLS with an interferometer and provides a particularly simple means of reducing the corresponding undesired effect. The use of an interferometer, here an MZI, enhances modulation in two ways:

- It allows IM with reduced residual wavelength modulation by using alternating destructive and constructive interference.
- It allows WM with an almost constant intensity by modulating at stationary points of the interference signal.

4.3.1 Experimental Setup

Figure 4-7 shows the experimental setup for IE modulation in TDLS. All relevant components and their parameters are listed in Table 4-2. The radiation source was the DFB-ICL characterised in Section 3.3, with a centre wavelength of 3 349.7 nm. The LDD controlled the operating current, while the TEC controller maintains a constant temperature. A WG provided the laser current setpoint to the driver.

Figure 4-7: Experimental setup for interferometrically enhanced modulation.

The MZI was a free-beam design that allowed for adjustable path lengths l_a and l_b . The beam splitters BS_1 and BS_2 are 5 mm thick CaF_2 plates with a coating optimised for wavelengths between 2 μm and 8 μm . Radiation reflected by the beam splitters and

Table 4-2: Components of the experimental setup.

Qty	Component	Model	Company	Address
1	Waveform generator	33220A	Agilent Technologies	Santa Clara, CA, USA
1	Interband cascade laser	DFB-280400	Nanoplus GmbH	Meiningen, Germany
1	Data acquisition card	USB-6210	National Instrumens	Austin, TX, USA
1	Laser diode driver	KLD101	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
1	Laser TEC controller	TTC001	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
2	Beamsplitter	BSW510	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
2	Mirror	PF10-03-P01	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
2	Iris	ID20/M	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
1	Photo detector	PDA07P2	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
5	Mirror mount	KM100	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA

by the protected silver mirrors M_a and M_b experienced a 180° phase shift, while the transmitted radiation remained unaltered. Radiation passing through a beam splitter experiences a longer optical path, which is a consequence of the higher optical density of CaF_2 compared to air. Since beam a passed through BS_1 and beam b through BS_2 , the individual path lengths are roughly equal. The distance between the ICL and the detector along path b was 149 cm.

The two iris diaphragms A_1 and A_2 (alternatively, pinhole apertures could have been used) allowed precise alignment of the interfering beams. The gas sample was positioned between A_1 and A_2 in a vacuum-sealed 30 cm long cell with 3 mm thick CaF_2 windows.

To detect the MZI's transmission, an InAsSb fixed-gain amplified PD, sensitive to wavelengths from 2.7 μm to 5.3 μm , with a transimpedance gain at Hi-Z of 300 kV A^{-1} , was utilised. The active area of the detector had a size of 0.7 mm times 0.7 mm, which was smaller than the beam width of 2.42 mm. The sensor's responsivity at a temperature of 19 $^\circ\text{C}$ and a wavelength of 3.35 μm was $(4.7 \pm 0.2) \text{ mA W}^{-1}$. This resulted in an amplification of $(1.41 \pm 0.06) \text{ V mW}^{-1}$ at the detector output. A 14 b, 250 kS s^{-1} data acquisition card converted the analogue detector signal into a digital one, which was then stored and evaluated.

The length of l_b from BS_1 to BS_2 was 35 cm, whereas BS_1 and M_b reflected the beam at exactly 45° . The length of l_a from BS_1 to BS_2 was 36 cm. This distance is

slightly longer due to a smaller reflection angle of 40° . The ICL and the detector were at 149 cm and 150 cm, respectively. The different concepts for the PS are described in the following.

Tunable Phase Shift

A tunable PS is essential to compensate for phase drift resulting from temperature variations and to shift the modulation point. The modulation point is the point at which the change in I_{MZI} is minimal for wavelength modulation and maximal for intensity modulation. A tunable phase shift can be achieved in several ways:

- Through an electro-optic PS, typically a lithium niobate (LN) or LT crystal, employed in one of the interferometer arms. It is actuated by voltages of up to 1.7 kV in the $3\ \mu\text{m}$ wavelength region [37].
- Through a linear, piezo-actuated mirror positioned at either M_a or M_b (see Figure 4-7). The optical path length is altered by the transverse motion of the mirror, which in turn results in a phase change.
- Through a tilting window placed in one of the interferometer arms and actuated by a piezoelectric element or a stepper motor, thereby modifying the optical path length via internal refraction (see Figure 4-8). The lateral shift introduced by the window may be compensated for by the introduction of a second, counter-rotating window.

For phase modulation in the kHz range, the electro-optic PS is the optimal choice, as demonstrated in [37]. For slow adjustments, the piezo-actuated mirror or the tilting window is to be preferred, given their lower cost, larger aperture, and lack of high-voltage requirements. Because the interferometer is sensitive to changes in the mirrors' reflection angle, the tilting window was chosen for this application.

A 2 mm thick CaF_2 window fitted in a kinematic mount was used as the PS (see Figure 4-7). The kinematic mount had an angular range from -4° to 4° and a resolution of 0.5° per revolution of its adjustment screw.

Figure 4-8: Tilted window with the angle α for the incident radiation and β for the refracted radiation inside the window.

To reduce reflections, the window was initially positioned at the Brewster angle of CaF_2 α_{Brewster} and subsequently tilted from -1° to 1° . The Brewster angle was calculated by [77]

$$\alpha_{\text{Brewster}} = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{n_{\text{CaF}_2}}{n_{\text{air}}} \right) = 54.76^\circ \quad (4-13)$$

using the refractive index of CaF_2 $n_{\text{CaF}_2} = 1.4152$, at $3.35 \mu\text{m}$ and 24°C [109,110]. It was observed that a change in angle of 1° results in a transition from destructive to constructive interference, indicating a phase change of 180° . Further details regarding the refraction of CaF_2 can be found in Appendix C. The relationship between the outer and inner angles of the incident laser beam on the CaF_2 window is shown in Figure C-4.

4.3.2 Analytical Description of the Interferometrically Enhanced Modulation

To describe the output intensity I_{MZI} of the MZI, the general equation for the interference of two beams, labelled a and b, is used [77].

$$I_{\text{MZI}} = I_a + I_b + 2\sqrt{I_a I_b} \cos(\varphi_a - \varphi_b), \quad (4-14)$$

with the intensities I_a, I_b and their phases φ_a, φ_b . The phase of each beam is determined by the wavelength λ and the path lengths l_a, l_b and the average refractive index n

$$\varphi_a = \frac{2\pi l_a n}{\lambda}, \quad (4-15)$$

$$\varphi_b = \frac{2\pi l_b n}{\lambda}. \quad (4-16)$$

The difference between φ_a and φ_b can be expressed as

$$\varphi_{\text{MZI}} = \frac{2\pi dn}{\lambda}, \quad (4-17)$$

with the difference of the path lengths $d = l_a - l_b$.

From Equation (4-17), it can be seen that the wavelength affects the phase. To utilise this fact, a path difference is introduced, which results in a wavelength dependent phase change

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\varphi_{\text{MZI}, \lambda} &= \varphi_{\text{MZI}}(\lambda_1) - \varphi_{\text{MZI}}(\lambda_0), \\ &= \frac{2\pi dn}{\lambda_1} - \frac{2\pi dn}{\lambda_0}, \\ &= \frac{2\pi dn\lambda_0}{\lambda_1\lambda_0} - \frac{2\pi dn\lambda_1}{\lambda_0\lambda_1}, \\ &= 2\pi dn \frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_0}{\lambda_0\lambda_1}. \end{aligned} \quad (4-18)$$

Modulation Efficiency

Equation (4-14) is the exact solution for the intensity of an ideal interferometer. It should be noted that several technical factors may influence the observable intensities \hat{I}_{MZI} , \hat{I}_a , and \hat{I}_b . In what follows, experimental values are always notated with a hat, as in \hat{I}_a . To make the Equation (4-14) applicable to the setup, an interference efficiency factor η_{MZI} is introduced to obtain

$$\hat{I}_{\text{MZI}} = \hat{I}_a + \hat{I}_b + 2\sqrt{\hat{I}_a\hat{I}_b} \cos(\varphi_{\text{MZI}})\eta_{\text{MZI}}. \quad (4-19)$$

The observable intensity may be influenced by an interference pattern on the PD, which can be caused by the beam divergence of the laser or by misalignment of the two beams [97]. A schematic interference pattern commonly associated with divergent beams is shown in Figure 4-9 a. However, a detector with a small sensitive area like the one used here, will not measure the outer interference pattern, but only the interference of the beam centre. Furthermore, the intensity of a Gaussian beam decreases with increasing distance from its centre, thereby reducing the influence of the outer interference

To obtain the individual intensities \hat{I}_a and \hat{I}_b , the other beam is blocked in the MZI (see Figure 4-7). The measured intensities \hat{I}_a and \hat{I}_b as a function of the emission wavelength during a linear increase of the laser current are shown in Figure 4-10 a. The blue solid line represents the measured intensity \hat{I}_a , while the orange dashed line represents the measured intensity \hat{I}_b . The ICL threshold current was determined to be 35 mA.

Figure 4-10: Measured intensities \hat{I} , scaled with respect to the intensity at 100 mA laser current $I_{ICL@100mA}$: (a) beam intensities \hat{I}_a and \hat{I}_b separately; (b) interference of \hat{I}_a and \hat{I}_b generating \hat{I}_{MZI} .

The intensity values were normalised with respect to the intensity of the ICL at 100 mA, the highest current level used in the measurements. The ICL intensity I_{ICL} could not be measured directly without modifying the experimental setup. Using Equation (4-19), and assuming that $\cos(\varphi_{MZI})\eta_{MZI} = 1$ and that the interferometer is lossless, I_{ICL} is estimated by

$$I_{ICL} = \hat{I}_a + \hat{I}_b + 2\sqrt{\hat{I}_a\hat{I}_b}. \quad (4-20)$$

The maximum intensities \hat{I}_a and \hat{I}_b corresponded to approximately a quarter of the original intensity of the laser I_{ICL} , which was to be expected given that the two output intensities were not significantly disparate. The slight discrepancy in intensity observed between \hat{I}_a and \hat{I}_b , as revealed in Figure 4-10 a, was attributed to the reflectivity of the beam splitters. The absorption line at approximately 3356.5 nm was caused by water vapor in the air.

The normalised intensity of the MZI output \hat{I}_{MZI} with both interferometer arms in use is shown in Figure 4-10 b. By evaluating a pair of consecutive maxima or minima, the difference in the optical path length of the two interferometer arms dn was calculated by

$$dn = \frac{\lambda_0 \lambda_1}{\lambda_1 - \lambda_0} \quad \text{at} \quad \varphi_{\Delta\lambda} = 2\pi, \quad (4-21)$$

with the wavelength-dependent phase change $\varphi_{\Delta\lambda}$, defined in Equation (4-18). Averaging over all pairs of minima and maxima yielded in this example a dn of (10.55 ± 0.21) mm.

The interference's efficiency factor was determined from the measurements of \hat{I}_a , \hat{I}_b , and \hat{I}_{MZI} entered into a rearranged variant of Equation (4-19)

$$\eta_{\text{MZI}} = \frac{|\hat{I}_{\text{MZI}} - \hat{I}_a - \hat{I}_b|}{2\sqrt{\hat{I}_a \hat{I}_b}} \quad \text{at} \quad \varphi_{\Delta\lambda} = 0, \pi, 2\pi, 3\pi, \dots \quad (4-22)$$

For the setup presented here, a factor of $\eta_{\text{MZI}} = (0.51 \pm 0.04)$ was achieved.

The model was evaluated by calculating I_{MZI} using Equation (4-19) with \hat{I}_a , \hat{I}_b and η_{MZI} , and comparing the result with the measured \hat{I}_{MZI} . The results of the calculation and the measurement are presented in Figure 4-11. The good agreement between the measurement and calculation validates the analytical description of the MZI presented

Figure 4-11: Measurement \hat{I}_{MZI} and calculation I_{MZI} of the interferometer intensity of a laser current-wavelength sweep. For the calculation, dn was set to 10.55 mm and η_{MZI} to 0.51.

in this section. The small deviations can be attributed to non-linearities in the ICL emission characteristics presented in Section 3.3.

Interferometrically Enhanced Intensity Modulation

In IE IM, the laser current is modulated to switch periodically between a local minimum (destructive interference) and the subsequent maximum (constructive interference) of the MZI. To obtain a sinusoidal intensity output, a triangular laser current modulation must be used [37]. Figure 4-12 shows the IE IM \hat{I}_{MZI} compared with traditional IM of the same amplitude.

Figure 4-12: Traditional IM I_{ICL} and IE IM \hat{I}_{MZI} . Intensities scaled with respect to the intensity emitted at 100 mA laser current $I_{\text{ICL}(100, \text{mA})}$.

Since the change in intensity is considered to be the IM signal \tilde{S} , the normalized amplitude is calculated by

$$\tilde{S} = \frac{\hat{I}_{\lambda} - \hat{I}_{\lambda - \Delta\lambda}}{I_{\text{ICL } 100\text{mA}}} \quad (4-23)$$

and its bias \bar{S} by

$$\bar{S} = \frac{\hat{I}_{\lambda - \Delta\lambda}}{I_{\text{ICL } 100\text{mA}}}, \quad (4-24)$$

with the wavelength at constructive interference λ and the residual wavelength modulation $\Delta\lambda$.

In the case of the example illustrated in Figure 4-12, a modulation with $\tilde{S} = 0.51$ and $\bar{S} = 0.19$ for both the IE and the traditional IM was selected. For the traditional IM, represented by the orange dashed line, a residual WM of $\Delta\lambda = 3.0758$ nm was measured. For the IE IM, represented by the blue solid line, a residual WM of only $\Delta\lambda = 0.5187$ nm was measured. This corresponds to a reduction of the residual WM by 83 %. The grey dotted lines indicate the intensity when the laser current (and hence the wavelength) lies outside the intended modulation range.

An increase in the path length difference d of the interferometer would further reduce the residual wavelength $\Delta\lambda$.

Interferometrically Enhanced Wavelength Modulation

In the case of WM, the objective is to induce a wavelength shift and minimise the intensity change. To achieve optimal IE WM, it is necessary to identify the point of local interference, defined as the point at which the intensity I_{MZI} is at its maximum and its derivative $\frac{d}{d\lambda} I_{\text{MZI}}$ is equal to zero. A comparison between IE WM and traditional WM of the same amplitude is illustrated in Figure 4-13.

Figure 4-13: Traditional WM I_{ICL} and IE WM \hat{I}_{MZI} . Intensities scaled with respect to the intensity emitted at 100 mA laser current $I_{\text{ICL}(100, \text{mA})}$.

In general, a reduction in the WM depth results in a corresponding decrease in the residual IM. A reduction in path length difference dn also results in a decrease in residual IM within IE WM. In the case of the example illustrated in Figure 4-13, a modulation of $\Delta\lambda = 0.1812$ nm was chosen. This resulted in a residual $\tilde{S} = 0.0325$ and bias $\bar{S} = 0.7512$ for the traditional modulation signal, represented by the orange dashed line, and a residual $\tilde{S} = 0.0301$ and bias $\bar{S} = 0.5434$ for the IE signal, represented by the blue solid line. The grey dotted lines illustrate the intensity when the laser current and, consequently, the wavelength exceeded or fell below the intended modulation range.

For the derivative signal, which is considered a noise factor in WMS, $\frac{d}{d\lambda}\tilde{S}\Delta\lambda = 0.1785$ nm⁻¹ was obtained for traditional modulation, and $\frac{d}{d\lambda}\tilde{S}\Delta\lambda = -0.0135$ nm⁻¹ for IE modulation. It can be observed that the residual IM in IE WM primarily contributes to the harmonic components of the signal, but not to the fundamental component itself. This allows straightforward filtering using lock-in amplification.

4.3.4 Discussion

Methods for IE intensity modulation and IE WM in TDLS have been introduced. The proposed methods reduce the entanglement between wavelength and intensity, enabling the measurement of spectra with higher spectral resolution.

To obtain continuous spectra, the phase of the MZI needs to be adjusted using either an electro-optic PS, a piezo-driven mirror, or a tilting window. The tilting window was found to be stable in operation. The sinusoidal wavelength-dependent transmission of the MZI could also be used to generate a discrete spectrum with well-defined wavelength steps.

The calculation of the interference model is validated by measurements. The remaining differences between calculation and measurement can be attributed to changes in the refractive index over the wavelength range, non-linearities in the laser emission, or small variations in the path length, for example due to thermal expansion. Further investigations could be conducted into all of these factors.

An increase in the path length difference d of the interferometer favours IE intensity modulation, while a decrease favours IE WM. A balanced d allows both IE

intensity modulation and IE WM with a single setup, thus enabling the measurement of the signal amplitude \tilde{S} and its derivative.

An alternative approach to reducing noise in TDLS uses an unbalanced MZI, in which the second interferometer output is utilised as an intensity reference. By demodulating the transmission and reference signals, the noise can be suppressed [111].

The presented IE intensity modulation and IE WM may be used alongside conventional methods, such as $2f$ modulation in TDLS, to reduce modulation residuals [103,112]. This does not aim to replace such methods but rather to complement them.

The work described in this study, some of which has been published in scientific journals, lays the foundation for the implementation of IE modulation in TDL-based PAS sensors. Future research could focus on improving the stabilisation of IE modulation and comparing different phase-shifting techniques, such as etalon windows, EOMs, and piezo-actuated mirrors.

Stabilisation by a IE Modulation Control Loop

In order to maintain the IE modulation at each ICL emission wavelength, the experimental setup described in Section 4.3.1 requires the addition of a control unit to continuously adjust the PS. The complete experimental setup including the control unit is shown in Figure 4-14, and all relevant parts are listed in Table 4-3. Initial tests of the setup were promising.

Only the extended part of the controller is described below. The optical signal is detected by a PD and converted into an electrical voltage, which is read and processed by an Arduino Portenta. The Arduino microcontroller runs a Goertzel algorithm described in Section 2.3.7 to determine the intensity-modulated component of the signal. The implemented C code is presented in Appendix C, Algorithm C-2. A stepper motor rotates a CaF₂ window with 6 400 microsteps per revolution until the IM fraction is minimised.

Figure 4-14: Experimental setup for interferometrically enhanced modulation in photoacoustic spectroscopy.

Table 4-3: Components of the experimental setup.

Qty	Component	Model	Company	Address
1	Waveform generator	33220A	Agilent Technologies	Santa Clara, CA, USA
1	ICL	DFB-280400	Nanoplus GmbH	Meiningen, Germany
1	Laser diode driver	KLD101	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
1	Laser TEC controller	TTC001	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
2	Beamsplitter	BSW510	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
2	Mirror	PF10-03-P01	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
2	Iris	ID20/M	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
1	Photo detector	PDA07P2	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
5	Mirror mount	KM100	Thorlabs	Newton, NJ, USA
1	Lock-in amplifier	7265	Signal Recovery	Berwyn, PA, USA
1	CaF ₂ window	25.4mm x 0.3 mm	Korth Kristalle GmbH	Altenholz, Germany
1	Arduino	Portenta H7 Light	Arduino	Ivrea, Italy
1	Stepper motor	joy-it NEMA 08-03	SIMAC Electronics GmbH	Neukirchen-Vluyn, Germany
1	Stepper motor driver	DM430	ACT Motor Co., Ltd	Jiangsu, China

Chapter 5

Quantitative PA Spectrum Analysis

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents a comprehensive multivariate analysis approach for the quantitative determination of methane, ethane, and propane in gas mixtures using WM PAS. The primary challenge addressed was the spectral overlap of absorption bands in the mid-infrared region, which complicates the extraction of individual component concentrations using conventional univariate methods. PLSR is employed to decompose the complex overlapping spectra and extract quantitative concentration information even where absorption features interfere.

Gas sample preparation utilises a custom-built gas handling system with four calibrated mass flow controllers, enabling precise preparation of multicomponent gas mixtures with concentrations up to 100 ppm per component. The system design minimises adsorption effects through the exclusive use of stainless steel and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) materials (see Section 5.2.1).

A key aspect of the methodology is the experimental design strategy employed to generate training, validation, and test datasets. The training dataset follows a 3-component, 4-stage simplex-lattice design as specified in the *2020 NIST Handbook*. This design ensures comprehensive coverage of the concentration space from 0 to 100 ppm while capturing component interactions through systematically selected mixture compositions. Ten replicate measurements per sample composition provide sufficient statistical variation to prevent overfitting during model training. The validation dataset employs a simplified 3-stage simplex-lattice design with five replicates per sample, while the test dataset consists of randomised mixtures designed to evaluate model performance under realistic analytical conditions. The datasets are strictly segregated

to enable unbiased performance assessment, following standard practice with approximately 70 % training data, 15 % validation data, and 15 % test data (see Section 5.2.3).

The chapter explores multiple approaches to evaluate wavelength importance within the PA spectra. Variance-covariance and correlation matrices provide target-independent assessments of spectral feature relationships, revealing which wavelength regions exhibit high variance and which regions demonstrate low correlation, both desirable characteristics for regression analysis. The PLS loadings offer a complementary target-dependent perspective, quantifying how strongly each wavelength contributes to the prediction of individual component concentrations. For methane and ethane, the loadings are highest in spectral regions where their respective PA signals are strongest. For propane, which exhibits a broader, lower-intensity spectrum, the loadings are strategically elevated in regions where methane and ethane signals are minimal, demonstrating the algorithm's ability to exploit complementary spectral information (see Section 5.3).

Prediction performance is assessed using RMSE metrics across the training, validation, and test datasets. The analysis demonstrates that with three PCs, the RMSE for concentration predictions ranges from 1.77 ppm to 5.74 ppm across the three target gases in the test dataset. These values are compared against the baseline LOD of 2.9 ppm for methane established in Section 3.6, confirming that prediction errors are consistent with the fundamental detection capabilities of the sensor. Additional investigations examine the isolated in-phase component of the PA signal, revealing improved prediction accuracy for methane and ethane but degraded performance for propane, suggesting complex interactions between RAM and quantitative analysis that warrant further investigation (see Section 5.4).

The optimal number of PCs n_{PC} is systematically determined through validation dataset analysis across $n_{PC} = 1, 2, \dots, 12$. The results indicate minimal non-linearity in the dataset, with $n_{PC} = 3$ providing optimal performance that matches the number of target analytes. This finding suggests that the simplex-lattice experimental design successfully captured the dominant variance sources without introducing excessive non-linear effects from component interactions (see @Section 5.4).

The chapter establishes that PLSR combined with structured experimental design enables reliable quantitative analysis of multicomponent gas mixtures even in the presence of significant spectral overlap. The prediction errors achieved are comparable to the fundamental detection limits of the PA sensor, demonstrating that multivariate analysis does not introduce significant additional uncertainty beyond the baseline measurement capabilities. These results validate the approach for practical applications requiring simultaneous quantification of multiple light alkanes in complex gas matrices.

5.2 Experiment Design

The experimental setup used to measure the PA WM spectra is covered in Section 3.2. Also of interest are the sample preparation and the composition of the datasets used for subsequent analysis. Both are presented below.

5.2.1 Sample Preparation

Figure 5-1 shows the piping and instrumentation diagram (P&ID) of the gas handling setup used in this study, the components shown are listed in Table 5-1. Four calibration/test gases are supplied in pressurised steel cylinders. Single-stage cylinder pressure regulators reduce the storage pressure (around (150 – 200) bar) to the mass flow controller (MFC) working pressure of 1.5 bar (shown as digital valves).

A photograph of the four MFCs used in the gas handling system can be found in Figure D-5 in Appendix D. The maximum relative error of each MFC is specified as up to 1 %. A filter prevents dust from entering the photoacoustic cell. Two valves can be closed during measurements to prevent gas flow or leakage.

The gas handling system is resistant to most chemicals as it consists only of stainless-steel components and PTFE pipes. Adsorption problems in the gas handling system are particularly severe for polar molecules with large dipole moments, such as water ($\mu = 1.85$ D) and ammonia ($\mu = 1.47$ D) [113]. The sample gases used here are not strongly polarised: methane ($\mu = 0$ D), ethane ($\mu = 0$ D), propane ($\mu = 0.08$ D).

Figure 5-1: P&ID of the gas flow system allowing the preparation of defined gas mixtures of methane, ethane, propane, and nitrogen.

Table 5-1: Components of the gas flow system.

Qty	Component	Model	Company	Address
1	High-Pressure Cylinder: 100 ppm methane	volume: 2 l, pressure: 200 bar	Westfalen AG	Münster, Germany
1	High-Pressure Cylinder: 100 ppm ethane	volume: 10 l, pressure: 150 bar	Linde GmbH	Pullach, Germany
1	High-Pressure Cylinder: 100 ppm propane	volume: 10 l, pressure: 150 bar	Linde GmbH	Pullach, Germany
1	High-Pressure Cylinder: nitrogen	volume: 10 l, pressure: 150 bar	E. Howe GmbH & CO. KG	Steinfurt, Germany
4	Single stage cylinder pressure regulator	C2001/1-3B	Linde GmbH	Pullach, Germany
4	Mass flow controller	GSC-A9TA-BB23	Vögtlin Instruments GmbH	Muttenz, Swiss
1	Filter	0001619154 0.5 micron	Swagelok	Ohio, USA
2	Valve	SS-6P4I-MM	Swagelok	Ohio, USA

5.2.2 Linearity of the PA Signal

The linear regression, together with the quadratic deviations of the individual values, is shown graphically in Figure 5-2. While all measurements from 0 to 75 ppm were taken on the same day, the measurements at 100 ppm were taken on a different day. For measurements taken on the same day, the data show good linearity, whereas measurements from different days show greater deviation from the regression line.

Figure 5-2: Linear regression of the PA signal for methane and ethane measured at different concentrations.

5.2.3 Dataset for Multivariate Analysis

Proper PLSR analysis requires separate training, validation and test measurements. Common ratios are 70 % for training data, 15 % for validation data and 15 % for test data. The exact sample and measurement numbers are shown in Figure 5-3. It is important to keep the three parts strictly separate to make reliable statements about the performance of the PLSR.

Figure 5-3: Dataset split into training, validation and testing data.

Training Data

The training data were based on a 3-component, 4-stage simplex-lattice design, as outlined in the *2020 NIST Handbook* [114]. The simplex-lattice design ensured comprehensive coverage of a defined concentration range from 0 to 100 ppm per component, while also capturing the interactions between the components. This design remains flexible, as it allows components to be replaced or added without repeating all measurements. Ten replicate measurements were taken per sample to provide sufficient variation and avoid overfitting during training. The precise concentrations selected are listed in Table 5-2.

Validation Data

Similar to the training measurements, the validation measurements were based on a 3-component simplex-lattice design, but with only 3 stages. This provided a sufficient difference from the training data and reduced the number of measurements. Measurements at 100 ppm per sample were not taken, as these would have been redundant with the test data. Furthermore, the number of measurements per sample was reduced from 10 to 5, as the variation within a sample is less important here than in the training data. The precise concentrations selected are listed in Table 5-3.

Table 5-2: Training Data based on a Simplex-Lattice Design for 3 components with $q = 4$.

Interaction	a	b	c	N
	Methane / ppm	Ethane / ppm	Propane / ppm	
-	0	0	0	10
a	100	0	0	10
b	0	100	0	10
c	0	0	100	10
a-b	75	25	0	10
a-b	50	50	0	10
a-b	25	75	0	10
a-c	75	0	25	10
a-c	50	0	50	10
a-c	25	0	75	10
b-c	0	75	25	10
b-c	0	50	50	10
b-c	0	25	75	10
a-b-c	50	25	25	10
a-b-c	25	50	25	10
a-b-c	25	25	50	10

Table 5-3: Validation Data based on a Simplex-Lattice Design for 3 components with $q = 3$.

Interaction	a	b	c	N
	Methane / ppm	Ethane / ppm	Propane / ppm	
a-b	$66.\bar{6}$	$33.\bar{3}$	0	5
a-b	$33.\bar{3}$	$66.\bar{6}$	0	5
a-c	$66.\bar{6}$	0	$33.\bar{3}$	5
a-c	$33.\bar{3}$	0	$66.\bar{6}$	5
b-c	0	$66.\bar{6}$	$33.\bar{3}$	5
b-c	0	$33.\bar{3}$	$66.\bar{6}$	5
a-b-c	$33.\bar{3}$	$33.\bar{3}$	$33.\bar{3}$	5

Test Data

Finally, the test measurements were collected. These were prepared by creating randomised mixtures with the same number of samples and measurements as in the validation data. The precise concentrations selected are listed in Table 5-4.

Table 5-4: Test Data based on randomised mixtures.

Interaction	a	b	c	d	<i>N</i>
	Methane / ppm	Ethane / ppm	Propane / ppm	Nitrogen / ppm ^a	
a-b-c-d	17	45	3	35	5
a-b-c-d	35	13	25	27	5
a-b-c-d	32	16	25	27	5
a-b-c-d	32	4	21	43	5
a-b-c-d	14	47	9	30	5
a-b-c-d	17	17	45	21	5
a-b-c-d	19	26	38	17	5

^aProportion of pure nitrogen used to dilute the mixture.

5.3 Importance of Individual Wavelengths

The results of the quantitative analysis of the WM PA spectra include the evaluation of the importance of individual wavelengths. This was achieved by considering the variance-covariance matrix, the correlation matrix and the loadings of the PLS.

Variance-Covariance and Correlation

The variance-covariance matrix of the training data is shown in Figure 5-4 (a). The indices of the explanatory variables can be read from the abscissa i and the ordinate j . At positions in the spectrum where characteristic absorptions occur, the heat map appears bright. The lighter the heat map, the greater the variance or covariance.

Similarly, the correlation matrix of the training data is shown in Figure 5-4 (b). The indices of the explanatory variables can be read from the abscissa i and the ordinate j . Regions of the spectrum that correlate with each other are shown in bright colours on the heat map. The lighter the heat map, the higher the correlation. As the correlations are normalised, the main diagonal ($i = j$) is filled with ones.

The training dataset was chosen because no information from the validation or test datasets was allowed to leak into the training phase. It also provided the best coverage of the full range of measurements.

Figure 5-4: Visualisation of (a) Variance-Covariance and (b) correlation matrix of the data matrix, containing the measured spectra.

Loadings of the PLS

The covariance and the correlation coefficient weigh the importance of features independent of the target. Another approach to weigh the target dependent importance of the features are the PLS loadings. Figure 5-5 shows all spectra and the loadings of the different target molecules of the training dataset. The top half shows the PA spectrum, while the bottom half shows the PLS loadings P . The loadings (analogous to weights) indicate how strongly the features, in this case the PA signals at the respective wavelengths, contribute to the regression¹.

Typically, the loadings are high in wavelength regions with strong PA signals for the target molecule. For strongly overlapping spectra, the region of high loadings may differ significantly from the region of high PA signals. The loadings for each target molecule, determined from the training data, show that for ethane (orange line) and methane (blue line) the loadings are high where their respective PA signals are strong. For propane (green line), which has a broader, lower intensity PA spectrum, the loadings are elevated in spectral regions where the PA signals of the other two target molecules are weak.

¹Regression is used to determine the concentration of the sample.

Figure 5-5: Top: Spectra from the training dataset. Bottom: Loadings calculated from PLSR.

5.4 Concentration Prediction Error

The n spectra, measured at m wavelengths, were combined into the data matrix \mathbf{X} of size (n, m) for subsequent analysis. The concentrations of the components in each gas mixture were determined from the recorded spectra. These individual concentrations were stored in the target matrix \mathbf{Y} .

A PLSR was performed on the entire training dataset without feature selection. Even before using the validation data, a technique called cross-validation (CV) can be used to assess the performance of the PLSR prediction. This involves withholding one or more measurements from the training data and using them for validation. This process is repeated until each measurement has been used for validation. In this study, 10-fold CV was applied to the randomised data matrix. The RMSE of the CV prediction, together with the RMSE for the validation and test data, are given in Table 5-5. The

corresponding mean error and its standard deviation can be found in Table D-3 in Appendix D. Training was performed on the entire training set to obtain the validation and test results.

Table 5-5: RMSE of the prediction for 3 PCs

Dataset	Methane / ppm	Ethane / ppm	Propane / ppm
Training CV	5.18	4.78	9.69
Validation	3.83	3.82	2.84
Testing	1.77	2.77	5.74

In-Phase Dataset

Section 3.5.4 explains how the PA signal can be divided into in-phase and quadrature components, with the latter containing only noise and a portion of the RAM. As reducing the RAM is one of the objectives of IE modulation for PAS, the PLSR data analysis procedure was performed using only the in-phase component. Similar to the previously presented results, Table 5-6 contains the RMSE of the CV, validation and test data predictions. The corresponding mean error and standard deviation can be found in Table D-4 in Appendix D.

Table 5-6: RMSE of the prediction of the in-phase dataset for 3 PCs.

Dataset	Methane / ppm	Ethane / ppm	Propane / ppm
Training CV	3.65	3.13	21.32
Validation	2.56	1.44	8.38
Testing	2.05	1.36	19.04

Analogous to the in-phase dataset, the same analysis was performed on the quadrature dataset. The RMSE values of the predictions are presented in Table 5-7. The corresponding mean error and standard deviation can be found in Table D-5 in Appendix D.

Table 5-7: RMSE of the prediction of the quadrature dataset for 3 PCs

Dataset	Methane / ppm	Ethane / ppm	Propane / ppm
Training CV	11.86	6.30	22.42
Validation	13.16	2.98	13.55
Testing	10.40	3.24	12.37

Number of PCs

Often, the number of PCs n_{PC} required to achieve accurate PLSR predictions exceeds the actual number of target molecules. This discrepancy can be due to the presence of unidentified components in the sample or to non-linear effects, such as interactions between components [96]. In order to determine whether these effects were present, training was performed with different numbers of PCs ($n_{PC} = 1, 2, \dots, 12$) and the predictions were subsequently examined using the validation dataset. The results are shown in Figure 5-6. The markers indicate the mean error \bar{e} and the error bars indicate the standard deviation of the error.

Figure 5-6: Prediction error of validation data for different numbers of PCs.

5.5 Discussion

The following discussion addresses the results presented above. Particular attention is given to the importance of individual wavelengths for multivariate analysis and to PLSR concentration prediction errors.

Importance of the Wavelengths

The variance–covariance and correlation matrices were presented alongside the PLS loadings to evaluate the importance of individual wavelengths in the PA spectrum for quantitative analysis.

Due to the non-normalised nature of the variance-covariance matrix, the ethane absorption line ($i > 200$) dominated the values, making meaningful evaluation difficult. The correlation matrix, by contrast, showed clear differences across all variables. Smaller values indicate lower correlation between variables indexed i and j . Variables that are uncorrelated are usually preferred for regression analysis. Thus, if the variable at index i was chosen because it has a high variance at around 210, useful complementary variables were found in the range $j = 70$ to 110.

Unlike the variance, covariance and the regression coefficient, the loadings weight each wavelength for each component. This allows portions of the spectrum that are particularly important for certain components to be identified.

Prediction Accuracy

The multivariate analysis was performed on a dataset consisting of training, validation and test data. Table 5-8 shows the mean concentrations for the different datasets. Because of the experimental design, the concentrations were evenly distributed. Given the 1 % accuracy of the MFC, the expected uncertainties are 0.31 ppm for the training dataset, 0.33 ppm for the validation dataset and 0.24 ppm for the test dataset.

Table 5-8: Mean concentration of components in datasets

Dataset	Methane / ppm	Ethane / ppm	Propane / ppm
Training CV	31.25	31.25	31.25
Validation	33.3	33.3	33.3
Testing	23.71	24.00	23.71

The PLSR prediction errors were higher than the concentration uncertainty in the samples:

- For the validation dataset, the RMSE of the methane, ethane and propane concentration predictions were 1.77 ppm, 2.77 ppm and 5.74 ppm, respectively.
- For the test dataset, the RMSE of the methane, ethane and propane concentration predictions were 3.83 ppm, 3.82 ppm and 2.84 ppm, respectively.

For comparison, the LOD for methane was determined to be 2.9 ppm in Section 3.6. Consequently, the PLSR prediction errors reported here are consistent with expectations. The stated uncertainties apply only to gas mixtures comprising these three components, with a maximum concentration of 100 ppm per component.

It should be noted that, while the absorption spectrum of a gas mixture can be seen as the sum of its individual components, this is not the case for the WM PA magnitude spectrum. It is linear only where the features do not overlap. This could have a negative effect on regression analysis. It can be dealt with in several ways. The non-linearities can be compensated for by increasing the number of PCs in the PLSR. Alternatively, the derivative spectrum, which is linear, could be determined from magnitude and phase. The PLSR results for the isolated in-phase component of the PA WM signal suggest that prediction errors decreased for methane and ethane but increased for propane:

- For the validation dataset, the RMSE values for the methane, ethane, and propane concentration predictions were 2.56 ppm, 1.44 ppm, and 8.38 ppm, respectively.
- For the test dataset, the RMSE values for the methane, ethane, and propane concentration predictions were 2.05 ppm, 1.36 ppm, and 19.04 ppm, respectively.

The increased prediction error for propane could be due to the RAM present in the spectrum, it could be beneficial in some circumstances. However, further investigation is required to draw any final conclusions.

Number of PCs

It was observed that the prediction error e for $n_{PC} < 3$ and for $n_{PC} > 6$ led to inaccurate predictions. It can therefore be assumed that there was little or no non-linearity in the

dataset. Therefore, $n_{\text{PC}} = 3$ was selected for training in this study. If the application required avoiding particularly negative prediction errors, $n_{\text{PC}} = 5$ or $n_{\text{PC}} = 6$ would be appropriate.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

6.1 Summary of Findings

This dissertation has addressed a fundamental challenge in TDLS: the intrinsic coupling between emission intensity and wavelength in semiconductor lasers, which manifests as RAM in WMS. Through theoretical analysis, experimental validation, and multivariate data analysis, this work has advanced the state of the art of PAS based on wavelength modulation TDLS by introducing the novel concept of IE modulation and demonstrating its practical application for quantitative gas detection.

The research objectives established in Chapter 1 have been systematically addressed through the development of a PA sensor system for the detection and quantification of methane, ethane, and propane in multi-component gas mixtures. The sensor combines a DFB-ICL operating at a wavelength of 3.35 μm , a custom-designed H-type resonant PA cell with a resonance quality factor of 24.22, and phase-sensitive lock-in amplification of the microphone signal. The system achieves detection limits in the low ppm range, with a demonstrated limit of detection of 2.9 ppm for methane.

The quantitative capabilities of the PA sensor have been evaluated through PLSR analysis of multicomponent gas mixtures. A structured experimental design based on a 3-component, 4-stage simplex-lattice methodology ensured coverage of the concentration space from 0 to 100 ppm per component. The analysis of variance-covariance matrices, correlation structures, and partial least squares loadings provided insights into the wavelength-dependent importance of spectral features, revealing that optimal predictions are achieved with three PCs, matching the number of target analytes and indicating minimal non-linearity in the system. RMSEs for concentration predictions ranged from 1.77 ppm to 5.74 ppm across methane, ethane, and propane

in the test dataset, values that are consistent with the fundamental detection limits of the sensor and demonstrate that multivariate analysis does not introduce significant additional uncertainty.

Another central contribution of this work is the comprehensive characterisation of RAM and its impact on PA WMS. The wavelength-modulation-generated PA signal was shown to be proportional to the mean optical power, while the RAM-generated signal was proportional to the modulated optical power. This research demonstrates that RAM effects can be partially removed from the wavelength-modulation PA signal by isolating it in the quadrature component of the PA signal. This fundamental insight enables improved spectral interpretation and provides a pathway for data-processing strategies mitigating RAM effects in PAS.

The most significant theoretical and practical advancement presented in this thesis is the introduction of IE modulation. A comprehensive mathematical framework has been developed that enables direct calculation of the MZM output in the frequency domain, accounting for triangular phase modulation required to produce sinusoidal intensity output. Experimental validation using a free-beam MZI with a LT electro-optic phase shifter confirmed the analytical predictions with a half-wave voltage of 1.697 kV and an interference efficiency factor of (0.51 ± 0.04) .

The concept of IE modulation enables two distinct operational modes: IE intensity modulation, where destructive and constructive interference are alternated to achieve strong intensity modulation with minimal wavelength variation (demonstrated with an 83 % reduction in residual wavelength modulation), and IE wavelength modulation, where operation at stationary points of the interference pattern enables wavelength variation with minimal intensity change (demonstrated with over 90 % reduction in the derivative of intensity with respect to wavelength).

The thesis has also provided a comprehensive analysis of the magnitude and phase behaviour of PA signals in resonant cells. By modelling the PA cell as a damped harmonic oscillator, excellent agreement between theoretical predictions and experimental measurements was achieved. This framework not only validates the acoustic design but

also offers a practical method for continuous resonance tracking capabilities that are essential for maintaining optimal sensor performance in field applications.

6.2 Limitations and Challenges

Although this research has made significant advances, there are several limitations that deserve acknowledgement. For instance, the separation of RAM from the wavelength modulation signal through phase adjustment of the lock-in amplifier is incomplete, only a portion of the RAM can be isolated to the quadrature component.

The IE modulation implementation utilised a free-beam Mach-Zehnder configuration, which is sensitive to mechanical vibrations, thermal drift and beam misalignment. The measured interference-efficiency factor of (0.51 ± 0.04) indicates that approximately half of the theoretical interference contrast was lost to practical imperfections. Future implementations would benefit from integrated photonic approaches or fibre-based interferometers, which offer improved mechanical stability and reduced sensitivity to environmental perturbations.

The PA sensor calibration was performed using trace gas concentrations up to 100 ppm, which avoids saturation effects that occur at higher concentrations. Extending the operational range to percent-level concentrations would require careful characterisation of non-linear effects.

In the multivariate analysis, the prediction accuracy for propane was consistently lower than for methane and ethane. This is attributed to propane's broader and weaker absorption within the wavelength range accessible with the ICL used. The analysis of the isolated in-phase component revealed improved prediction accuracy for methane and ethane but degraded performance for propane, suggesting complex interactions between RAM and quantitative analysis that require further investigation.

Glossary

absorbance: The absorbance (A) is a dimensionless quantity that describes to what extent a material absorbs light at a given wavelength. A distinction is made between *decadic* and *Napierian* absorbance. In this thesis, only the latter is used. It is defined as

$$A = -\ln(I - \alpha),$$

where l is the sample length and α is the absorption coefficient.

absorption coefficient: The absorption coefficient α in m^{-1} quantifies how much light is absorbed per unit distance as it travels through the sample. A distinction is made between *decadic* and *Napierian* absorbance. In this thesis, only the latter is used. It is defined as

$$\alpha = \frac{A}{l},$$

where A is the absorbance and l is the sample length.

Allan deviation: The Allan deviation is a measure of the stability of a signal over time, commonly used in time-series analysis to characterize noise and drift. It is particularly useful in evaluating the performance of sensors and oscillators.

chopper: A chopper is a mechanical device used to modulate the intensity of the incident light beam at a specific frequency. A rotating disk with slots or holes is typically used. As it rotates in the path of a continuous light beam, it periodically blocks and unblocks the light, producing a modulated light beam.

coherence length: The coherence length l_c in m is the distance over which a coherent wave (e.g. laser light) maintains a specified degree of coherence. It is defined as

$$l_c = \frac{c}{\delta\nu},$$

where c is the speed of light and $\delta\nu$ is the spectral width of the light source.

coherent: In general, a distinction is made between temporal and spatial coherence. Both of these are based on a single phenomenon: the correlation between light waves. Temporal coherence refers to the consistency of a light wave's phase over time, which is also related to its spectral purity (i.e. monochromaticity). Lateral spatial coherence refers to the consistency of phase across the wavefront. High coherence enables light to produce clear interference patterns.

conduction band: The conduction band is the lowest unfilled band of electronic energy levels in a semiconductor. It is the band where electrons can move freely, allowing for electrical conduction [57].

correlation coefficient: The correlation coefficient is normalised covariance between -1 and $+1$ and is defined by [88,115]

$$\text{corr}(x, y) = \frac{\text{cov}(x, y)}{\text{var}(x)\text{var}(y)} = \frac{\text{cov}(x, y)}{s_x s_y}.$$

covariance: The covariance of two random variables, x and y , is a measure of their relationship, indicating the extent to which they change together, either in similar or opposite ways [115]. It can be calculated as

$$\text{cov}(x, y) = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y}),$$

where x_i and y_i are the individual values of the two variables, and \bar{x} and \bar{y} are their respective means. In this study, only the unbiased *sample covariance* is used.

cuvette: A cuvette is a small, transparent container used to hold liquid or gas samples for spectroscopic analysis.

dimensionality reduction: Dimensionality reduction is the process of reducing the number of input variables in a dataset while preserving its essential information.

half-wave voltage: The half-wave voltage $V_{\lambda/2}$ is the voltage applied to a phase shifter required to shift the phase ϕ by π .

heat power density: The heat power density is defined as heat flux per unit volume. In PA, it is determined by the heat released from all non-radiative de-excitation processes within the sample, along with its spatial distribution. The latter is governed by the laser beam profile and the absorption path length [52].

interband: Interband refers to the transition of electrons between the valence band and the conduction band in a semiconductor. The band gap is the energy difference between these bands and has a value between 0.1 and 3 eV [57].

molar absorption coefficient: The molar (linear) (Napierian) absorption coefficient ε_{mol} , also known as the absorbance cross-section per mole in $\text{m}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$, quantifies the effective area per mole of molecules that absorb light at a given wavelength.

monochromatic: Monochromatic light consists of a single wavelength (or frequency).

principal component: A principal component is a linear combination of the original variables, that points in the direction of maximum variance in the dataset, provided it is orthogonal (uncorrelated) to all previous components.

quantum well: In ICLs, the term *quantum well* refers to a structure in which the lasing semiconductor is embedded between two wider-bandgap semiconductor regions with opposite doping types, forming

a quantum well that confines both electrons and holes. These potential barriers prevent electrons from flowing into the p-type region and holes from escaping into the n-type region [116].

sound: Sound can be described as the propagation of pressure variations through a medium. The sound pressure p in Pa is the local deviation from the ambient (static) atmospheric pressure p_{amb} caused by a sound wave. It can usually be regarded as small-amplitude perturbations to the ambient state. The threshold of hearing for a human with acute hearing at 1 kHz is considered to be $p_{\text{min}} = 20 \mu\text{Pa}$ [117].

sound pressure level: The sound pressure level L_p in dB is a logarithmic measure of the effective sound pressure of a sound relative to a reference value. It is defined as

$$L_p = 20 \log\left(\frac{p}{p_{\text{ref}}}\right),$$

where p is the sound pressure and p_{ref} is the reference sound pressure, typically taken as $p_{\text{ref}} = 20 \mu\text{Pa}$ [117].

standard deviation: The standard deviation is a measure of dispersion. It gives the average distance of each element in a sample from the arithmetic mean. In this study, only the *sample standard deviation*, given by

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2},$$

is used. The sample contains the values x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n and has the sample mean \bar{x} [115].

standard error: The standard error measures the expected variability of a sample statistic due to sampling. It decreases as sample size increases. In this study, only the *standard error of the mean* is considered

$$\Delta x = \frac{s_x}{\sqrt{N}},$$

with the sample standard deviation s_x and the sample size N .

valence band: The valence band is the highest filled band of electronic energy levels in a semiconductor. It is the band where electrons are bound to atoms and cannot move freely [57].

variable selection: Variable selection is the process of identifying and retaining the most relevant variables from a dataset, effectively filtering out less significant factors.

variance: The variance is the mean square deviation of a real random variable from its expected value, e.g. the square of the standard deviation s^2 . In this study, only the *sample variance* is used [115].

Appendix A

Supplement: Design of the PA Sensor

The following supplementary material belongs to Section 3.

Figure A-1: Raw measurement of acoustic resonance.

```

1 def AllanDeviation(dataArr: np.ndarray, fs: float, maxNumM: int=100):
2     """Compute the Allan deviation (sigma) of time-series data.
3
4     Algorithm inspired by Mathworks documentation:
5     https://www.mathworks.com/help/fusion/ug/inertial-sensor-noise-analysis-
6     using-allan-variance.html
7
8     Args
9     ----
10
11         dataArr: 1D data array
12         fs: Data sample frequency in Hz
13         maxNumM: Number of output points
14
15     Returns
16     -----
17
18         (taus, allanDev): Tuple of results
19         taus (numpy.ndarray): Array of tau values
20         allanDev (numpy.ndarray): Array of computed Allan deviations
21
22     """
23     ts = 1.0 / fs
24     N = len(dataArr)
25     Mmax = 2**np.floor(np.log2(N / 2))
26     M = np.logspace(np.log10(1), np.log10(Mmax), num=maxNumM)
27     M = np.ceil(M) # Round up to integer
28     M = np.unique(M) # Remove duplicates
29     taus = M * ts # Compute 'cluster durations' tau
30
31     # Compute Allan variance
32     allanVar = np.zeros(len(M))
33     for i, mi in enumerate(M):
34         twoMi = int(2 * mi)
35         mi = int(mi)
36         allanVar[i] = np.sum(
37             (dataArr[twoMi:N] - (2.0 * dataArr[mi:N-mi]) + dataArr[0:N-twoMi])**2
38         )
39
40     allanVar /= (2.0 * taus**2) * (N - (2.0 * M))
41     return (taus, np.sqrt(allanVar)) # Return deviation (dev = sqrt(var))

```

Algorithm A-1: Implementation of Allan Deviation calculation in Python.

Figure A-2: Photo of the PAC and ICL in the experimental setup.

Figure A-3: Photo of the MZI with tilting windows as PS.

Appendix B

Supplement: Mach–Zehnder Modulator in Frequency and Time Domain

The following supplementary material belongs to Section 4.2.

Table B-1: Values of the calculated discrete spectrum.

f / f_m	S_p
0	0.3118298
1	0.5102669
2	0.0877021
3	0.0296981
4	0.0154202
5	0.0095296

The following steps refer to the transformation of Equation (4-5) to Equation (4-8) in the main text. We use the properties of convolution with a shifted Dirac delta function

$$\underline{S}(f) * \delta(f - a) = S(f - a) \quad (\text{B-1})$$

to transform Equation (4-5) to Equation (B-2)

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{S}(f) = & \frac{T_m}{4} \left[\text{sinc} \left(\frac{(\pi f - \varphi_m f_m) T_m}{2} \right) e^{j\varphi_0} e^{-j(\pi f - \varphi_m f_m) T_m / 2} \right. \\
& + \left. \text{sinc} \left(\frac{(\pi f + \varphi_m f_m) T_m}{2} \right) e^{-j\varphi_0} e^{j(\pi f + \varphi_m f_m) T_m / 2} \right] \\
& + \frac{T_m}{4} \left[\text{sinc} \left(\frac{(\pi f - \varphi_m f_m) T_m}{2} \right) e^{-j\varphi_0} e^{j(\pi f - \varphi_m f_m) T_m / 2} \right. \\
& + \left. \text{sinc} \left(\frac{(\pi f + \varphi_m f_m) T_m}{2} \right) e^{j\varphi_0} e^{j(\pi f + \varphi_m f_m) T_m / 2} \right] \\
& + s_{\text{DC}} T_m \text{sinc}(\pi f T_m).
\end{aligned} \tag{B-2}$$

By factoring out, we can simplify Equation Equation (B-2) to

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{S}(f) = & \frac{T_m}{4} \left[\text{sinc} \left(\frac{(\pi f - \varphi_m f_m) T_m}{2} \right) (e^{j\varphi_0} e^{-j(\pi f - \varphi_m f_m) T_m / 2} + e^{-j\varphi_0} e^{j(\pi f - \varphi_m f_m) T_m / 2}) \right. \\
& + \left. \text{sinc} \left(\frac{(\pi f + \varphi_m f_m) T_m}{2} \right) (e^{-j\varphi_0} e^{-j(\pi f + \varphi_m f_m) T_m / 2} + e^{j\varphi_0} e^{j(\pi f + \varphi_m f_m) T_m / 2}) \right] \\
& + s_{\text{D}} T_m \text{sinc}(\pi f T_m)
\end{aligned} \tag{B-3}$$

with the use of $\cos(x) = 0.5e^{jx} + 0.5e^{-jx}$ and utilizing $T_m = 1/f_m$, we obtain the much shorter and simpler form.

Appendix C

Supplement: Interferometrically Enhanced Modulation and TDLs

The following supplementary material belongs to Section 4.3.

Refraction at the Boundary between CaF₂ and Air

Figure C-4: Angle of incidence α and angle of refraction β of a refracted ray in a CaF₂ window.

The refractive index of CaF₂ is $n_{\text{CaF}_2} = 1.4152$, at 3.35 μm and 24 °C [109,110].

The law of refraction at the boundary between two media is [77]

$$\sin(\beta) = \sin(\alpha) \frac{n_{\text{air}}}{n_{\text{CaF}_2}}. \quad (\text{C-4})$$

The Brewster angle in the case of external reflection is [77]

$$\alpha_{\text{Brewster}} = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{n_{\text{CaF2}}}{n_{\text{air}}}\right) = 54.755^\circ. \quad (\text{C-5})$$

and in the case of internal reflection

$$\beta_{\text{Brewster}} = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{n_{\text{air}}}{n_{\text{CaF2}}}\right) = 35.245^\circ. \quad (\text{C-6})$$

The critical angle in the case of total internal reflection is [77]

$$\beta_{\text{crit}} = \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{n_{\text{air}}}{n_{\text{CaF2}}}\right) = 44.958^\circ. \quad (\text{C-7})$$

```

1 float goertzel(unsigned short x[], int length, float freq, int samplerate) {
2     // Calculate magnitude at a given frequency of the input signal
3     float yr, yi, mag;
4
5     // Precalculation of constants
6     float omega = 2 * M_PI * freq / samplerate;
7     float ci = sin(omega);
8     float cr = cos(omega);
9     float coeff = 2 * cr;
10
11     // State variables
12     float s0 = 0;
13     float s1 = 0;
14     float s2 = 0;
15
16     for (int i = 0; i < length; i++) {
17         s0 = (float)(x[i]) + coeff * s1 - s2;
18         s2 = s1;
19         s1 = s0;
20     }
21     // Finalizing calculations
22     s0 = coeff * s1 - s2;
23
24     // Scaling factor = length / 2
25     yr = (float)(s0 - s1 * cr) / length * 2;
26     yi = (float)(s1 * ci) / length * 2;
27
28     // Calculate amplitude (magnitude of the Goertzel response at the target
29     // frequency)
30     mag = sqrt(yr * yr + yi * yi);
31     return mag;
32 }

```

Algorithm C-2: Implementation of Gorzel algorithm in C.

Appendix D

Supplement: Quantitative PA

Spectrum Analysis

Table D-2: Steps of the NIPALS algorithm.

Step	Math	Description
		The data matrix (\mathbf{X}) and the matrix of the target variables (\mathbf{Y}) are in centre-centred form
0	$\mathbf{E} \leftarrow \mathbf{X}$	Without principal components ($\mathbf{TP}^\top = 0$) the residuals (\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{F}) correspond to the matrices of the influence and target variables (\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y})
0	$\mathbf{F} \leftarrow \mathbf{Y}$	
	for i in $1, \dots, l$	Outer loop of the NIPALS algorithm, number of principal components (l):
1	$\mathbf{u}_i \leftarrow \mathbf{f}$	The score vector (\mathbf{u}) is initialised with the first column of the remaining residual matrix (\mathbf{F})
	do	Inner loop of the NIPALS algorithm:
2	$\mathbf{w}_i \leftarrow \frac{\mathbf{E}^\top \mathbf{u}_i}{\mathbf{u}_i^\top \mathbf{u}_i}$	Weights (\mathbf{w}) from the residual residuals (\mathbf{E}).
2	$\mathbf{w}_i \leftarrow \frac{\mathbf{w}_i}{\sqrt{\mathbf{w}_i^\top \mathbf{w}_i}}$	Normalisation of the weights to the amount one ($ \mathbf{w} = 1$).
3	$\mathbf{t}_i \leftarrow \mathbf{E} \mathbf{w}_i$	The scores (\mathbf{t}) are calculated from the weights
4	$\mathbf{c}_i \leftarrow \frac{\mathbf{F}^\top \mathbf{t}_i}{\mathbf{t}_i^\top \mathbf{t}_i}$	The weights (\mathbf{c}) are calculated from the scores
5	$\mathbf{u}_i \leftarrow \frac{\mathbf{F} \mathbf{c}_i}{\mathbf{c}_i^\top \mathbf{c}_i}$	The scores (\mathbf{u}) are calculated from the weights
	while $\Delta \mathbf{w}_i > 1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	The cancellation criterion is met if \mathbf{w} no longer changes significantly (convergence is achieved)
6	$\mathbf{p}_i \leftarrow \frac{\mathbf{E}^\top \mathbf{t}_i}{\mathbf{t}_i^\top \mathbf{t}_i}$	The loadings (\mathbf{p}) are calculated from the scores
6	$\mathbf{q}_i \leftarrow \frac{\mathbf{F}^\top \mathbf{t}_i}{\mathbf{t}_i^\top \mathbf{t}_i}$	The loadings (\mathbf{q}) are calculated from the scores
7	$\mathbf{E} \leftarrow \mathbf{E} - \mathbf{t}_i \mathbf{p}_i^\top$	
7	$\mathbf{F} \leftarrow \mathbf{F} - \mathbf{t}_i \mathbf{q}_i^\top$	

Figure D-5: Photo of the MFCs of the gas handling system.

Table D-3: Prediction error for 3 PCs

Dataset	Methane / ppm	Ethane / ppm	Propane / ppm
Training CV	(0.00 ± 5.20)	(-0.00 ± 4.80)	(0.05 ± 9.72)
Validation	(-0.92 ± 3.77)	(-0.13 ± 3.88)	(1.44 ± 2.48)
Testing	(0.28 ± 1.77)	(-0.54 ± 2.75)	(4.99 ± 2.89)

Table D-4: Prediction error of the in-phase dataset for 3 PCs.

Dataset	Methane / ppm	Ethane / ppm	Propane / ppm
Training CV	(-0.02 ± 3.66)	(-0.01 ± 3.14)	(-0.00 ± 21.39)
Validation	(0.19 ± 2.59)	(0.45 ± 1.39)	(-3.59 ± 7.68)
Testing	(1.14 ± 1.74)	(0.86 ± 1.06)	(16.92 ± 8.87)

Table D-5: Prediction error of the quadrature dataset for 3 PCs

Dataset	Methane / ppm	Ethane / ppm	Propane / ppm
Training CV	(-0.25 ± 11.90)	(0.07 ± 6.32)	(0.17 ± 22.49)
Validation	(6.25 ± 11.75)	(-0.30 ± 3.01)	(-4.69 ± 12.90)
Testing	(9.41 ± 4.50)	(1.73 ± 2.78)	(10.21 ± 7.09)

Appendix E

Publications and Conference Contributions

E.1 List of Publications

The following publications were published as part of this doctoral thesis. All publications are open access and can be found in the references.

Multivariate Spectra Analysis: PLSR vs. PCA + MLR S. Vervoort and M. Wolff, *Eng. Proc.* 2020, 2, 83-86 (2020) [118].

Mach-Zehnder Modulator Output in Time and Frequency Domain – Calculation and Experimental Confirmation S. Vervoort, Y. Saalberg and M. Wolff, *Photonics, Special Issue: Emerging Frontiers in Photoacoustic Spectroscopy Detection*, 10, 337 (2023) [37].

Interferometrically Enhanced Intensity and Wavelength Modulation in Tunable Diode Laser Spectroscopy S. Vervoort and M. Wolff, *Photonics, Special Issue: 10th Anniversary*, 2024, 11 740 (2024) [38].

E.2 List of Conference Contributions

Contributions were made to the following conferences as part of this doctoral thesis.

IABR Breath Summit 2018 (The International Association of Breath Research)

Y. Saalberg, S. Vervoort and M. Wolff, *Photoacoustic analyzer for lung cancer biomarkers*, Maastricht/The Netherlands (2018), see Appendix E.3.

Breathomics 2019 S. Vervoort and M. Wolff, *Multivariate Analysis of Photoacoustic Biomarker Spectra*, Manchester/UK (2019), see Appendix E.4.

- 20th International Conference on Photoacoustic and Photothermal Phenomena (ICPPP20)** S. Vervoort, M. Wolff, *Comparison of techniques for multivariate analysis of photoacoustic spectra*, EP040, Moscow/Russia (2019), see Appendix E.6.
- 7th International Electronic Conference on Sensors and Applications (ECSA-7)** S. Vervoort and M. Wolff, *Spectroscopic selectivity of multivariate analysis techniques*, A. Chemo- and Bio Sensors, sciforum-036600 (2020), see Appendix E.5.
- UWS Research Festival 2022** S. Vervoort, *Photoacoustic Sensor for Breath Analysis*, University of the West of Scotland, Paisley/UK (2022), see Appendix E.7.
- 5th International Workshop on Opportunities and Challenges in mid-infrared Laser-based Gas Sensing (Mirsens 5)** S. Vervoort, M. A. Pitir and M. Wolff, *QEPAS Module for a Mach-Zehnder modulated OPO*, Wroclaw/Poland (2022), see Appendix E.8.
- 21st International Conference on Photoacoustic and Photothermal Phenomena (ICPPP21)** S. Vervoort, M. Wolff, *New Voltage Control Technique for Mach-Zehnder Modulators*, Session 8. Novel Methodologies, Instrumentation, and Applications, Bled/Slovenia (2022), see Appendix E.9.
- 22nd International Conference on Photoacoustic and Photothermal Phenomena (ICPPP22)** S. Vervoort and M. Wolff, *Interferometrically Enhanced Diode Laser Modulation*, P44, Coimbra/Portugal (2024), see Appendix E.10.

E.3 IABR Breath Summit 2018: Photoacoustic Analyzer for Lung Cancer Biomarkers

Wolff, M.¹, Saalberg, Y.¹ and Vervoort, S.¹

In 2016, a systematic literature review identified volatile organic compounds (VOCs) that could serve as lung cancer biomarkers for future breath tests. In order of priority, the six most relevant substances are 2-butanone, 1-propanol, isoprene, ethylbenzene, styrene and hexanal. A sensitive and selective detection of the six biomarkers could enable future lung cancer diagnostics via breath tests. Methods: Photoacoustic spectroscopy (PAS) is an established method for the detection of trace gases and the analysis of gaseous samples. It is based on the absorption of electromagnetic radiation. The thermal relaxation of the excited molecules leads to an increase of pressure. If the radiation is periodically modulated, it will result in an acoustic wave with the same frequency. We developed a photoacoustic analyzer based on a continuous-wave optical parametric oscillator (cw-OPO) as radiation source and an all-optical Mach-Zehnder modulator. The photoacoustic signal is detected by a digital MEMS microphone. The photoacoustic spectrum is then evaluated by multivariate analysis. Results: The multivariate Partial Least Squares (PLS) Regression was configured to calculate the concentrations of the six listed biomarkers from photoacoustic spectra of gas mixtures in the wavelength region of 3 250 nm to 3 550 nm. The derived concentrations showed a standard deviation from the true concentration of 2.60 %, without a priori knowledge of the possible concentration levels. The root mean square error (RMSE) of the dataset equaled 2.79 ppm. Conclusions: The new photoacoustic analyzer proved both, high detection sensitivity and selectivity for the six VOCs that could serve as lung cancer biomarkers for future breath tests. The system can be configured for other multicomponent analyses as well.

Presentation available [119].

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E.4 Breathomics 2019 Abstract: Multivariate analysis of photoacoustic biomarker spectra

Vervoort, S.¹ and Wolff, M.¹

Photoacoustic spectroscopy (PAS) is an extremely sensitive method for the detection of trace gases. It is based on the absorption of electromagnetic radiation and the non-radiating transfer of the absorbed energy into heat. If the radiation is periodically modulated, expansion of the absorbing gas results in an acoustic wave with the modulation frequency (*K.H. Michaelian, Photoacoustic IR spectroscopy, Wiley-VCH, 2010*). We developed a photoacoustic analyzer for volatile organic compounds (VOCs) that could serve in future breath tests for the detection of the lung cancer biomarkers 2-butanone, 1-propanol, isoprene, ethylbenzene, styrene and hexanal (*Clin. Chim. Acta 2016, 459:5-9*). The analyzer is based on a continuous-wave optical parametric oscillator (cw-OPO) as radiation source and an all-optical Mach-Zehnder modulator. The photoacoustic signal is detected by a digital MEMS microphone (*Sensors 2017, 17(1):210*).

The concentrations of the single components are determined by multivariate analysis of the photoacoustic spectra. In this process it has to be considered that interdependencies of predictor variables (PA signal) could negatively affect the accuracy of the results. A variable selection or dimension reduction can prevent this (*H. Martens, M. Martens, Introduction to Multivariate Data Analysis for Understanding Quality, J. Wiley, 2000*). The following methods were compared for the analysis of photoacoustic biomarker spectra:

- Multiple Linear Regression (MLR),
- variable selection by Random Forest approach (RF) and subsequent MLR,
- dimension reduction by Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and subsequent MLR,
- Partial Least Squares Regression (PLS).

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RF, PCA and PLS showed increased accuracy (smaller error) and increased precision (higher cross-validation score) compared to MLR. PLS provided the best results.

E.5 7th International Electronic Conference on Sensors and Applications; Session: Chemo- and Biosensors: Spectroscopic Selectivity of Multivariate Analysis Techniques

Wolff, M.¹ and Vervoort, S.¹

Optical spectroscopy is based on the interaction between electromagnetic radiation and matter. As measured spectra of single substances are characteristic like a fingerprint, they can be used to identify atoms and molecules. Concentrations can be determined by the magnitudes of the individual features of the spectra. However, if the investigated sample is composed of different substances, the individual spectra may overlap and are sometimes hard to differentiate. This often applies to larger molecules where the spectra differ only slightly in their characteristic features. In this case multivariate analysis methods can be instrumental to decompose the superimposed spectra. The regression analysis focuses on the correlation between spectral features and concentrations of individual substances. To increase the prediction accuracy of regression, the dataset can be prepared by a feature selection or feature projection, which helps to reduce the influence of noise in the dataset by reducing its dimension.

We analyzed photoacoustic spectra of mixtures of different volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in the infrared wavelength region. The spectral features of the single substances are broad and overlap strongly. For trace gases with weak absorption, the features of the photoacoustic spectrum are quasi linearly proportional to the concentration, hence linear methods can be applied in this case. Different combinations of feature selection, feature projection and regression are compared to demonstrate

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their strengths and weaknesses and to determine the combination with the highest detection selectivity.

Presentation available [120].

E.6 20th International Conference on Photoacoustic and Photothermal Phenomena (ICPPP20)

Comparison of techniques for multivariate analysis of photoacoustic spectra

Sander Vervoort^{1,2} and Marcus Wolff¹

- Hamburg University of Applied Sciences, Heinrich Blasius Institute for Physical Technologies
- University of the West of Scotland, School of Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences

Motivation

- Early detection of lung cancer (LC) by breath tests:
- LC has the highest incidence and mortality rate of all cancer types [1].
 - Chance of surviving LC: 45% in early stage, 1% in late stage [2].
 - Early detection is currently not available.

Exhaled air of patients with lung cancer shows an altered VOC pattern compared to healthy probands. Lung cancer biomarkers: **2-butanone, 1-propanol, isoprene, ethylbenzene, styrene and hexanal** [3,4].

Photoacoustic spectroscopy (PAS)

- PAS is an extremely sensitive method for the detection of trace gases.
- PAS is based on the absorption of electromagnetic radiation and the non-radiating transfer of the absorbed energy into heat. If the radiation is periodically modulated, expansion of the absorbing gas results in an acoustic wave with the modulation frequency [5,6].

Radiation source: Continuous-wave Optical Parametric Oscillator (cw-OPO).

Modulator: All-optical Mach-Zehnder modulator.

PA signal detector: Digital MEMS microphone.

Multivariate analysis (MVA)

The concentrations of the single VOCs are determined by multivariate analysis of the photoacoustic spectra. A dimension reduction (feature subset selection or feature extraction) can prevent negative effects on the accuracy due to interdependencies in the spectra [7].

Regression

Modelling the relationship (**b**) between dependent (**y**) and explanatory (**x**) variables.

Simple linear regression: one explanatory variable (**x**).

Multiple linear regression (MLR): multiple explanatory variables (**X**).

$$y = Xb + e$$

Results

- Feature subset selection RF and BE.
- Feature extraction PCA and PLS.

Regression method	Error (nMAE) %	cross-validation %
MLR	ref	ref
RF + MLR	- 2.77	+0.339
BE + MLR	- 3.82	-0.090
PCA + MLR	-13.73	+4.091
PLS	-14.84	+4.317

Feature subset selection

Selecting a subset (**A**) of relevant features from the initial set of variables (**X**).

Filter method: low variance or high correlation filter.

Wrapper method: forward selection or backward elimination (BE).

Embedded method: decision tree based like random forest (RF).

$$A \subset X$$

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Feature extraction

Building informative and non-redundant features (**T**) from the initial set of variables (**X**).

Unsupervised learning: factor analysis or principal component analysis (PCA).

Supervised learning: partial least squares (PLS) regression.

Scores (**T**), weights (**P**) and residuals (**E**).

$$X = TP^T + E$$

E.7 UWS Research Festival 2022

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Photoacoustic Sensor for Diagnostic Breath Analysis

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E.8 5th International Workshop on Opportunities and Challenges in MIR Laser-based Gas Sensing

QEPAS Module for a Mach-Zehnder modulated OPO

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Abstract

Due to its extremely high detection sensitivity the concept of quartz-enhanced photoacoustic spectroscopy (QEPAS) became increasingly popular. QEPAS utilizes a quartz tuning fork as acoustic detector, thus, replacing the microphone. The high sensitivity of this approach is owed to the fact that the tuning fork represents an active band-pass filter amplifying only acoustic signals of a very narrow frequency band [1]. We applied the QEPAS concept in combination with an Optical Parametric Oscillator (OPO). This radiation source is widely tunable in the mid-infrared spectral range and, therefore, particularly suited for the analysis of complex gas mixtures [2]. The OPO modulation which must be kept stable within the narrow frequency band of the tuning fork is realized with an electro-optical Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM) [3]. In order to perfectly combine the advantages of QEPAS and Mach-Zehnder modulated OPO we designed a new acoustic detection module (ADM). It employs a conventional quartz tuning fork with a resonance frequency of 32.768 kHz. The respective off-beam micro resonator is specifically designed for the tuning fork and the beam dimensions. The ADM is modular, mechanically highly customizable and consists of 3D printed components. The first figure shows the schematic experimental setup.

Experimental Setup

The radiation of the CW-OPO is intensity modulated by a MZM. The gaseous sample is contained in the ADM. When modulated radiation is absorbed by the sample, a photoacoustic signal occurs, which is measured by the quartz enhanced spectrophone.

- CW-OPO** Continuous Wave Optical Parametric Oscillator with a spectral range from 3.2 to 3.5 μm at 2 W, beam width of 3 mm.
- MZM** Mach-Zehnder intensity Modulator 32.768 KHz modulation frequency.
- ADM** Acoustic Detection Module with quartz enhanced spectrophone results in 5 Hz bandpass.
- PDA** Amplified Photo Detector up to 9 MHz sampling frequency.

Results

The frequency response of the tuning fork shows the narrow band pass filter characteristic of QEPAS.

The next step is to compare different resonators, utilising acoustic longitudinal, azimuthal and radial modes. As well as different positions of the quartz tuning fork, to find the best solution in terms of signal to noise ratio.

Off-Beam QEPAS Module

The quartz enhanced spectrophone is located in the ADM, surrounded by the sample gas. The lenses to reduce the beam diameter to the size of the microresonator also serve as gas-tight windows. The microresonator contains a central outlet where a tuning fork captures the PA signal.

The ADM is designed in two parts to ensure quick access to the adjustment options. The microresonator is easily interchangeable and the position of the tuning fork is adjustable in all directions.

- Lens** 12.7 mm CaF₂ plano-convex lenses, uncoated, back focal length 37.8 mm, transmission over 90%.
- Acoustic micro-resonator** Stainless steel, inner diameter 2 mm, outer diameter 2.2 mm, length 3.54 mm, signal outlet diameter 150 μm .
- Quartz tuning fork** Distance between prongs 300 μm , length of prongs 3.7 mm, resonance frequency 32.768 kHz.
- Plug** 4-pole LEMO connector, watertight and vacuum-tested.
- Gas handling system** 1/4" Swagelok Connector (ISO Tapered Thread) - Metric.
- Embedded adjustment** x-, y-, z-axis adjustment of spectrophone, 3D-printed holder in PLA (Polyamide) for quartz tuning fork and acoustic micro-resonator.

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E.9 21st International Conference on Photoacoustic and Photothermal Phenomena (ICPPP21)

New Voltage Control Technique for Mach-Zehnder Modulators

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Introduction

For amplitude-modulated Photoacoustic Spectroscopy the optical power of the laser must vary periodically to excite the sample in a way that an acoustic signal develops. An electro-optic modulation can be achieved by a Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM), consisting of a Pockels Cell (PC) and a Mach-Zehnder Interferometer [1, 2]. However, MZMs often suffer from phase drifts that cause operating point fluctuations and signal instabilities. By controlling the bias voltage of the PC it is possible to maintain its quadrature operating point [3]. From the ratio between the average output power and the first-order harmonic signal the required bias correction can be calculated. An approach using a Fast Fourier Transform to control the PC bias voltage achieved stable operation (phase shift: $\pm 0.08^\circ$ over three hours) [4]. Since the optical wavelength influences the required half-wave voltage of the PC, measurements over a wider spectral range, such as with an Optical Parametric Oscillator, require a control loop for both, the half-wave and the bias voltage to maintain its optimum operation point. We developed a new concept of a control loop based on Discrete Fourier Transform that allows control of both voltages simultaneously.

Experimental Setup

Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM) operation

- The continuous-wave laser is divided equally into two partial waves by a beam splitter (left).
- Subsequently, one beam is phase-modulated by the Pockels Cell (PC).
- When the two beams reunite behind the second beam splitter (right), interference leads to intensity-modulated output [5].

Concept

The intensity modulated signal of the MZM is described by

$$I_o = I_{in} \cos^2 \frac{\Delta\varphi}{2}, \quad \text{with} \quad \Delta\varphi = \varphi_0 - \pi \frac{V}{V_{A/2}}$$

The voltage applied to the PC is the sum of the bias voltage and the amplitude modulation voltage

$$V = V_{bias} + V_{mod}$$

The voltages V_{bias} and V_{mod} represent the variables manipulated by the controller. The transformed optical signal $I(f)$ serves as the corresponding feedback for the control loop. Just the signals at the fundamental frequency f_0 and at the harmonics f_i of the spectrum are evaluated.

Results

In the figure below three states of the modulation by a MZM are shown. There are clear differences between the influence of V_{bias} and V_{mod} .

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E.10 22nd International Conference on Photo-acoustic and Photothermal Phenomena (ICPPP22)

Interferometrically Enhanced Diode Laser Modulation

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Introduction

Tunable Diode Laser Spectroscopy (TDLS) is an analytical method with high spectral resolution. It is based on tuning the emission wavelength of a semiconductor laser by adjusting its current and/or temperature. However, adjusting the wavelength leads to a change in the emission intensity. The combination of TDLS with interferometric techniques, such as a Mach-Zehnder interferometer (see Fig. 1), enhances the modulation of either the wavelength or the intensity while keeping the other nearly constant. We have presented a mathematical description of the signal of a Mach-Zehnder modulator in the frequency and time domain in a previous publication [1].

Experimental Setup

Figure 1: Schematic of the experimental setup.

Components

- ICL Interband Cascade Laser, Nanoplus (Meiningen, Germany)
- BS 50:50 Beam Splitter
- M Silver Mirror
- PS Phase Shifter
- Sample Gas Cell
- PD Photodiode

Concept

The basics of interference and the Mach-Zehnder interferometer can be found in [2]. More information about modulation in TDLS can be found in [3] and [4]. In our application, the following steps are important:

- Wavelength modulation of ICL** in combination with **wavelength dependent interference in MZI**, (Figure 2) resulting in **intensity modulation** with low residual wavelength modulation (Figure 3, left), or **wavelength modulation** with low residual intensity modulation (Figure 3, right).
- Signal generated by the Sample** may be lock-in amplified.

Figure 2: Intensity measurement of MZI output.

Results

Intensity modulation with over 83% lower residual wavelength modulation compared to traditional modulation (Figure 3, left).

Wavelength modulation with no residual intensity modulation at modulation frequency compared to traditional modulation (Figure 3, right).

Figure 3: Left: Intensity modulation. Right: Wavelength modulation.

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